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D6.3 Open Calls Report

DRG4FOOD

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Open Calls Report

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Executive summary

Deliverable D6.3, "Open Call #1 Report," is a public document that outlines the first Open Call for Enablers in the DRG4Food project. It covers the full timeline and key steps, starting with the call announcement on October 9th, 2023, ending on December 11th, 2023, the evaluation process finishing on February 20th, 2024, and the completion of sub-grant agreements by March 15th 2024.

This report provides a detailed overview of the entire Open Call #1 process, from announcement to the final agreements with selected projects.

Following the project review, this deliverable was updated to include information on the experts chosen to participate in remote evaluations, as well as the Evaluation Summary Reports

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Index of contents

Executive summary	3
1 Introduction	8
2 DRG4Food Open Call #1	9
2.1 Publication and Promotion.....	9
2.2 Open Call #1 Statistics	13
2.2.1 Matchmaking Service for DRG4Food - Open Call #1 Participants.....	13
2.2.2 Open Call #1.....	15
Evaluation, Ranking & Selection.....	20
2.3 Phase 1: Eligibility Check.....	20
2.4 Phase 2: Remote Evaluation	21
2.5 Final Selection & Awarded Teams	23
3 Contracting Phase	24
4 DRG4Food supporting activities for 3rd Parties	25
5 Conclusion.....	28
Annex I Evaluation Ranking and Pilot Project Selection for Contracting Phase	29
Annex II Information on Selected Applications	36
Annex III Call for Expression of Interest of Experts	38
Annex IV Guidelines for Evaluating Experts	39

Index of tables

Table 1 Reason for non-eligibility	21
Table 2 Payment schedule for DRG4FOOD – Open Call #1 funding programme.....	27

Index of figures

Figure 1 DRG4Food Open Call #1 Timeline	8
Figure 2 DRG4Food Open Call #1: Featured on EU Funding & Tenders Portal	9
Figure 3 DRG4Food Open Call #1 Highlighted on AgFunderNews	10
Figure 4 F6S Targeted Promo Email to Potential Applicants.....	10
Figure 5 DRG4Food Open Call #1 - Meetup in Novi Sad	11
Figure 6 Promo Events with DIH Agrifood & Sploro	12
Figure 7 Closing Notice for DRG4Food Open Call #1 on F6S	13
Figure 8 Comparison of Started vs Submitted Matchmaking Requests.....	14
Figure 9 Distribution of Matchmaking Requests by Country	14
Figure 10 DRG4Food Open Call #1: Applicants, Matchmaking Requests, and Resulting Submissions.....	15
Figure 11 Open Call #1 on F6S: 85 Submitted vs. 79 Unfinished Applications.....	15
Figure 12 Overview of Applications by Lead Applicant Country: Distribution Across 34 Countries	16
Figure 13 Total Applications by Consortium Partners: Spanning 38 Countries	17
Figure 14 Applications Finalized by Challenge Area.....	17
Figure 15 Consortium Composition (Overall).....	18
Figure 16 Consortium Composition (by challenge area)	18
Figure 17 Sources of Awareness for DRG4Food: Participant Responses.....	19
Figure 18 Eligible vs. Non-Eligible Proposals	21
Figure 19 Countries representation in selected proposals.....	23
Figure 20 DRG4Food supporting activities for 3rd Parties.....	25
Figure 21 DRG4Food Pilot Projects and Their Timeline.....	26

Abbreviations

DRG	Digital Responsibility Goals
FSTP	Financial Support to Third Parties
ISR	Individual Summary Report
ESR	Evaluation Summary Report

1 Introduction

The DRG4Food Open Call #1 aimed to fund **pilot projects** leveraging digital innovation in the food industry, focusing on **Food Tracking, Targeted Nutrition, and Consumer Food Choices**. This call invited 2 to 3 member consortia from Horizon Europe eligible countries and also Switzerland¹, including SMEs, startups, as per EU law (EU recommendation 2003/361), RTOs, universities, non-profit research organizations, alongside technology adopters/users within the food sector such as NGOs and consumer groups.

Projects were expected to demonstrate significant market potential and align with **Digital Responsibility Goals (DRGs)**, enhancing the economy and societal well-being through responsible, data-driven technology enablers.

Proposals required technologies at a minimum of **TRL 4 or 5**, with the prospect of reaching **TRL 7**.

The call offered a total of **€950,000** in funding, supporting 3 to 6 projects with budgets between **€150,000** and **€300,000** each, emphasizing **user needs, societal benefits, openness, user-centricity, sovereignty, and trust**.

The complete eligibility criteria and call conditions, along with the necessary annexes for proposal submission, were detailed in the **DRG4Food Open Call #1 Guidelines for Applicants**² (refer to D6.1 Open Call Documents Kit).

The submission period for DRG4Food Open Call #1 started on October 9, 2023, at 17:00 CET and ended on December 11, 2023, at 17:00 CET, exclusively through the F6S platform. Proposals submitted through any other means were not accepted.

The full process of DRG4Food Open Call #1 is illustrated in the following image:

Figure 1 DRG4Food Open Call #1 Timeline

¹ Swiss entities were welcome to participate as Associated Partners, however, they would not receive funding from DRG4Food and should secure financing from SERI or through their existing thirdparty main project funds.

² Available at: <https://drg4food.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/11/DRG4Food-Open-Call-1-Annex-A-Guidelines-for-Applicants-v1.2.pdf>

2 DRG4Food Open Call #1

2.1 Publication and Promotion

The announcement regarding DRG4Food Open Call #1 was made public through the F6S platform on October 9, 2023. A dedicated page was created on [F6S](#), providing access to the application form for the call. Prior to this, an online discussion group was initiated on F6S to facilitate the exchange of information related to the call.

Additional details and documentation concerning the call were available on the DRG4Food website, specifically on the Open Calls page (accessible via <https://drg4food.eu/open-calls/>), as well as on the [EU Funding & Tenders Portal](#).

The open calls page had 7044 unique visits by the call closing date.

Figure 2 DRG4Food Open Call #1: Featured on EU Funding & Tenders Portal

During Open Call #1, DRG4Food, with the collaboration of EUFIC and INOSENS, launched a comprehensive online campaign. This effort was focused on promoting the call, along with highlighting the available financial support, and business and technical assistance services, to reach our target audience.

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EUFIC³ distributed an official press release to prominent publications including [Innovationfoodsystem](#), [Alpha Galileo](#). Additionally, the press release garnered attention from [AgFunderNews](#), a renowned industry news site.

Funds, grants & accelerators

■ EU Horizon's **DRG4Food** accelerator launches first open call of €950,000 (\$1 million). The accelerator will support three projects (up to €300,000 each) developing data sharing systems for agrifood. *(The European Food Innovation Council)*

Figure 3 DRG4Food Open Call #1 Highlighted on AgFunderNews

In addition to DRG4Food's social media channels (with approximately 26k followers on Twitter (now called "X") @SciFoodHealth and around 2k followers on LinkedIn @SciFoodHealth), we extensively utilized our partners' social media platforms during Open Call #1. Consortium partners of DRG4Food were provided with a series of social media posts to share during the promotional period of the open call. Social media activity on LinkedIn up to December 11, 2023, included 23 posts, generating a total of 6,595 impressions and 455 engagements.

Additionally, we used the **F6S Platform**, targeted promo which reached approximately 3,300 startups.

Figure 4 F6S Targeted Promo Email to Potential Applicants

INOSENS organized official **guidelines webinars** to introduce the call, detailing eligibility criteria, the application process, evaluation procedures, and support activities:

- October 12th: [Presentation of application procedures for Open Call #1](#), with 96 registered attendees.
- November 21st: [Second webinar on Open Call #1 guidelines](#), with 129 registered attendees.

³ Available at: <https://www.eufic.org/en/newsroom/article/drg4foods-first-open-call-gives-up-to-300000-to-pilot-projects-building-a-trustworthy-data-driven-food-system>

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Webinar registration was managed through F6S, and announcements were posted in the News & Events section of the DRG4Food website. Information about the webinars was also disseminated on the FOOD 2030 Networks on Sustainable Food Systems Network platform.

Subsequently, recordings of the webinars were uploaded to YouTube for easy accessibility.

Additionally, INOSENS organized a **matchmaking session** to assist interested applicants in finding potential partners.

- September 14th, 2023: [MeetYourMatch webinar](#), where 10 potential applicants pitched their ideas. The session drew in 78 participants.

DRG4Food Open Call #1 event marketing and promotion highlights include:

- October 24th, 2023: the EEN health, digital, and agri sector group were informed about Open Call #1 through a presentation organized by EUFIC. Both F6S and INOSENS presented the Foodity and DRG4Food open calls.
- October 25th, 2023: INOSENS presented Open Call #1 during the [EU Funding Clinics Webinar](#) hosted by DIH Agrifood Slovenia, engaging 25 participants, primarily agrifood startups/SMEs.
- October 31st, 2023: INOSENS showcased Open Call #1 at the [Cascade Funding Opportunities – Session #6](#) webinar by Sploro, focusing on funding opportunities in AgTech and FoodTech sectors. Approximately 30 attendees, mainly SMEs and researchers, participated.
- November 15th, 2023: At the Conference on the Future of Food at Startit Center Belgrade, INOSENS was invited to introduce Open Call #1 to participants in the EWA (Empowering Women in Agrifood) program by EIT Food.
- November 16th, 2023: INOSENS organized a Meetup in Novi Sad, where Open Call #1 was presented to 30 attendees, predominantly researchers and agrifoodtech startups.

Figure 5 DRG4Food Open Call #1 - Meetup in Novi Sad

Prior to the launch of Open Call #1, close collaboration was forged with the FOODITY project:

- On July 4th, 2023, a joint webinar titled "Discover the funding opportunities of DRG4FOOD and FOODITY" attracted 99 registered attendees.

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Additionally, DRG4Food was invited to participate in FOODITY's official webinar, and reciprocally, FOODITY was invited to join a brief session during our Guidelines webinar.

The collaboration will continue into Open Call #2, with plans already underway for a joint matchmaking event. This event will draw on the best practices from DRG4Food's MeetYourMatch Session.

During the promotional phase of Open Call #1, significant efforts were made to engage with relevant professional networks, business support organizations, and accelerators/incubators. These activities aimed at maximizing outreach and ensuring effective dissemination both regionally and locally.

- Promotion via EEN Serbia to promote [matchmaking events](#), [webinars](#), and Open Call #1. Additionally, they are conducting regular outreach to **EEN Local Contact Points** through email, for example [Tera Tehnopolis](#) (EEN Croatia), [NCP Flanders.be](#)
- Promotion via [the Vojvodina ICT Cluster](#), one of the largest business associations in the Balkan region (by INOSENS), Digital Innovation Hubs (DIHs) such as: [DIHBU](#), [DHI4E](#);
- Promotion of Open Call #1 through the [Western Balkans Info Hub](#) - a platform that serves as a key source of high-quality, targeted information on research, technology, and innovation in, with, and for the Western Balkan countries (WBCs).
- Open Innovation community Helixes on [CrowdHelix](#), thematic platforms such as: [ICT Agrifood Meta Knowledge Base](#); [Fod2030 Online Platform](#).

Figure 6 Promo Events with DIH Agrifood & Sploro

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2.2 Open Call #1 Statistics

The DRG4Food Open Call #1 for technology enablers closed on Monday, December 11th, 2023, at 17:00 Brussels time with a **total of 85 applications submitted** through the F6S platform, the designated official call submission platform as outlined in the Open Call #1 Guidelines for Applicants.

Figure 7 Closing Notice for DRG4Food Open Call #1 on F6S

2.2.1 Matchmaking Service for DRG4Food - Open Call #1 Participants

During Open Call #1, INOSENS, serving as the manager of the call, launched a Matchmaking service⁴ to help potential applicants find partners and form consortia. This service was developed in response to requests from attendees of promotional webinars held before the call opened. Details of the service were provided in the Guidelines for Applicants, and the application form was made available on a special page on F6S.

The matchmaking application form only requested essential information required for application processing and follow-up, including contact person details, organization, and email. Additionally, applicants were prompted to provide a concise overview of their proposal, specify the challenge area for their DRG-focused solution, and outline the type of organizations they aimed to collaborate with. Moreover, applicants were asked to identify their expertise areas as well as specify the expertise areas they sought in potential partners. This matchmaking application form remained available throughout the entirety of Open Call #1.

All participants were advised that participation in the matchmaking process didn't guarantee acceptance into Open Call #1. Additionally, DRG4Food wasn't liable for matchmaking outcomes or participant agreements. Success depended on various factors. Therefore, participants were urged to exercise discretion and evaluate collaborations independently.

⁴ DRG4Food Matchmaking Service for Open Call #1 Participants was available at: <https://www.f6s.com/drg4food-open-call-1-matchmaking/>

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As illustrated in the figure below, we received a total of **14 matchmaking requests through F6S**. Additionally, 12 requests were initiated but not completed or submitted on the F6S platform.

Figure 8 Comparison of Started vs Submitted Matchmaking Requests

As depicted in the figure below, we received one matchmaking request from each of the following countries: Turkey, Tunisia, Italy, Latvia, South Korea, Portugal, Luxembourg, Bosnia and Herzegovina, and Greece. Germany stood out with three requests, and Estonia also made a notable contribution with two requests.

Figure 9 Distribution of Matchmaking Requests by Country

Interest across the DRG4Food challenge areas was closely matched. The Matchmaking service saw a slight preference for the "Consumers' food choices" challenge with 5 mentions, closely tailed by "Targeted Nutrition" and "Food Tracking," each receiving 4 mentions.

Given that the bulk of the requests (10 out of 14) originated from startups and SMEs, it makes sense that many were seeking collaborations with academic and research institutions, like universities and nonprofits (7 out of 14), as well as with technology users (3 out of 14).

In terms of desired partner expertise, there was a notable emphasis on "DRG-Related Topics," including aspects like data privacy and handling, which were of interest in 7 out of the 14 requests.

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After receiving matchmaking requests through F6S, the INOSENS team emailed participants to confirm receipt and let them know we were reviewing their requests. If a match was found, we introduced the participants to each other and suggested they arrange a follow-up call. If no match was found, we advised them to watch the **MeetYourMatch** session recording. For those who submitted requests close to the Open Call #1 deadline, we recommended applying for the second Open Call and encouraged them not to be discouraged.

INOSENS held the main responsibility for overseeing the Matchmaking requests pipeline. Additionally, they provided weekly updates on the application statuses to the entire DRG4Food consortium, seeking any potential suggestions and support in the partner search process.

Among the 14 Matchmaking requests, 7 participants ultimately applied for the DRG4Food Open Call #1.

Total Open Call #1 Applicants	Matchmaking Service Requests	Open Call #1 Submissions from Matchmaking
85	14	7

Figure 10 DRG4Food Open Call #1: Applicants, Matchmaking Requests, and Resulting Submissions

Matchmaking Service Outcomes and Recommendations for Open Call #2 The Matchmaking service, though not initially planned according to the Grant Agreement (GA), turned out to be a success. It mainly functioned as a means of communication during the promotional period, particularly during crucial times when there were no submissions on the F6S platform yet. Based on feedback received during the MeetYourMatch session and direct emails throughout the service period, participants were satisfied with the service. INOSENS plans to continue offering this service for Open Call #2. However, the period during which potential applicants can request this service will be shortened to prevent last-minute requests and potential disappointments should there be no match close to the open call deadline.

2.2.2 Open Call #1

Open Call #1 saw a **total of 85 applications submitted via F6S**, alongside another 79 applications that were started but not finalized (submitted).

Figure 11 Open Call #1 on F6S: 85 Submitted vs. 79 Unfinished Applications

The figure below shows the number of applications created and finalized, sorted by date. It is evident that the bulk of applications were submitted in the final three days leading up to the deadline, with many only beginning their submission process on F6S in the last week before the deadline.

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The figure below illustrates the number of applications created and finalized, sorted by the country of the lead applicant. In total, we received applications from 34 different countries, based on the country of the consortium lead.

Figure 12 Overview of Applications by Lead Applicant Country: Distribution Across 34 Countries

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When including all consortium partners, the list expands to cover 38 different countries. Among the 85 applicant consortia, 40 featured partners all from the same country.

Figure 13 Total Applications by Consortium Partners: Spanning 38 Countries

The figures below illustrate the number of applications created and finalized (submitted), categorized by challenge area:

Figure 14 Applications Finalized by Challenge Area

The figure below depicts the composition of consortia, both overall and segmented by challenge area.

Among the 85 applications, 53 featured 3 partners, while 32 involved 2 partners.

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Figure 15 Consortium Composition (Overall)

The figure below outlines the consortia composition, comparing 2-partner versus 3-partner consortia, across different challenge areas.

Figure 16 Consortium Composition (by challenge area)

The figure below shows responses to Question 39, detailing how participants learned about DRG4Food. Most applications originated from the F6S portal, referrals, social media, email, and the EC Funding & Tenders Portal, highlighting the impact of our direct outreach activities conducted through both offline and online/social media channels by partners.

Figure 17 Sources of Awareness for DRG4Food: Participant Responses

Open Call #1 Outcomes and Future Strategies for Open Call #2 Open Call #1 was deemed a success regarding the volume and quality of the submissions, although the growth rate of applications showed a gradual increase. A key recommendation for future calls is the implementation of a guideline mandating that at least 50% of the members in applicant consortia originate from EU-27 countries, aiming to maximize European impact. Additionally, while continuing active promotion, for Open Call #2, it is advised to forge stronger connections with networks such as the Enterprise Europe Network (EEN), European Digital Innovation Hubs (EDIHs), Startup Europe, and other similar initiatives to enhance outreach and participation.

Evaluation, Ranking & Selection

The DRG4Food evaluation process was developed based on INOSENS' experience as Open Call Manager & Treasurer and their previous work with open calls and financial support mechanisms (STARTUP3, DIATOMIC, KATANA, Block.IS) for third parties (FSTP). The evaluation included three stages:

- Phase 1: Eligibility Check,
- Phase 2: Remote Evaluation,
- Phase 3: Ranking of Proposals and Selection.

These stages took place between December 11, 2023, and February 20, 2024.

The evaluation of proposals for the DRG4Food project was undertaken by the review committee, which included TWINDS as the Project Coordinator and toolbox and enabler experts, INOSENS as the Open Call Manager and Treasurer, IDV as experts in DRGs, and Privanova as the Ethics and Legal Manager, with assistance from independent external experts. This consortium made sure the evaluation process complied with the European Commission's guidelines for proposal submission and evaluation, ensuring a fair process throughout.

2.3 Phase 1: Eligibility Check

Following the closure of the call on December 11, a preliminary screening was conducted to remove non-eligible proposals, leading to a shortlist.

This was done by DRG4Food's Open Call Manager and Treasurer (INOSENS) in December 2023. The eligibility check confirmed if the proposal met the following criteria outlined in the Guidelines for Applicants, specifically section 4.2.1, Phase 1 – Eligibility Check:

- a. Does the proposing consortium fulfill the consortium formation requirements as outlined in section 3.1? *[Yes/No]*
- b. Are the applicants' legal entities established in an eligible Horizon Europe country and eligible for funding under Horizon Europe rules, as detailed in section 3.1.3 of this Guidelines for Applicants? *[Yes/No]*
- c. Does the proposal directly align with the Participation Tracks of DRG4Food Open Call #1, namely, Food Tracking, Targeted Nutrition, and Consumers' Food Choices, as defined in section 2.2? *[Yes/No]*
- d. Has the participation rule, as defined in section 3.1.5, been followed regarding the number of proposals per applicant and multiple submissions, and confirm that there was no double submission of the proposal? *[Yes/No]*
- e. Is the proposal complete and submitted in English, including all required documents, and in accordance with the provided guidelines? Have all necessary documents, namely Annex B: Technical Proposal, Annex C: Applicant Declaration of Honor, Annex D: Consortium Declaration of Honor, and Annex E: SME Declaration, been correctly submitted? *[Yes/No]*
- f. Was the submission exclusively made through the F6S platform and within the specified deadline (11th December 2023, 17:00 CET Brussels time)? *[Y/N]*

INOSENS, acting as DRG4Food's Open Call Manager and Treasurer, performed this eligibility check in January 2024. Proposals identified as non-eligible were sent a rejection letter, outlining the reasons (listed from a to f) for their non-eligibility. No further details on the evaluation process were provided.

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Figure 18 Eligible vs. Non-Eligible Proposals

From the 85 proposals received, **11** were deemed ineligible. Each of these 11 applicants was sent a rejection letter detailing the reasons for their ineligibility, as outlined in the table below, which lists the eligibility criteria and the number of proposals not meeting them.

Table 1 Reason for non-eligibility

Eligibility Criteria	Number of Applications
a. Consortium Formation Met? [Yes/No]	10
b. Legal Entity Eligibility? [Yes/No]	0
c. Challenges Alignment? [Yes/No]	0
d. Multiple Submissions Rule Followed? [Yes/No]	0
e. Proposal Completeness? [Yes/No]	1
f. Platform Submission Timely? [Yes/No]	0

2.4 Phase 2: Remote Evaluation

The second phase of the evaluation process involved a combined effort from the DRG4Food Review Committee and external experts, who were chosen via the Call for Expression of Interest for Experts.

An Expression of Interest for experts was made available on F6S and published on the website, with selection criteria and application instructions explained in the "[Expression of Interest for Experts - DRG4Food Open Call #1](#)" document.

Evaluators were expected to bring their expertise and practical knowledge from areas such as food science, nutrition, supply chain management, and broader fields like social sciences, humanities, economics, and environmental science, in line with DRG4Food's goals.

Nineteen experts responded to the Call for Expression of interest; subsequently, the review committee (TWINDS, IDV, PN) used the Expert's Assessment Checklist, an internal tool prepared by INOSENS, to evaluate each submission. Each expression of interest was scored from 1 to 5 on a range of criteria, including background, expertise, knowledge and skills, relevant field experience, and CV quality.

Contracts were established with external experts, while both internal and external experts executed an NDA and a declaration affirming no conflict of interest. A remote evaluation kickoff meeting took place on February 5th, aimed at briefing the evaluators on the criteria for evaluation.

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A total 7 internal and 5 external experts were involved in evaluating the 74 proposals that advanced to this stage. Each proposal was reviewed by one internal and one external evaluator, who both scored and provided feedback on each submission based on the specified evaluation criteria. All evaluators were provided with a "Guidelines for Evaluators" document, prepared by INOSENS, to support them throughout the evaluation process. Evaluators were reimbursed a total of €3,330.00 for their remote evaluations, at a rate of €45 per application reviewed.

<i>Expert</i>	<i>Country</i>	<i>Gender</i>
Vanya Milkova Slavova	Bulgaria	Female
MARCO DE LA FELD	Italy	Male
Aleksandar Zobec	Serbia	Male
Giuseppe Mastandrea	Italy	Male
Nikolaos Marianos	Greece	Male

Both internal and external experts for the DG4Food project's evaluation were carefully paired with proposals that matched their expertise, considering key criteria such as:

- The alignment of project needs with the evaluator's expertise.
- Geographical factors, ensuring experts were not from the same country as the applicants.
- Additional aspects such as language abilities, experience, sector-specific knowledge, etc.

Each evaluator prepared an Individual Summary Report (ISR) which were later unified into a single Evaluation Summary Report (ESR).

Upon completion of the remote evaluation process, all proposals were consolidated into a unified list and ranked accordingly (refer to Annex I). The primary criterion for ranking proposals was their overall score, which was derived from the average scores provided by the evaluators.

In cases where multiple proposals share the same ranking position, tie-breaking procedures were implemented. These tie-breaks prioritized proposals with the highest scores in specific criteria, following the subsequent order:

- EC3. Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact
- EC1. Technology Excellence and Innovation
- EC2. Data Responsibility, Transparency, and Alignment with DRGs
- EC4. Consortium Capability, Team Qualifications, and Resource Allocation
- Date of submission: Proposals submitted earlier will be prioritized.

Regrettably, one of the top 5 proposals had to be excluded since it had already received funding from DRG4Food Open Call #1. Consequently, after consulting with the DRG4Food Review Committee, we moved forward with the next proposal on the list, adhering to the tie-break rule.

Ultimately, all applicants were notified of their scores through an evaluation summary provided for each stage.

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2.5 Final Selection & Awarded Teams

Details on the four chosen proposals can be found in Annex II, which contains information on the selected applications.

Below are some statistics regarding these selected proposals.

Figure 19 Countries representation in selected proposals

The total budget requested amounted to EUR 926,865.00, resulting in a budget of EUR 973,135 for Open Call #2.

One proposal was selected for Food Tracking, two for Targeted Nutrition, and one under the Consumers' Food Choices challenge.

Three out of the four selected projects are led by an SME, and three out of four projects include an end user. Additionally, all selected proposals feature an RTO, as mandated by the call guidelines.

Three out of the four selected proposals consist of consortia with three partners each, and three out of these four proposals include partners from different countries, demonstrating international collaboration. Additionally, one of the selected proposals is composed of partners all from the same country, highlighting a mix of both international and national collaborations among the chosen projects.

3 Contracting Phase

In late February, successful applicants were approached to finalize a Sub-grant Agreement with the DRG4Food project. During this phase, the DRG4Food Open Call Manager and Treasurer (INOSSENS), along with the project coordinator, engaged in discussions with the coordinators of the selected proposals. The aim was to conduct administrative and financial verifications, potentially extending into technical discussions, all rooted in the feedback from evaluators. The negotiations aimed to meet the legal stipulations binding the DRG4Food project consortium with each call beneficiary, covering several crucial aspects:

- Incorporating feedback from the Evaluation Summary Report into the Sub-grant Agreement.
- Verifying the status of the beneficiaries, including:
 - For SMEs: Required documentation included an SME declaration, a Status Information Form detailing the organizational structure, financial health, and in the case of startups, foundational documents. Legal documentation proving the existence and status as an SME was necessary.
 - Employee and Ownership Verification: When employee numbers or ownership details were unclear, supplementary documents such as payroll, annual reports, or official declarations were requested.
 - Bank Account Details: The specified account for fund transfers had to be confirmed via a form signed by the SME and bank authorities, ensuring the account belonged to the SME or the group's coordinator.
 - Sub-grantee Funding Agreement: A formal agreement was signed between the project consortium and the beneficiaries, establishing the financial and administrative conditions.

Documentation had to be submitted by specific deadlines. Failure to comply could result in the termination of negotiations, with reserve list projects stepping in as replacements. However, all selected projects complied with these requirements, successfully signing the subgrant agreements.

The projects officially started with a joint kickoff on March 18, 2024.

4 DRG4Food supporting activities for 3rd Parties

This chapter provides a preliminary outline of the business and technical support services available to the beneficiaries of the DRG4Food Open Call #1. Each pilot project undergoes three distinct phases: the establishment and planning of a citizen-centric data-driven food system (Phase 1), the implementation of digital responsibility-driven innovation, research, and pilot testing (Phase 2), and the expansion of digital solutions into the market (Phase 3). The comprehensive process will be recorded in the **D6.5 Report on DRG4Food technical and business support services (M35)**.

The program starts with the pilot launch, marked by an online kickoff meeting set for March 18, 2024. Post-launch, the projects move into Phase 1 and are assigned a mentor from within the consortium. Participants will meet with their mentors monthly until the project concludes, monitoring progress toward set Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). Phase 1 concludes with the submission of a first deliverable, which, **upon evaluation by the DRG4Food consortium members**, initiates the release of their first payment. This evaluation and payment release procedure is consistently applied for subsequent deliverables in Phases 2 and 3.

Phase 2 is characterized by its focus on four key modules: **DRG, Technology, Food, and Communications & Business**. This phase includes a series of webinars on diverse but related topics, presented by members of the consortium involved in this task (TWINDS, INOSENS, PMT, PMT PL, and ENEA) and, potentially, experts from the **focus group**. These webinars may be either live or pre-recorded. A boot camp, planned for the latter part of Phase 2, will be an in-person gathering designed with a pre-set agenda including training sessions, pitching opportunities, and more.

The transition from Phase 2 to Phase 3 intensifies the sharing of experiences among beneficiaries, such as through online roundtables, and encourages attendance at relevant events within our ecosystem to enhance their visibility to investors. Phase 3 concludes with a demo day, which may be aligned with a larger event to maximize impact. If not, it will be an online event inviting a select group of investors and focus group members.

M01		M02-M09				M10-M12		
Phase 1		Phase 2				Phase 3		
		Modules						
Online Launch of Open Call #1 Projects: March 18	<i>Individual Work with Mentor; Launch of Promo Pages on DRG4Food.eu;</i>	DRGs	Tech	Comms& Biz	Food	BOOTCAMP <i>(In-Person, October, Munich)</i>	<i>Experience Sharing Webinars, Individual Work, Collaborative Event Participation</i>	<i>Sales Development - Experience Sharing, Business Webinars, Online Pitch Training</i>
							DEMO DAY <i>(Online)</i>	
<i>Monthly Mentorship Sessions: Progress Tracking and Feedback</i>								

Figure 20 DRG4Food supporting activities for 3rd Parties

The ATTESTED, NutriSight and NutriWell pilot projects are designed with a 12-month timeline. On the other hand, SafeNutriKids projects are set for a shorter duration of 9 months. As a result, some coordination adjustments are necessary to ensure that all participants can fully benefit from the services and opportunities provided.

Deliverable D6.3

Figure 21 DRG4Food Pilot Projects and Their Timeline

Each of the four projects has been paired with a mentor/coach responsible for monitoring their progress and work towards achieving Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) through monthly meetings across different phases of their pilot projects.

Phase 1 - Setting up and Planning for a Trustworthy Data-driven Food System

- **Duration:** 1 month
- **Activities:** Deliver a detailed workplan, including objectives, milestones, KPIs, timeline & distribution of resources.
- **Deliverable:** Report on the activity plan
- **Support:** Review proposed pilot project workplan and alignment with the DRG4Food project to benefit from its technology enablers.
- **Funding Released:** Up to 30% of the pilot project budget. Upon successful definition and submission of the workplan, including objectives, milestones, and KPIs.
- **Conditions:** If the KPIs are completed less than 25%, the pilot project will be disqualified, and no further payment will be released.

Phase 2 - Digital Responsibility-Driven Innovation, Research, and Piloting

- **Duration:** 3-8 months
- **Activities:** Implement the workplan defined in Phase 1, including delivery of the proposed solution and its piloting.
- **Deliverable:** Report on the technical aspects of the solution developed and piloted.
- **Support:** Technical support on the integration of DRG4Food technology enablers; support in addressing technical issues.
- **Funding Released:** Up to 50% of the pilot project budget. Upon completion of 100% of the KPIs defined in Phase 1.
- **Conditions:** Proportional payment for lower completion of KPIs. If KPIs are completed less than 25%, the pilot project will be disqualified, and no further payment will be released.

Phase 3 - Scaling up – Bring your digital solution to market

- **Duration:** 1-3 months
- **Activities:** Present to external actors the results achieved and prepare a commercialization/business sustainability strategy. Participate in a boot camp located in Central Europe, which is easily accessible. It is required that at least one partner attends along with beneficiaries from Open Call #1 and #2.
- **Deliverable:** Report in the form of a business plan detailing the activities carried out and the strategy for business sustainability.
- **Support:** Business support in identifying activities (e.g., business modelling) and actors (e.g., investors) to support commercialization and the business strategy.
- **Funding Released:** Payment of final 20% of the pilot project budget. Upon successful submission and acceptance of the business plan detailing activities for business sustainability.

Deliverable D6.3

- **Conditions:** If KPIs are completed less than 25%, the pilot project will be disqualified, and no further payment will be released.

The payment schedule is directly linked to the relevant stages of each pilot project according to Annex 1 - Guidelines for Applicants. The payment in each Phase will be disbursed once the work related to a specific Phase has received positive assessment and against the evaluation of KPIs, based on the report submitted to the DRG4FOOD team and respective review (Table 2).

The financial contribution will be made to the Lead Beneficiary, representing the Beneficiaries, by the DRG4Food Project Coordinator (TWINDS) with InoSens acting as the treasurer, conducting the transfers.

Table 2 Payment schedule for DRG4FOOD – Open Call #1 funding programme

Phase	Schedule	Requirements	Payment
Phase 1	Duration: 1month	Report 1 – Pilot Specification and Design Report	Up to 30%
Phase 2	Duration: 3-8 months	Report 2 – Pilot Implementation and Validation Report	Up to 50%
Phase 3	Duration: 1-3 months	Report 3 – Business Plan and Market Entry Strategy	Up to 20%

All chosen pilot projects will be supported comprehensively by DRG4Food, enhancing their visibility within the broader innovation ecosystem. As outlined in their Subgrant funding agreements, projects must ensure to:

- Display the EU emblem and DRG4Food logo on all project materials.
- Include the following acknowledgment in communications:

“The [PROJECT NAME] project has indirectly received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation action programme, via the DRG4FOOD – Open Call #1 issued and executed under the DRG4FOOD project (Grant Agreement no. 101086523).”

When featuring the EU emblem alongside other logos, ensure it is prominently displayed.

We also invited them to share photos, videos from events, demonstrations of your technology, press releases, or surveys with the DRG4Food communications team.

5 Conclusion

The DRG4Food Open Call #1 successfully attracted 85 applications, thanks to a clear, thorough evaluation process that identified the 4 most promising proposals, achieving a 4.71% success rate and allocating a total budget of EUR 926,865.00. These selected projects span across the three defined challenge areas: 1 project in Food Tracking, 2 in Targeted Nutrition, and 1 in Consumers' Food Choices. With an eye towards April 2024, DRG4Food Open Call #2 will be announced, incorporating insights from the first call. The aim is to enhance dissemination and outreach efforts to secure a broader spectrum of high-quality proposals across these challenge areas. Open Call #2 will have a total funding pool of EUR 973,135 available.

Annex I Evaluation Ranking and Pilot Project Selection for Contracting Phase

Ranking Table from Remote Evaluation: Highlighting the 4 Pilot Projects Proceeding to the Contracting Phase.

	<i>Proposal title</i>	<i>Proposal acronym</i>	<i>Challenge area</i>	<i>Status</i>	<i>Total score</i>
1	Affordable and eThical TracEability SYStEMs to support proDucer-consumer relationships in small and medium supply chains	ATTESTED	Food Tracking	ABOVE TRESHOLD	19
2	Human-Centric Trustworthy AI Personalised Dietary Components for Healthier Living	NuTriGuide	Targeted Nutrition	<i>Not selected due to prior selection in FOODITY No double funding allowed</i>	18.5
3	Nutrition AI for Well-being and Social Inclusion	NutriWell	Targeted Nutrition	ABOVE TRESHOLD	18.5
4	Safe Nutrition for Kids	SafeNutriKids	Targeted Nutrition	ABOVE TRESHOLD	17.5
5	NutriSight: A window to food nutritional transparency	NutriSight	Consumers' Food Choices	ABOVE TRESHOLD	17.5
6	Certification of Environmental and Sustainability Food Impact, Origin and Authenticity based on ISO standards, and Distributed Ledger Technology	ISOChain	Food Tracking	ABOVE TRESHOLD	17.5
7	BlockChain and Artificial Intelligence enabled Food Traceability	FOODCHAIN	Food Tracking	ABOVE TRESHOLD	17
8	Data driven food prosumption	FoodTrust	Food Tracking	ABOVE TRESHOLD	17
9	Food IQ - save more, waste less	Food IQ	Food Tracking	NOT ELIGIBLE	0

Deliverable D6.3

10	OilTrace - AI-powered traceability system for monitoring oil oxidation in the supply chain.	<i>OilTrace</i>	Food Tracking	ABOVE TRESHOLD	17
11	Digital Reputation and Risk Assessment System	<i>DiRRAS</i>	Consumers' Food Choices	ABOVE TRESHOLD	17
12	Responsible and Trustworthy Chain for Food and CO2 Traceability and Optimisation	<i>BROADCAST</i>	Food Tracking	NOT ELIGIBLE	0
13	AquaGuard Traceability Project	<i>AGTP</i>	Food Tracking	ABOVE TRESHOLD	16.5
14	Individual Sports Nutrition Through Digital Innovation	<i>ISNU</i>	Targeted Nutrition	NOT ELIGIBLE	0
15	Transforming the Cacao Value Chain: Empowering Ecuadorian Smallholder farmers through a Centralised Processing Unit for Screening and Processing of Cacao Pulp to Enhance Quality and Transparency for creating Shelf-stable Products	<i>CacaoTEES</i>	Food Tracking	ABOVE TRESHOLD	16.5
16	Self-sustained urban gardens utilising a cartesian Robotic Platform based on AI	<i>CityVeg</i>	Food Tracking	ABOVE TRESHOLD	16.5
17	Din Chain	<i>DC</i>	Food Tracking	NOT ELIGIBLE	0
18	REFRESH	<i>Resilient Urban Food Chains through a Digital Fresh Fruits and Vegetables Distribution Platform</i>	Consumers' Food Choices	NOT ELIGIBLE	0
19	Enabling technology for real-time, on-site analysis of salmon quality and safety, pursuing Digital Responsibility Goals (DRG) and enhanced consumer trust	<i>DRG4Salmon</i>	Food Tracking	ABOVE TRESHOLD	16.5
20	Artificial Intelligence Module for Targeted Nutrition	<i>Ambrosia</i>	Targeted Nutrition	ABOVE TRESHOLD	16.5
21	Digitally Enhanced Transparency and Sustainability in Honey Supply Chain	<i>Trace4Honey</i>	Food Tracking	ABOVE TRESHOLD	16
22	Navigating Enhanced Understanding through Real-time Observations and Data Analytics in Virtual Reality	<i>NeuroData.VR</i>	Consumers' Food Choices	ABOVE TRESHOLD	16
23	MEditerranean Diet TAIlored Nutrition as a Service	<i>MEDiTAiNaaS</i>	Targeted Nutrition	ABOVE TRESHOLD	16

Deliverable D6.3

24	ReviewBOT: LLMs Guardrails alternative for Retrieval Augmented Generation, within the industries of FoodTech & Biotech.	<i>ReviewBOT</i>	Consumers' Food Choices	ABOVE TRESHOLD	16
25	Empowering Consumer Sovereignty with Transparent Food Sustainable Journey Insights	<i>Boostainability</i>	Food Tracking	ABOVE TRESHOLD	16
26	Traceability for food supply chains	<i>TRACE4FOOD</i>	Food Tracking	ABOVE TRESHOLD	15.5
27	Digital Food AUthenticity and Traceability: Eliminating Food Fraud for Good	<i>DIGFOA</i>	Food Tracking	ABOVE TRESHOLD	15.5
28	For transparEnt and Ethical food tRacking: A digiTal respOnsibility appRoach	<i>FEDERATOR</i>	Food Tracking	ABOVE TRESHOLD	15.5
29	Ecological Footprint Tool for Education on Consumers' Food Choices	<i>ECO4EDU</i>	Consumers' Food Choices	ABOVE TRESHOLD	15.5
30	Sensor Data Management for Food Tracking	<i>SDM4Food</i>	Food Tracking	ABOVE TRESHOLD	15.5
31	Gastro Quest	<i>GQ</i>	Consumers' Food Choices	ABOVE TRESHOLD	15
32	Learning Pills - micro-learning doses of empowerment and knowledge in an adolescent's nutrition journey	<i>BYTE-BITES</i>	Targeted Nutrition	ABOVE TRESHOLD	15
33	Your Guide to Healthy, Sustainable, and Antinutrient-Informed Choices	<i>NutriChain</i>	Consumers' Food Choices	ABOVE TRESHOLD	15
34	Optimizing Reliable Agriculture, Cultivating Learning and Ethical Efficiency	<i>ORACLE</i>	Food Tracking	ABOVE TRESHOLD	14.5
35	Open Food Data Network	<i>OFDN</i>	Consumers' Food Choices	ABOVE TRESHOLD	14.5
36	NUTRition with Personalized Assistance in Local restaurants	<i>NUTRIPAL</i>	Targeted Nutrition	ABOVE TRESHOLD	14.5
37	Trusted Traceability and Trackability for Citizens	<i>T3FC</i>	Food TrackinG	ABOVE TRESHOLD	14.5
38	Smart AI for Food Excellence - Traceability and Safety Assurance	<i>SAFE-TRACE</i>	Food Tracking	ABOVE TRESHOLD	14.5

Deliverable D6.3

39	Empowering Citizen-Consumers through Blockchain and AI-Enable Food Traceability	<i>TraceWell</i>	Food Tracking	ABOVE TRESHOLD	14
40	"EMA Trust: Revolutionizing Consumer Food Waste Behavior through Secure, Transparent, and Smart Food Practices, Enhanced by the EAT ME APP and Blockchain Technology for Knowledge-Based Attitude and Practice Shifts	<i>"EMA Trust"</i>	Food Tracking	ABOVE TRESHOLD	14
41	Basic Digital Infrastructure for sustainable fresh food	<i>BDI4Fresh</i>	Food Tracking	ABOVE TRESHOLD	14
42	Food reformulation software for healthy food environments	<i>NutriReform</i>	Targeted Nutrition	ABOVE TRESHOLD	14
43	Preventive Solution through AI Personalized Health	<i>Heal your Future</i>	Targeted Nutrition	NOT ELIGIBLE	0
44	AI-driven strategies for quality assurance in fruit and vegetable transportation.	<i>Q-Tracklife</i>	Food Tracking	ABOVE TRESHOLD	14
45	Delicious - Individual - Sustainable - Healthy	<i>DISH</i>	Targeted Nutrition	ABOVE TRESHOLD	14
46	AI virtual assistant for Food Tracking, Targeted Nutrition and Consumers' Food choices	<i>AI4FOOD</i>	Food Tracking, Targeted Nutrition	ABOVE TRESHOLD	14
47	Nutrient-Centric Health: Assisting in a Healthy Life	<i>NutriCare Health</i>	Targeted Nutrition	ABOVE TRESHOLD	14
48	Digital DNA data driven traceability and sustainability in the Olive Oil industry.	<i>DNA4Olive</i>	Food Tracking	ABOVE TRESHOLD	14
49	Beekeeping Transparency and Real-time Apiary Communication Ecosystem	<i>B-TRACE</i>	Food Tracking	ABOVE TRESHOLD	13.5
50	Sustainability and Digitalization Unleashing Supply Chain Harmony Achieving Innovative Networking	<i>SUSTAINCHAIN</i>	Food Tracking	BELOW TRESHOLD	13.5
51	Artificial Intelligence Food Guardian	<i>AIFG</i>	Food Tracking	ABOVE TRESHOLD	13.5
52	Community Supported Fisheries	<i>CSF</i>	Food Tracking	BELOW TRESHOLD	13

Deliverable D6.3

53	Meticulous and Authentic Transparency for Tomato Origin	<i>MATTO</i>	Food Tracking	BELOW TRESHOLD	13
54	Digi Food NPD & Nutrition First Product Development	<i>DFNPD</i>	Food Tracking	NOT ELIGIBLE	0
55	Ready Food Data Aggregator	<i>RFDA</i>	Targeted Nutrition	BELOW TRESHOLD	13
56	eXplainable Artificial Intelligence for Microbiome Balancing using Diet Recommendation and Nutraceutical Supplements	<i>XAI_MicroBalancer</i>	Targeted Nutrition	BELOW TRESHOLD	13
57	Intelligent and modern food traceability done by blockchain network	<i>IMT_BL</i>	Food Tracking	ABOVE TRESHOLD	13
58	A novel Data-Driven System targeting farmers, beekeepers and consumers to ensure Honey authenticity.	<i>DDS4Honey</i>	Food Tracking	BELOW TRESHOLD	13
59	Choose your food	<i>ChooseYFood</i>	Consumers' Food Choices	BELOW TRESHOLD	12.5
60	Balanced Wellness through Eco-friendly Living and Learning	<i>B-WELL</i>	Consumers' Food Choices	BELOW TRESHOLD	12.5
61	Nature LIFE Extremadura	<i>Naturedynamics (Nature Life + Biothermodynamics)</i>	Food Tracking	NOT ELIGIBLE	0
62	AI AND SPECTROSCOPY BASED IoT PLATFORM FOR OLIVE OIL QUALITY CERTIFICATION	<i>SPECTROSCOP-IA</i>	Food Tracking	BELOW TRESHOLD	12.5
63	Anomaly detection and localization in farms	<i>ADLF</i>	Food Tracking	BELOW TRESHOLD	12
64	BeerConcept	<i>BC</i>	Consumers' Food Choices	BELOW TRESHOLD	12
65	Shop Pilot Empowerment	<i>Shopilemp</i>	Consumers' Food Choices	NOT ELIGIBLE	0
66	Critical temperature control for sustainable digital food tracking	<i>CTC4DFT</i>	Food Tracking	BELOW TRESHOLD	12

Deliverable D6.3

67	Cross-Platform e-Commerce to Connect Farmers & Individual Agriculturalists with Buyers & Involve Service Providers	<i>FERMERS</i>	Food Tracking	BELOW TRESHOLD	12
68	Revolutionizing application Nutritional Wellness through AI-Powered Guidance disease risk reduction and health prevention	<i>AiNutri Care</i>	Targeted Nutrition	BELOW TRESHOLD	11.5
69	FarmE App	<i>Ecological world</i>	Targeted Nutrition	NOT ELIGIBLE	0
70	Personalised Diet and Nutrition Mobile Application for a Healthier Life	<i>MyHealthyApp</i>	Targeted Nutrition	BELOW TRESHOLD	11.5
71	Tracking food origins by means of a decentralised blockchain-based network	<i>FoodCHAIN.org</i>	Food Tracking	BELOW TRESHOLD	11.5
72	Smart Pest Management Systems	<i>SPMS</i>	Food Tracking	BELOW TRESHOLD	11.5
73	Sustainable Innovation for Meals Delivery Application	<i>SuslMeal</i>	Consumers' Food Choices	BELOW TRESHOLD	11.5
74	Artificial Intelligence for Health and Sustainability: Personalized and Eco-Friendly Nutrition Programs	<i>AI-HEAL</i>	Targeted Nutrition	BELOW TRESHOLD	11
75	Grow Wild	<i>GW</i>	Consumers' Food Choices	BELOW TRESHOLD	11
76	Verifiable Labels for Food Provenance	<i>BEE-CODE</i>	Food Tracking	BELOW TRESHOLD	11
77	Agro Sensor Data Monitoring (AGRO-XXI+I)	<i>AGRO-XXI+I</i>	Food Tracking	NOT ELIGIBLE	0
78	Openbatra 3.0	<i>Digitalizing Local Food information data for Enhanced Transparency and Responsibility</i>	Food Tracking	BELOW TRESHOLD	11
79	Vineyard-to-Consumer Lifecycle tracing for wine through Digital Passport	<i>WineDigiPass</i>	Food Tracking	BELOW TRESHOLD	11
80	FoodVault: A cryptographic toolkit for the Digital Food Systems of the future	<i>FoodVault</i>	Food Tracking	BELOW TRESHOLD	11
81	Smart Plate	<i>S-ATE</i>	Targeted Nutrition	BELOW TRESHOLD	10

Deliverable D6.3

82	Urban food platform	<i>UFP</i>	Food Tracking	BELOW TRESHOLD	10
83	«Arctic Station Survival» - digital solution for balanced nutrition	<i>"ArcSS" - digital solution for balanced nutrition</i>	Targeted Nutrition	BELOW TRESHOLD	8.5
84	New Ecosystem for Knowledge and Responsible Agri-Food Transparency	<i>NECTAR</i>	Food Tracking	BELOW TRESHOLD	8.5
85	TeMePE approach to tackle prevalent malnutrition and stunting in Rwanda	<i>TeMePE</i>	Food Tracking	BELOW TRESHOLD	7.5

Annex II Information on Selected Applications

ATTESTED - Affordable and eThical TracEability SysTEms to support producer consumer relationships in small and medium supply chains (Total score: 19)

Food Tracking

CommonsLab (Greece-SME), **FiBL** (Switzerland-RTO), **Valdibella** (Italy-SME)

ATTESTED is an innovation project aiming to introduce a comprehensive set of interoperable baseline technologies in order to improve efficacy in the agricultural and food production landscape. This "toolbox" serves as the foundation for a transformative traceability and monitoring system, strategically designed to encompass the entire farm-to-fork journey. Embracing a cooperative and solidarity economy approach, our project aims to empower both producers and consumers by enhancing transparency, efficiency, and sustainability within the agri-food sector. The key components of our toolbox include technologies such as Radio Frequency identification (RFID), GPS geolocation technologies, IoT and portable sensing systems. To test and integrate these systems into a real-world setting three entities are joining forces creating a pilot in the form of a combined system. The pilot serves as a crucial testing ground where we assess the practical viability and performance of our combined system. By implementing the toolbox in a live environment, we gain invaluable insights into its functionality, reliability, and adaptability to diverse agricultural scenarios.

Requested budget: 173,750.00€

NutriWell - Nutrition AI for Well-being and Social Inclusion (Total score: 18.5)

Targeted Nutrition

Innova Living Ltd. (Bulgaria-SME), **Institute of Technologies and Development (ITD)** (Bulgaria-RTO), **Sofia Development Association**, **Sofia Municipality** (Bulgaria-NGO)

NutriWell will develop five AI based building blocks (enablers) that can be integrated into the DRG4Food Toolbox and in various solutions related to the "Targeted nutrition" use-case. The primary target group will be elderly people (65+), but in the next stage the solution will be expanded towards other citizen groups as well. Each enabler is related to specific DRGs:

Nutrition Data Space (Generic Enabler), a multi-domain public data space containing anonymized food/nutrition related data, medical data; non-medical data; user generated data, AI generated data, etc. (DRG#7,1,2,3 & 4)

Users personal data wallet adapter (Specific Enabler), a service for personal data storage containing personal data, health and medical profiles (DRG#7,1,2,3&4);

AI nutrition plan generator (Specific Enabler) - it generates nutrition plan based on medical and wellbeing profiles (DRG#5,1,2,3 & 4);

AI cuisine allocator (Specific Enabler) - it generates menus for individuals based on their nutrition plan and their choice for a specific cuisine (e.g. Bulgarian and Greek).(DRG#5,1, 2,3 & 4);

Social cooking organiser (Specific Enabler) - it allows users with similar nutrition plans and menus to exchange experiences, cooking together (DRG#6, 1,2,3 & 4);

They will utilise additional open source enablers from the toolbox of the i4Trust platform¹ - enablers from FIWARE and iSHARE. The NutriWell enablers will be developed in co-creation with the user groups and other stakeholders by applying the

Deliverable D6.3

Living Labs methodology. All collected data during the implementation will be processed to follow the GDPR rules. Until the AI Act is adopted by the European Parliament, we will follow the recommended Assessment List for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence (ALTAI). The key requirements for ethically sound and trustful AI systems will be ensured by adopting a trustworthy-by-design approach. The opportunity to integrate the NutriWell system and enablers into an existing service platform will be tested by using the Active@Home platform (TRL7) with dedicated user groups in Bulgaria. In this case, to ensure GDPR compliant data gathering and data sharing we will use dataU2 - a distributed data sharing platform used also in the FOODITY project.

Requested budget: 299,250.00€

SafeNutriKids - Safe Nutrition for Kids (Total score: 17.5)

Targeted Nutrition

PhaseGrowth OÜ (Estonia-SME), Trakia University (RTO-Bulgaria), Sabri Ulker Foundation (NGO-Turkey)

The SafeNutriKids project is a human-centred initiative combining scientifically driven efforts of partners from Estonia, Bulgaria and Turkey. It aims at delivering AI-driven personalized nutrition education app with a focus on digital literacy for children aged 6-12. Spearheaded by a consortium of experts from Phasegrowth, Trakia University, and the Sabri Ulker Foundation, this project aims to integrate cutting-edge technology with interactive learning to enhance children's dietary habits and digital skills, ultimately contributing to better health and responsible digital citizenship.

Requested budget: 267,262.50€

NutriSight - NutriSight: A window to food nutritional transparency (Total score: 17.5)

Consumers' Food Choices

Open Food Facts (France-RTO), El CoCo (Spain-SME)

Nutritional information is crucial in assessing the quality of food products, but often, this data is presented to consumers in the form of nutritional tables, which can be challenging to comprehend. This project aims to address this issue by developing a tool that can automatically extract nutritional information from a photograph of food product's packaging. Leveraging deep learning techniques, our solution will encompass a machine learning model and an associated API, capable of operating in a highly multilingual context, enabling the extraction of nutritional data from photos across a wide spectrum of countries and languages. Furthermore, our tool will facilitate the presentation of nutritional information in a more user-friendly manner, such as through the implementation of the Nutri-Score system.

The project will also have a substantial impact on the Open Food Facts database, the world's largest open repository of food product information. Currently reliant on manual data entry by volunteers, our tool will significantly accelerate the collection of nutritional data while enhancing its accuracy and completeness.

To validate the effectiveness and usability of our tool, we will integrate it into the Open Food Facts mobile app and website as a pilot program. This implementation will allow us to gather valuable feedback from a large user base and refine the tool based on their experiences.

Requested budget: 186,603.00 €

Annex III Call for Expression of Interest of Experts

DRG4Food is currently seeking experts for an external evaluator pool to review submissions under DRG4Food Open Call #1, which targets responsible, data-driven innovation in food tracking, targeted nutrition, and consumer decision-making in the food sector.

We anticipate evaluators to contribute their insights and practical experience from technical realms like food science, nutrition, supply chain management, as well as from fields encompassing social sciences, humanities, economics, and environmental science, aligning with DRG4Food's visionary objectives.

Ideal candidates will meet the following requirements:

- Extensive experience in the food industry, particularly in areas such as Food Tracking, Targeted Nutrition, and Consumers' Food Choices.
- A solid background in academia, technology, or industry, with a focus on innovative services and applications that align with values of openness, sovereignty, fairness, and trust.
- Proven experience in evaluating European Commission proposals or similar assessment experience is required.

If you have the expertise and are interested in joining our evaluator pool, you are encouraged to apply. Responsibilities include a thorough assessment of proposals during the evaluation period in January 2024.

Experts will work independently and must not represent any company or organization during the evaluation process. The selection criteria and application details are outlined [Expression of Interest for Experts - DRG4Food Open Call #1](#) document.

Expert evaluator applications for DRG4Food Open Call #1 are welcome from nationals of EU Member States, their outermost regions, associated OCTs, and countries affiliated with Horizon Europe. Being selected as an expert requires signing a contract and non-disclosure agreement.

To apply for the evaluator pool for DRG4Food Open Call #1, please visit the F6S page at [DRG4Food Open Call #1 - Call for Expressions of Interest](#).

Note that submitting your expression of interest requires an F6S account, which you can create at no cost.

The deadline for expressing your interest is **November 30, 2023 (17.00 CET)**.

Thank you for considering this opportunity, and best of luck with your application. We are eager to potentially work together and value your interest in collaborating with us!

DRG4Food Open Call Coordination Team

(published on <https://drg4food.eu/drg4food-news/call-for-expert-evaluators-drg4food-open-call-1/>)

Annex IV Guidelines for Evaluating Experts

- Used internally by DRG4FOOD project consortium to evaluate and rank experts. -

Consider the following important points:

We are working to establish a diverse panel of experts who possess expertise in the following areas:

- o Food sector
- o Data ethics and data governance
- o Supply chain management
- o Social sciences
- o Humanities
- o Business development, scaling, and commercialization
- o Environmental science
- o Responsible innovation
- o Citizen engagement
- o Sustainable food systems

While previous experience in evaluating cascade funding and EC proposals is not mandatory, it is viewed as advantageous. Applicants with proven experience in these domains will receive a more favorable evaluation.

The final selection of evaluators will aim for diversity in terms of geographic location, expertise, and gender.

How to score:

You will be using the Expert's Assessment Checklist to score each of the 19 Expressions of Interest (Eols) submitted for review. For each Eol, scores should be assigned on a scale from 1 to 5 across various criteria. The checklist is designed to automatically calculate the total average score for each submission, simplifying the evaluation process.

When reviewing the Eols, follow the guidelines provided for assigning scores to ensure consistency and accuracy in your evaluations. It's important to thoroughly assess each Eol against the set criteria, giving a fair and balanced view of the applicants' qualifications and relevance to the DRG4Food initiative.

In cases where there's a significant discrepancy in scoring, indicating a possible divergence in how criteria are interpreted or the overall quality of submissions, a secondary review will be conducted by Maja.

Background, Expertise, Knowledge, and Skills Review: Assess if applicants have clearly detailed their background and expertise in areas critical to DRG4Food, like the food sector and sustainable food systems. It's important to check for specific details and quantification of their experience in related fields, such as environmental science or data governance.

Experience in Relevant Fields: Ensure that applicants have adequately described their expertise in areas they've indicated, like social sciences or business development, especially in relation to the food sector. Their experience should align with DRG4Food's goals, including citizen engagement and sustainability.

CV Comparison: Review the CVs to confirm a minimum of 5 years of experience in relevant fields to DRG4Food. Highlighted roles and achievements should directly relate to the project's focus, such as food supply chain management or policy development in the food sector. Remember, a PhD qualification can be counted as part of this experience.

Deliverable D6.3

Table 1 Scoring Criteria for DRG4Food Evaluators: Assessing Expertise, Curriculum Vitae, and Quality of Responses

Score	Background and Expertise Review	Experience and CV Comparison	Quality of Response
1	Stated expertise does not align with DRG4Food. No experience in evaluating EC/FSTP or related proposals.	CV lacks relevant details for DRG4Food, with minimal or irrelevant experience and education.	Responses lack clarity and specificity; no detailed explanation of listed expertise.
2	Minimal alignment with DRG4Food. Stated expertise vaguely related. Limited experience in evaluating similar projects.	CV structure is basic, with some relevant experience for DRG4Food but not substantial.	Limited details on expertise. Responses show weak understanding of DRG4Food criteria, with little quantification of experience.
3	Adequate alignment with DRG4Food. Relevant expertise stated but lacks depth. Some experience in relevant evaluations.	CV is relevant to DRG4Food but lacks comprehensive detail. Key experiences and qualifications are present but not well-highlighted.	Fair explanation of expertise. Some quantification of experience (less than 5 years), but missing depth in certain areas.
4	Good alignment with DRG4Food. Most expertise areas are relevant and well explained. Some experience in DRG4Food evaluations.	Strong CV, well-aligned with DRG4Food. Clear presentation of relevant experiences and qualifications.	Responses are clear, with detailed explanations in most areas. Quantification of expertise for 5 years or more in most areas.
5	Excellent match with DRG4Food needs. Comprehensive and relevant expertise, with strong justifications. Extensive experience in evaluating similar projects.	Outstanding CV, highly relevant and tailored to DRG4Food. Demonstrates extensive experience and qualifications clearly.	Detailed and insightful responses across all areas of expertise. Clear evidence of more than 5 years of experience in multiple relevant areas.

Evaluation Summary Report

DRG4Food Open Call #1

Proposal Title: ADFL

Outcome of Phase 2 – Remote Evaluation

Criterion	Average Points
Technology Excellence and Innovation <i>Assessing projects on innovation, compliance with EU food policies, advancements in data-driven technology, user collaboration, ethical standards, and open-source contributions.</i>	2.5/5
Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs <i>Evaluating projects on cybersecurity expertise, privacy standards, dataset integrity, user data control, algorithm transparency, and enabling DRG realization.</i>	3/5
Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact <i>Assessing business viability, scalability, and impact through unique selling points, market research, competitor analysis, financial projections, and IP rights management.</i>	2.5/5
Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation <i>Assessing consortium capability and qualifications, including work plan clarity, milestone definition, resource allocation, and expertise for development.</i>	4/5
TOTAL POINTS	12/20

STATUS: NOT SELECTED FOR FUNDING

Feedback and Areas for Improvement

Technology Excellence and Innovation

While the concept is described in a basic outline without going into technical details, it fails to connect with DRG4FOODs challenges and mission. This is because the proposal is mainly geared towards serving the farming community without clear benefits to consumers. Given the advanced TRL of some components, the TRL plan seems feasible. The proposal provides no measures for user engagement. Open-source contributions, ethical and legal considerations are not addressed.

Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs

As the proposal has little relevance or touchpoints with consumers the answers to relevant digital responsibility criteria miss the target. In general, the proposal fails to show relevance for enabling the DRGs.

Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact

The proposal remains does not sufficiently address market or competitor analysis, nor business model considerations.

Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation

The workplan is reasonably clear and feasible. The proposal sets out a comprehensible roadmap and timeline for deliverables. The consortium partners are qualified, and their fields of expertise provide for useful synergies. Risk management is not addressed.

Appraisal Scale per Criterion

Each criterion is evaluated on a scale up to 5, detailed as follows:

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- 1 / POOR** *The proposal addresses the criterion in an inadequate manner or there are significant weaknesses.*
- 2 / FAIR** *The proposal addresses the criterion broadly, but there are still several weaknesses.*
- 3 / GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion well, but improvements are necessary.*
- 4 / VERY GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion very well, but some improvements are still possible.*
- 5 / EXCELLENT** *The proposal successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the criterion. Any shortcomings are minor.*

The overall threshold for the total score is 12/20.

Evaluation Summary Report

DRG4Food Open Call #1

Proposal Title: AGTP

Outcome of Phase 2 – Remote Evaluation

Criterion	Average Points
Technology Excellence and Innovation <i>Assessing projects on innovation, compliance with EU food policies, advancements in data-driven technology, user collaboration, ethical standards, and open-source contributions.</i>	3.5
Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs <i>Evaluating projects on cybersecurity expertise, privacy standards, dataset integrity, user data control, algorithm transparency, and enabling DRG realization.</i>	4.5
Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact <i>Assessing business viability, scalability, and impact through unique selling points, market research, competitor analysis, financial projections, and IP rights management.</i>	4.5
Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation <i>Assessing consortium capability and qualifications, including work plan clarity, milestone definition, resource allocation, and expertise for development.</i>	4
TOTAL POINTS	16.5

STATUS: NOT SELECTED FOR FUNDING

Feedback and Areas for Improvement

Technology Excellence and Innovation

The proposal elaborates well how the proposal aligns with the specific challenges of DRG4FOOD. There is a reasonably detailed outline of the proposals' technological approach, however some questions remain, such as, for example, the type of data collected through IoT sensors. Overall, the technological excellence of the proposal is more pronounced than the innovative character. The plan for the advancement of TRL is elaborate and seems feasible. The proposal lays out basic measures for user co-design. Ethical considerations are briefly addressed. Open-source contributions are addressed; however, it remains a bit vague how and what the proposal will provide to the DRG4FOOD toolbox.

Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs

The proposal provides answers to most relevant criteria and proposes arguments how DRGs will be enabled, demonstrating a technical knowledge of implementing responsible technologies.

Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact

USPs of the proposal are debatable, as the proposal's novelty in the realm of food-tracking is limited. However, the advanced and professional approach to an established idea can be seen as a USP in itself. The market and competitor analysis is well-founded and the elaboration of the business model is well done. IPR management and exploitation strategy is sufficiently discussed.

Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation

The workplan is detailed and feasible in general, however 105 PM seem an excessive amount of workforce. Description of the qualifications of the consortium partners is sufficient. Risk management and mitigation is not discussed.

Appraisal Scale per Criterion

Each criterion is evaluated on a scale up to 5, detailed as follows:

- 1 / POOR** *The proposal addresses the criterion in an inadequate manner or there are significant weaknesses.*
- 2 / FAIR** *The proposal addresses the criterion broadly, but there are still several weaknesses.*
- 3 / GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion well, but improvements are necessary.*
- 4 / VERY GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion very well, but some improvements are still possible.*
- 5 / EXCELLENT** *The proposal successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the criterion. Any shortcomings are minor.*

The overall threshold for the total score is 12/20.

Evaluation Summary Report

DRG4Food Open Call #1

Proposal Title: AI4FOOD

Outcome of Phase 2 – Remote Evaluation

Criterion	Average Points
Technology Excellence and Innovation <i>Assessing projects on innovation, compliance with EU food policies, advancements in data-driven technology, user collaboration, ethical standards, and open-source contributions.</i>	4/5
Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs <i>Evaluating projects on cybersecurity expertise, privacy standards, dataset integrity, user data control, algorithm transparency, and enabling DRG realization.</i>	3.5/5
Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact <i>Assessing business viability, scalability, and impact through unique selling points, market research, competitor analysis, financial projections, and IP rights management.</i>	3/5
Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation <i>Assessing consortium capability and qualifications, including work plan clarity, milestone definition, resource allocation, and expertise for development.</i>	3.5/5
TOTAL POINTS	14/20

STATUS: NOT SELECTED FOR FUNDING

Feedback and Areas for Improvement

Technology Excellence and Innovation

The proposal addresses well the DRG4Food specific challenge areas, focusing on all 3: Consumer' Food Choices, Targeted Nutrition and Food Tracking. In addressing these areas, there is strong emphasis on trust, citizen engagement, and user sovereignty. The proposal has an ambitious technological approach, which promised to go beyond the current state of the art. However, it's not entirely clear on how this will be succeeded. A main problem is that the app promises to offer a lot of functionalities and tap into a large number or data sources, but it would benefit from more clarity on how this will be achieved.

The concept has a good level of novelty and its relevant to the call.

Due to the complexity of the app to be developed, it's not easy to assess the actual feasibility for market launch. More information would be needed to convince this is feasible.

The extent and effectiveness of planned engagement with end users in co-designing and testing the solution appears to be appropriate.

The proposal has in place a plan for addressing ethical and legal considerations relevant to the project, through the internal ethics committee of Consorzio Italtotec.

There is no clear indication that the proposed project will contribute to the DRG4Food toolbox with open source solutions. Only the willingness to adopt some of the toolbox's enablers is clear.

Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs

The team's expertise in cybersecurity is very good, as their core expert has 14-year experience in the field. The identification of cybersecurity threats and the strategies for their mitigation appear to be appropriate.

In terms of privacy and data handling, on one hand the proposal explains that only a few data will be entered manually, but on the other hand, there is a mention about multiple data streams coming from the device of the user, including browsing history, data from health apps, etc. The proposed approach lacks sufficient clarity.

The strategies for ensuring dataset integrity and mitigating potential biases presented by the proposal, appear to be appropriate.

A process for reviewing the clarity of algorithmic outputs and the assessment and mitigation of algorithmic bias, is in place.

The proposal adequately facilitates user control over data and establishes transparency measures.

The proposal has the potential to realize more than one DRG criterion.

Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact

The presented USPs of the proposed solution, their alignment with user needs, and the value proposition of the solution, appear to be strong.

Although the market analysis, including competitor analysis, is comprehensive, the claim that the app has no real competitors, is not justified properly.

The credibility of the business model and the financial projections is not sufficiently justified, as there are not sufficient data that could support the fact that there will be enough producers that can afford a fee of 400 €/month. More information on this target group, would be needed.

The proposal's approach to IPR management and the strategy for exploiting the results appears to be appropriate.

Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation

The clarity and feasibility of the proposed work plan is good and the same applies to the definition and feasibility of milestones and deliverables. Milestones are not specifically mentioned, it's very clear what is delivered within the defined phases. A shortcoming is that the phases are not properly aligned with the phases and milestones mentioned in the DRG4FOOD guidelines. The KPIs are not very appropriate.

There is no clear indication on the procedures for risk assessment and the strategies for risk mitigation. The resource allocation appears to be appropriate.

Although the proposal mentions that "Giancarlo Visalli has 14 years experience in software solutions for SME companies", the justification of the consortium's strength in terms of business is not sufficient. A lot more emphasis is put on the scientific skills, which appear to be strong. The strength of collaboration is appropriate. There is gender balance in the consortium. The explanation of the individual capacities of the team members lacks detail.

Appraisal Scale per Criterion

Each criterion is evaluated on a scale up to 5, detailed as follows:

- 1 / POOR** *The proposal addresses the criterion in an inadequate manner or there are significant weaknesses.*
- 2 / FAIR** *The proposal addresses the criterion broadly, but there are still several weaknesses.*
- 3 / GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion well, but improvements are necessary.*
- 4 / VERY GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion very well, but some improvements are still possible.*
- 5 / EXCELLENT** *The proposal successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the criterion. Any shortcomings are minor.*

The overall threshold for the total score is 12/20.

Evaluation Summary Report

DRG4Food Open Call #1

Proposal Title: AIFG - Artificial Intelligence for Health and Sustainability: Personalized and Eco-Friendly Nutrition Programs

Outcome of Phase 2 – Remote Evaluation

Criterion	Average Points
Technology Excellence and Innovation <i>Assessing projects on innovation, compliance with EU food policies, advancements in data-driven technology, user collaboration, ethical standards, and open-source contributions.</i>	3.5/5
Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs <i>Evaluating projects on cybersecurity expertise, privacy standards, dataset integrity, user data control, algorithm transparency, and enabling DRG realization.</i>	3/5
Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact <i>Assessing business viability, scalability, and impact through unique selling points, market research, competitor analysis, financial projections, and IP rights management.</i>	3.5/5
Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation <i>Assessing consortium capability and qualifications, including work plan clarity, milestone definition, resource allocation, and expertise for development.</i>	3.5/5
TOTAL POINTS	13.5/20

STATUS: NOT SELECTED FOR FUNDING

Feedback and Areas for Improvement

Technology Excellence and Innovation

The proposal presents a clear main idea aligned with the call's scope, though it lacks detailed explanations on achieving described results, offering only basic technical development information. Despite its strong alignment with DRG4Food challenges and its commendable focus on enhanced traceability through a dynamic, AI-powered platform for HACCP plan management, the proposal falls short in justifying the novelty of its solution. Its objectives are clear and relevant, aligning with Digital Responsibility Goals, like enhancing food safety and compliance. However, its ambitious Technology Readiness Level (TRL) progression and market introduction strategy lack realism. End-user engagement through beta testing and co-design feedback loops is well-conceived, yet ethical, legal considerations, and detailed plans for open source contributions need further elaboration.

Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs

While the proposal thoroughly describes data responsibility and showcases the team's strong expertise in secure software design and cybersecurity, it lacks complete alignment with Digital Responsibility Goals (DRGs), missing crucial information and clear connections to specific activities. Cybersecurity threats are identified with some mitigation strategies proposed, and the approach to privacy and dataset integrity through blockchain technology is convincingly presented. User data control and transparency measures are well-addressed, with a brief yet appropriate discussion on mitigating algorithmic bias. The integration of AI, IoT, and blockchain technologies demonstrates the proposal's potential to meet several DRG criteria, emphasizing privacy, security, and transparency.

Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact

The solution's scalability and business model are clearly and effectively described, yet the business plan lacks completeness, with missing assumptions and unclear impact strategies for the project's duration and beyond. While Unique Selling Points (USPs) are convincingly outlined, and the market analysis is thorough, competitor analysis lacks depth, particularly in benchmarking against similar market solutions. The business model and financial projections are credible, with a well-considered scaling strategy. However, IPR management is only briefly mentioned, and the proposal does not adequately detail individual exploitation strategies for partners.

Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation

The team is mostly equipped with the competencies and experience for the proposed project, demonstrating good cooperation and mostly defined activities among partners. The work plan mostly aligns with project outcomes. The budget is appropriately set, with person-months distribution matching the activities across work packages.

Appraisal Scale per Criterion

Each criterion is evaluated on a scale up to 5, detailed as follows:

- 1 / POOR** *The proposal addresses the criterion in an inadequate manner or there are significant weaknesses.*
- 2 / FAIR** *The proposal addresses the criterion broadly, but there are still several weaknesses.*
- 3 / GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion well, but improvements are necessary.*
- 4 / VERY GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion very well, but some improvements are still possible.*
- 5 / EXCELLENT** *The proposal successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the criterion. Any shortcomings are minor.*

The overall threshold for the total score is 12/20.

Evaluation Summary Report

DRG4Food Open Call #1

Proposal Title: AIHEAL

Outcome of Phase 2 – Remote Evaluation

Criterion	Average Points
Technology Excellence and Innovation <i>Assessing projects on innovation, compliance with EU food policies, advancements in data-driven technology, user collaboration, ethical standards, and open-source contributions.</i>	3/5
Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs <i>Evaluating projects on cybersecurity expertise, privacy standards, dataset integrity, user data control, algorithm transparency, and enabling DRG realization.</i>	2/5
Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact <i>Assessing business viability, scalability, and impact through unique selling points, market research, competitor analysis, financial projections, and IP rights management.</i>	3/5
Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation <i>Assessing consortium capability and qualifications, including work plan clarity, milestone definition, resource allocation, and expertise for development.</i>	3/5
TOTAL POINTS	11/20

STATUS: NOT SELECTED FOR FUNDING

Feedback and Areas for Improvement

Technology Excellence and Innovation

The proposal to incorporate the SU-EATABLELIFE open-source database into a project aimed at recommending foods with lower carbon and water footprints is intriguing for its sustainability focus. However, it lacks detailed information on the technological innovations involved in this integration, how it would enhance the database's accuracy and applicability, or contribute to broader open-source development. While the idea of aligning dietary advice with environmental footprints through an AI model is innovative, the proposal does not adequately address potential challenges or the specifics of the technology's sophistication, particularly in terms of digital responsibility, data privacy, and user control.

Moreover, the proposal primarily discusses updating a consumer app with AI capabilities but fails to clearly articulate the innovative aspects of this technology, how it will ensure data privacy, or contribute to the DRG4FOOD toolbox for open-source use. The proposal does not strongly emphasize user engagement or how it will support the goals of data sovereignty and fair value distribution, which are crucial for aligning with the European Data strategy's vision. It appears to focus on enhancing an existing solution without a clear strategy for contributing to broader societal benefits or fostering innovation in the food system through open-source sharing.

Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs

The proposal outlines a team with strong cybersecurity expertise and a strategy to mitigate cybersecurity threats, primarily within a commercial development context. However, it lacks specificity on advancing innovative cybersecurity methods or

contributing insights to the DRG4FOOD toolbox, which would align with the European Data Strategy and DRG innovation focus. The approach to handling sensitive personal data and ensuring user sovereignty and trust is mentioned but not detailed, missing a clear alignment with DRG4FOOD challenges and the broader European Data Strategy goals.

While the proposal indicates an intention to mitigate algorithmic biases and improve transparency in model predictions, it does not provide a clear methodology or innovation focus in these areas, nor does it detail contributions to the DRG4FOOD toolbox beyond a mentioned NLP model in English. The integration of an existing open-source database is noted, but the proposal does not clarify how this integration will enhance the database or if the AI model developed will be available for broader use, thus lacking a direct connection with EU goals for communal data use and innovation in the food and nutrition sector.

Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact

The business model outlined in the proposal shows potential in financial terms but lacks critical details on user numbers and other key value drivers, creating uncertainty regarding its viability. The model conflates the markets for medical health services aimed at patients with those for health-conscious consumers, overlooking the significant differences in validation, legal requirements, and certification needed for medical applications. This oversight suggests a lack of consideration for the risks associated with making health claims, especially since the proposal ambiguously states that no special categories of personal data will be processed, which contradicts the apparent focus on health data.

Furthermore, the financial projections are vague, with no clear information on the existing subscriber base, projected user growth, target markets, or language options beyond English. This ambiguity raises questions about the proposal's commitment to accessibility and its strategy for engaging diverse EU markets.

The proposal's unique selling points (USPs) hinge on AI-driven data insights and expert content generation. However, the work packages do not emphasize the significant effort required for content creation and user feedback mechanisms, which are critical for addressing digital rights goals (DRGs). While personalized nutrition plans, a video recipe library, and AI-generated healthy eating advice are highlighted as USPs, the plan to share only an English NLP model as open-source—without clarifying whether additional documentation on development and integration will be provided—suggests a focus on proprietary development. This approach risks creating a value imbalance, potentially failing to align with the objectives of EU funding and the specific aims of the DRG4FOOD call, which seeks broader communal benefits and open-source contributions.

Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation

Consortium presents a diverse team with a reasonable balance of expertise in technology development and technology research. There are however no user experience researchers, experts or designers, or expert support with EU health data regulations and legal support – especially in relation to personal data and developing AI models this is not apparent. There is a high cost allocated to equip video content creation.

Appraisal Scale per Criterion

Each criterion is evaluated on a scale up to 5, detailed as follows:

- 1 / **POOR** *The proposal addresses the criterion in an inadequate manner or there are significant weaknesses.*
- 2 / **FAIR** *The proposal addresses the criterion broadly, but there are still several weaknesses.*
- 3 / **GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion well, but improvements are necessary.*
- 4 / **VERY GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion very well, but some improvements are still possible.*
- 5 / **EXCELLENT** *The proposal successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the criterion. Any shortcomings are minor.*

The overall threshold for the total score is 12/20.

Evaluation Summary Report

DRG4Food Open Call #1

Proposal Title: AiNutriCare

Outcome of Phase 2 – Remote Evaluation

Criterion	Average Points
Technology Excellence and Innovation <i>Assessing projects on innovation, compliance with EU food policies, advancements in data-driven technology, user collaboration, ethical standards, and open-source contributions.</i>	2.5/5
Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs <i>Evaluating projects on cybersecurity expertise, privacy standards, dataset integrity, user data control, algorithm transparency, and enabling DRG realization.</i>	3/5
Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact <i>Assessing business viability, scalability, and impact through unique selling points, market research, competitor analysis, financial projections, and IP rights management.</i>	3/5
Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation <i>Assessing consortium capability and qualifications, including work plan clarity, milestone definition, resource allocation, and expertise for development.</i>	3/5
TOTAL POINTS	11.5/20

STATUS: NOT SELECTED FOR FUNDING

Feedback and Areas for Improvement

Technology Excellence and Innovation

The proposal aligns with the challenges of DRG4FOOD, however, the elaboration on technological excellence remains vague or incomplete and the outline of the proposed solutions lacks clarity. Especially, in terms of innovation the proposal lacks novelty. There is no discussion of ethical or legal considerations despite engaging in collection and processing of health data. The plan for TRL advancement remains vague. The proposal mentions measures for some user testing but it remains unclear how this will be realized concretely. Open-sourcing is not addressed.

Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs

Despite providing basic answers to some relevant criteria little effort is made to describe concretely how the implementation of digital responsibility will be achieved concretely and technically. Measures described don't go beyond standard practices in software development.

Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact

Description of the USP remains underdeveloped. The proposal sets out that: "The difference from the competition lies in the innovative data processing model..." without going into any details how the data processing differs from already existing models. Market and competition analysis is insufficient; business model is described only vaguely as "freemium" without specifying. IPR management and exploitation is only discussed superficially.

Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation

While the consortium seems capable and qualified for delivering proposed solution, the workplan remains quite basic. A detailed cost table is missing; risk management is not discussed.

Appraisal Scale per Criterion

Each criterion is evaluated on a scale up to 5, detailed as follows:

- 1 / POOR** *The proposal addresses the criterion in an inadequate manner or there are significant weaknesses.*
- 2 / FAIR** *The proposal addresses the criterion broadly, but there are still several weaknesses.*
- 3 / GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion well, but improvements are necessary.*
- 4 / VERY GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion very well, but some improvements are still possible.*
- 5 / EXCELLENT** *The proposal successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the criterion. Any shortcomings are minor.*

The overall threshold for the total score is 12/20.

Evaluation Summary Report

DRG4Food Open Call #1

Proposal Title: AMBROSIA

Outcome of Phase 2 – Remote Evaluation

Criterion	Average Points
Technology Excellence and Innovation <i>Assessing projects on innovation, compliance with EU food policies, advancements in data-driven technology, user collaboration, ethical standards, and open-source contributions.</i>	4.5/5
Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs <i>Evaluating projects on cybersecurity expertise, privacy standards, dataset integrity, user data control, algorithm transparency, and enabling DRG realization.</i>	4/5
Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact <i>Assessing business viability, scalability, and impact through unique selling points, market research, competitor analysis, financial projections, and IP rights management.</i>	3.5/5
Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation <i>Assessing consortium capability and qualifications, including work plan clarity, milestone definition, resource allocation, and expertise for development.</i>	4.5/5
TOTAL POINTS	16.5/20

STATUS: NOT SELECTED FOR FUNDING

Feedback and Areas for Improvement

Technology Excellence and Innovation

The proposal addresses well the DRG4Food specific challenge area “Targeted Nutrition”, while having strong emphasis on trust, citizen engagement, and user sovereignty. The proposal has an ambitious technological approach, which promises to go beyond the current state of the art. The market launch of the proposed solution appears to be feasible. The extent and effectiveness of planned engagement with end users in co-designing and testing the solution appears to be appropriate. The proposal has in place a plan for addressing ethical and legal considerations relevant to the project. Open source contribution is credibly proposed. However, the willingness and plan to contribute to the DRG4Food toolbox is not sufficiently demonstrated. This is a shortcoming.

Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs

The team’s expertise in cybersecurity is strong. Moreover, the identification of cybersecurity threats and the strategies for their mitigation are thorough. The proposal's approach to privacy, including how personal data is handled securely and transparently, appears to be appropriate. The only thing that is not clear is how they will handle the data needed to support the Nutrition Intake tool that is supposed to offer nutrition recommendation. This needs more clarity. The strategies for ensuring dataset integrity and mitigating potential biases presented by the proposal, appear to be appropriate. A process for reviewing the clarity of algorithmic outputs and the assessment and mitigation of algorithmic bias, is in place. The proposal adequately facilitates user control over data and establishes transparency measures. The proposal has the potential to realize at least two DRGs.

Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact

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The presented USPs of the proposed solution, their alignment with user needs, and the value proposition of the solution, appear to be strong. A shortcoming is that the claim that “in case of a restaurant or homemade meal, manual user input is cumbersome and inaccurate”, implying that it can be done better though the app, is not properly substantiated. The market analysis and the competitor analysis are comprehensive, and there is a detail comparison with the main identified competitor. The credibility of the business model and the financial projections appears to be appropriate. However, some more information would be needed on the current service subscription cost paid to these premium fitness clubs operators by the final end users. This would allow us to fully judge its potential. The proposal’s approach to IPR management is not presented in an appropriate level of detail.

Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation

The clarity and feasibility of the proposed work plan is good and the same applies to the definition and feasibility of milestones and deliverables. The procedures for risk assessment and have not been described in details. The identified risks and the strategies for risk mitigation are presented and, although they appear to be somewhat generic, they are relevant. The resource allocation appears to be appropriate. The strength of collaboration is appropriate and the individual capacities of the team members appear to be relevant, although some more detail would be appreciated. In terms of gender balance in the consortium, 1/3 of the team members are female and the rest are male.

Appraisal Scale per Criterion

Each criterion is evaluated on a scale up to 5, detailed as follows:

- 1 / POOR** *The proposal addresses the criterion in an inadequate manner or there are significant weaknesses.*
- 2 / FAIR** *The proposal addresses the criterion broadly, but there are still several weaknesses.*
- 3 / GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion well, but improvements are necessary.*
- 4 / VERY GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion very well, but some improvements are still possible.*
- 5 / EXCELLENT** *The proposal successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the criterion. Any shortcomings are minor.*

The overall threshold for the total score is 12/20.

Evaluation Summary Report

DRG4Food Open Call #1

Proposal Title: ArcSS

Outcome of Phase 2 – Remote Evaluation

Criterion	Average Points
Technology Excellence and Innovation <i>Assessing projects on innovation, compliance with EU food policies, advancements in data-driven technology, user collaboration, ethical standards, and open-source contributions.</i>	2/5
Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs <i>Evaluating projects on cybersecurity expertise, privacy standards, dataset integrity, user data control, algorithm transparency, and enabling DRG realization.</i>	3/5
Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact <i>Assessing business viability, scalability, and impact through unique selling points, market research, competitor analysis, financial projections, and IP rights management.</i>	1.5/5
Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation <i>Assessing consortium capability and qualifications, including work plan clarity, milestone definition, resource allocation, and expertise for development.</i>	2/5
TOTAL POINTS	8.5/5

STATUS: NOT SELECTED FOR FUNDING

Feedback and Areas for Improvement

Technology Excellence and Innovation

The "Arctic Station Survival" project aligns with DRG4Food's focus on promoting a healthy lifestyle through its gamified approach, targeting a broad demographic with emphasis on digital literacy and balanced nutrition. However, while the project's objectives and ethical considerations demonstrate potential and are aligned with the DRG4Food challenges, there are significant gaps in detailing technological structure and state of the art advancement and open-source contributions. The user engagement strategies are outlined but lack specifics on the co-design process.

Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs

The "Arctic Station Survival" game leverages Google's infrastructure for cybersecurity, prioritizing user data protection with minimal personal data use and secure server hosting. It features an intuitive interface and explanatory elements, ensuring algorithmic clarity and adaptability to user needs. Testing and user feedback form the core of their algorithmic error mitigation strategy, promoting transparency through public documentation, privacy policies, and user communication. While the game supports DRG principles, enhancing digital literacy and privacy, it could detail specific cybersecurity practices further. Furthermore, what is not outlined is the Team's expertise in cybersecurity.

Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact

The proposal approach to USP, Market fitness, Business value, commercialization strategy, business model, financial projections and strategy for scaling is very weak. It fails short to articulate the details of the value model, scalability plans, market engagement strategy.

Financial forecasts are non-existent. It doesn't showcase any competitors, and its IPR strategy is rudimentary.

Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation

Work Plan, descriptions, planned outputs are well defined. Project implementation strategy follows the agile method. Potential risks and mitigation strategies outlined. Highly ambitious KPIs (KPI 3, KPI 4, 8,9, 11.) given the timeframe. KPI improvements on described KPIs show consideration adaptability. Team indicates strong capacity for game development, but as already mentioned, fails to indicate data expertise that is aligned with the projects DRGs. The project costs and resources indicate 57% indirect costs / sub-contracting, which is extremely high, and not looked at favorably by the evaluators.

Appraisal Scale per Criterion

Each criterion is evaluated on a scale up to 5, detailed as follows:

- 1 / POOR** *The proposal addresses the criterion in an inadequate manner or there are significant weaknesses.*
- 2 / FAIR** *The proposal addresses the criterion broadly, but there are still several weaknesses.*
- 3 / GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion well, but improvements are necessary.*
- 4 / VERY GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion very well, but some improvements are still possible.*
- 5 / EXCELLENT** *The proposal successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the criterion. Any shortcomings are minor.*

The overall threshold for the total score is 12/20.

Evaluation Summary Report

DRG4Food Open Call #1

Proposal Title: ATTESTED

Outcome of Phase 2 – Remote Evaluation

Criterion	Average Points
Technology Excellence and Innovation <i>Assessing projects on innovation, compliance with EU food policies, advancements in data-driven technology, user collaboration, ethical standards, and open-source contributions.</i>	5/5
Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs <i>Evaluating projects on cybersecurity expertise, privacy standards, dataset integrity, user data control, algorithm transparency, and enabling DRG realization.</i>	4.5/5
Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact <i>Assessing business viability, scalability, and impact through unique selling points, market research, competitor analysis, financial projections, and IP rights management.</i>	4.5/5
Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation <i>Assessing consortium capability and qualifications, including work plan clarity, milestone definition, resource allocation, and expertise for development.</i>	5/5
TOTAL POINTS	19/20

STATUS: SELECTED FOR FUNDING

Feedback and Areas for Improvement

Technology Excellence and Innovation

The ATTESTED proposal exhibits strong alignment with DRG4Food challenges, particularly in enhancing trust and user sovereignty through technology. Its integration of RFID, GPS, IoT, and sensory systems shows a high-quality, state-of-the-art technological approach. The objectives are clear, robust, and innovative, yet the project could benefit from a more detailed plan for market launch to clarify the feasibility. User engagement and technology testing is planned. Ethical and legal considerations, along with open-source contributions, are addressed but may require further depth.

Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs

ATTESTED's approach to data responsibility and transparency is a strong suit, especially with its GDPR compliance and emphasis on data security and privacy. The proposal indicates a knowledgeable team in cybersecurity yet could benefit from more explicit descriptions of cybersecurity threat identification and mitigation strategies. Privacy and user control measures are mentioned, but the strategies to ensure dataset integrity and mitigate bias could be further detailed. The realization of DRGs is acknowledged, but the specifics on how these will be achieved could be clearer. The evaluators recognizes their robust cybersecurity measures while noting the need for more detail in certain areas.

Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact

ATTESTED has identified a clear USP with its technology enabling traceability and monitoring for cooperative economies. The business model, focused on a subscription-based revenue stream, shows potential for scalability. The IPR management seems proactive while the commercialization strategy seems to be overviewed, however could use more details, focusing on distribution channels, customer acquisition, marketing and sales activities. SWOT analysis is well received.

Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation

The ATTESTED consortium demonstrates a well-rounded expertise and a collaborative spirit, which are significant strengths. The work plan, KPIs and deliverables are very well structured. Resource allocation is appropriately planned, however, risk mitigation appears to be considered however, could have been discussed, specifically focusing on mitigation strategies. Overall, consortium capability and synergy seem solid.

Appraisal Scale per Criterion

Each criterion is evaluated on a scale up to 5, detailed as follows:

- 1 / POOR** *The proposal addresses the criterion in an inadequate manner or there are significant weaknesses.*
- 2 / FAIR** *The proposal addresses the criterion broadly, but there are still several weaknesses.*
- 3 / GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion well, but improvements are necessary.*
- 4 / VERY GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion very well, but some improvements are still possible.*
- 5 / EXCELLENT** *The proposal successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the criterion. Any shortcomings are minor.*

The overall threshold for the total score is 12/20.

Evaluation Summary Report

DRG4Food Open Call #1

Proposal Title: BDI4Fresh

Outcome of Phase 2 – Remote Evaluation

Criterion	Average Points
Technology Excellence and Innovation <i>Assessing projects on innovation, compliance with EU food policies, advancements in data-driven technology, user collaboration, ethical standards, and open-source contributions.</i>	4/5
Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs <i>Evaluating projects on cybersecurity expertise, privacy standards, dataset integrity, user data control, algorithm transparency, and enabling DRG realization.</i>	3/5
Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact <i>Assessing business viability, scalability, and impact through unique selling points, market research, competitor analysis, financial projections, and IP rights management.</i>	3/5
Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation <i>Assessing consortium capability and qualifications, including work plan clarity, milestone definition, resource allocation, and expertise for development.</i>	4/5
TOTAL POINTS	14/20

STATUS: NOT SELECTED FOR FUNDING

Feedback and Areas for Improvement

Technology Excellence and Innovation

The proposal presents a robust technological framework that aims to develop a new digital infrastructure for fresh food trading channels. The integration of i4Trust, Gaia-X and FEDeRATED into a Data Space architecture demonstrates a strong commitment to innovation and excellence. The focus on data-driven services, interoperability and sustainability aligns well with current technological advances and market needs. However, the transition from TRL 4 to 7, while ambitious, may face challenges in implementation and testing in real-world environments. The proposal would benefit from more detailed risk mitigation strategies regarding technology adoption and integration in different market ecosystems.

Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs

The proposal outlines a credible approach to data responsibility and transparency, with a clear alignment with the DRGs. The emphasis on data sovereignty, robust authentication, and a decentralized architecture for data exchange is notable. However, the proposal could enhance its approach by detailing mechanisms for ongoing monitoring and adaptation to emerging data protection regulations. Moreover, there are some references that seem to be related to DRG4FOOD components to be integrated into the proposed solution, although the reference is to project FOODITY. Furthermore, the engagement strategy with stakeholders and end-users on data governance could be more elaborated to ensure wider acceptance and trust.

Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact

The business model demonstrates the potential for scalability and significant impact,

particularly in improving the competitiveness of traditional grocery channels against digital giants. The focus on mutualized logistics services, business intelligence, and sustainability through data fairness presents a compelling value proposition. However, the proposal could strengthen its market analysis and financial projections, taking into account potential competition and market barriers. In addition, strategies for capturing and sustaining user engagement beyond initial adoption could be better addressed to ensure long-term viability and impact.

Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation

The consortium composition is well-balanced, featuring partners with expertise in relevant technological, business, and market aspects. The proposal outlines a clear plan for collaboration and resource allocation. However, it could benefit from a more detailed risk management plan and contingency strategies for addressing potential challenges in project execution. Planned outputs are referenced to FOODITY.

Appraisal Scale per Criterion

Each criterion is evaluated on a scale up to 5, detailed as follows:

- 1 / POOR** *The proposal addresses the criterion in an inadequate manner or there are significant weaknesses.*
- 2 / FAIR** *The proposal addresses the criterion broadly, but there are still several weaknesses.*
- 3 / GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion well, but improvements are necessary.*
- 4 / VERY GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion very well, but some improvements are still possible.*
- 5 / EXCELLENT** *The proposal successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the criterion. Any shortcomings are minor.*

The overall threshold for the total score is 12/20.

Evaluation Summary Report

DRG4Food Open Call #1

Proposal Title: BEE-CODE

Outcome of Phase 2 – Remote Evaluation

Criterion	Average Points
Technology Excellence and Innovation <i>Assessing projects on innovation, compliance with EU food policies, advancements in data-driven technology, user collaboration, ethical standards, and open-source contributions.</i>	3/5
Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs <i>Evaluating projects on cybersecurity expertise, privacy standards, dataset integrity, user data control, algorithm transparency, and enabling DRG realization.</i>	3/5
Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact <i>Assessing business viability, scalability, and impact through unique selling points, market research, competitor analysis, financial projections, and IP rights management.</i>	2.5/5
Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation <i>Assessing consortium capability and qualifications, including work plan clarity, milestone definition, resource allocation, and expertise for development.</i>	2.5/5
TOTAL POINTS	11/20

STATUS: NOT SELECTED FOR FUNDING

Feedback and Areas for Improvement

Technology Excellence and Innovation

BEE-CODE's Tech, Excellence and Innovation strengths include a clear alignment with DRG4Food challenges and the needs of the multiple stakeholders within the industry, showcasing innovation potential in digital food labeling for trust and transparency.

The BEE-CODE proposal is missing more detailed plans for user engagement to ensure their solution is co-designed with end-users ("some pilots?"), which is crucial for user sovereignty and trust. Additionally, while it mentions technological advancements, it could further clarify how these advancements represent a significant leap over current technologies. The proposal may also benefit from a detailed outline of the technology and infrastructure used and of its open-source contributions to the DRG4Food toolbox, demonstrating a commitment to the broader community and ecosystem.

Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs

BEE-CODE's strengths in this section include a focus on secure and transparent data handling, reflecting expertise in cybersecurity. The approach to privacy and dataset integrity indicates strong points. However, they may need to provide more details on user control over data, algorithmic clarity, and how they plan to realize specific Digital Responsibility Goals as well as establish the infrastructure in line with their claims.

Additionally, strategies for mitigating cybersecurity threats and algorithmic biases require further elaboration.

Lastly, more explicit discussions on ethical and legal considerations relevant to food traceability could strengthen the proposal.

Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact

While BEE-CODE's demonstrates the understanding of its users needs, it demonstrates its Unique Selling point in a very mediocre way. BEE-CODE needs to enhance their market fitness assessment by including a more detailed competitor analysis (indicating particular players, and comparing both features as well as benefits in much more detail), demonstrate and in detail outline their business model and commercialization strategy to ensure credibility and scalability. Path to market hasn't been discussed and impact has been weekly described. Their approach to Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) management and strategy for result exploitation might also be well-developed. Financial projections will only be performed and are not showcased.

Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation

The expertise within the consortium indicates a strong point, showcasing good collaboration and synergy. Areas for improvement could involve a more detailed risk assessment and mitigation strategy, ensuring all potential challenges are addressed.

The proposed work plan is generally well sounding, however, it has been developed on a very surface level. Missing is more project management information, like partner engagement activity, task description. Identification of milestones has to be made at the beginning of the project, and not during the project. Citizen engagement / pilots has not been described. KPIs are written as milestones and not quantifiable KPIs. Additionally, ensuring the adequacy of resources, both human and financial, to meet project objectives might require further elaboration to confirm the consortium's capability to execute the plan effectively.

Appraisal Scale per Criterion

Each criterion is evaluated on a scale up to 5, detailed as follows:

- 1 / POOR** *The proposal addresses the criterion in an inadequate manner or there are significant weaknesses.*
- 2 / FAIR** *The proposal addresses the criterion broadly, but there are still several weaknesses.*
- 3 / GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion well, but improvements are necessary.*
- 4 / VERY GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion very well, but some improvements are still possible.*
- 5 / EXCELLENT** *The proposal successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the criterion. Any shortcomings are minor.*

The overall threshold for the total score is 12/20.

Evaluation Summary Report

DRG4Food Open Call #1

Proposal Title: BeerConcept

Outcome of Phase 2 – Remote Evaluation

Criterion	Average Points
Technology Excellence and Innovation <i>Assessing projects on innovation, compliance with EU food policies, advancements in data-driven technology, user collaboration, ethical standards, and open-source contributions.</i>	3/5
Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs <i>Evaluating projects on cybersecurity expertise, privacy standards, dataset integrity, user data control, algorithm transparency, and enabling DRG realization.</i>	3.5/5
Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact <i>Assessing business viability, scalability, and impact through unique selling points, market research, competitor analysis, financial projections, and IP rights management.</i>	2.5/5
Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation <i>Assessing consortium capability and qualifications, including work plan clarity, milestone definition, resource allocation, and expertise for development.</i>	3/5
TOTAL POINTS	12/20

STATUS: NOT SELECTED FOR FUNDING

Feedback and Areas for Improvement

Technology Excellence and Innovation

The proposal only loosely aligns with DRG4FOODs challenges. There is a rudimentary outline of the proposals' technological approach. Overall, the technological excellence and innovative character of the proposal is underdeveloped. It does not become sufficiently clear what sets it apart from existing predictive algorithm systems in e-commerce. The proposal provides no measures for user engagement and co-design. Ethical, legal/policy considerations are not addressed. Open-source contribution is addressed.

Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs

The proposal provides answers to all relevant criteria and proposes well-founded and comprehensible solutions on digital responsibility can be implemented. The proposed solution itself is not likely to enable the DRGs.

Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact

While the proposed solution might be unique in the target market, the business plan, market analysis and exploitation plan is underdeveloped.

Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation

While the consortium has experience in the proposed field, on the whole there is a lack of diversification, especially in terms of digital technologies.

The person months (PM) required do not become apparent from the proposal, given the advanced state of the solution (TRL6) the proposed cost seem high, especially because brand & web redesign is part of the equation.

Appraisal Scale per Criterion

Each criterion is evaluated on a scale up to 5, detailed as follows:

- 1 / POOR** *The proposal addresses the criterion in an inadequate manner or there are significant weaknesses.*
- 2 / FAIR** *The proposal addresses the criterion broadly, but there are still several weaknesses.*
- 3 / GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion well, but improvements are necessary.*
- 4 / VERY GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion very well, but some improvements are still possible.*
- 5 / EXCELLENT** *The proposal successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the criterion. Any shortcomings are minor.*

The overall threshold for the total score is 12/20.

Evaluation Summary Report

DRG4Food Open Call #1

Proposal Title: *Boostainability*

Outcome of Phase 2 – Remote Evaluation

Criterion	Average Points
Technology Excellence and Innovation <i>Assessing projects on innovation, compliance with EU food policies, advancements in data-driven technology, user collaboration, ethical standards, and open-source contributions.</i>	4/5
Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs <i>Evaluating projects on cybersecurity expertise, privacy standards, dataset integrity, user data control, algorithm transparency, and enabling DRG realization.</i>	4/5
Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact <i>Assessing business viability, scalability, and impact through unique selling points, market research, competitor analysis, financial projections, and IP rights management.</i>	4.5/5
Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation <i>Assessing consortium capability and qualifications, including work plan clarity, milestone definition, resource allocation, and expertise for development.</i>	3.5/5
TOTAL POINTS	16/20

STATUS: NOT SELECTED FOR FUNDING

Feedback and Areas for Improvement

Technology Excellence and Innovation

The proposal effectively integrates advanced technologies such as IoT, RFID, sensors, blockchain, and AI to address traceability, sustainability, and privacy in the food industry.

The inclusion of Zero Knowledge Proof for privacy and the development of a consumer-facing app demonstrates significant innovation. However, the goal of moving from TRL 4-5 to 7 seems to be ambitious and highlights the challenges of integration complexity and real-world validation. Despite these hurdles, the project's innovative approach to improving food industry transparency and consumer trust is very good.

Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs

The team's extensive background in secure software design and cybersecurity, combined with its proactive approach to cybersecurity threats and commitment to user-friendly data rights implementation, is good.

The approach to data responsibility and transparency of this proposal is based on user-centric concept with ZKP principles. Overall, the approach to information security is well-described. It relies on the relevant expertise of the consortium. The proposal states an intent to obtain the ISO 27001 certificate, which is very positive. Several potential cybersecurity threats were identified and related to underlying technologies the solution will use.

On the other hand, the management of data subjects' rights is described broadly. This is a weakness. The proposal gives a list of several various data subject's rights that will be operationalised, without providing adequate description on how this will be achieved.

The issue of algorithmic biases is also briefly presented. This aspect of the proposal could be further improved, not only from the technical but from the legal/ethical point of view. This is a minor shortcoming.

Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact

Overall, BOOSTABILITY presents a balanced business plan. It includes several useful elements including a general description of the value model and incentives.

Additional efforts concerning market research as well as the competitor analysis with similar-scaled initiatives could benefit the proposal. Besides, focusing on more specific sales strategies including collaborations for market penetration could lead to a more competitive scalability plan and increase the overall impact of the proposal.

Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation

The consortium composition is strong, with StelvioTech and CluBE offering a wide range of expertise. The team's background in key projects and their diverse skills in technology, project management and stakeholder relations stand out. Although the work plan, resource allocation and KPIs indicate a well-prepared approach to project implementation, there's room for improvement in increasing the specificity of some KPIs for clearer success metrics. Moreover, since the project heavily relies on the proper implementation of the information security aspects critical for its success - the externalisation of the costs for security assessments including pentest is not justified. This is a weakness. This also implies lack of appropriate expertise concerning this aspect on the side of the consortium.

Appraisal Scale per Criterion

Each criterion is evaluated on a scale up to 5, detailed as follows:

- 1 / POOR** *The proposal addresses the criterion in an inadequate manner or there are significant weaknesses.*
- 2 / FAIR** *The proposal addresses the criterion broadly, but there are still several weaknesses.*
- 3 / GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion well, but improvements are necessary.*
- 4 / VERY GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion very well, but some improvements are still possible.*
- 5 / EXCELLENT** *The proposal successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the criterion. Any shortcomings are minor.*

The overall threshold for the total score is 12/20.

Evaluation Summary Report

DRG4Food Open Call #1

Proposal Title: B-Trace

Outcome of Phase 2 – Remote Evaluation

Criterion	Average Points
Technology Excellence and Innovation <i>Assessing projects on innovation, compliance with EU food policies, advancements in data-driven technology, user collaboration, ethical standards, and open-source contributions.</i>	3/5
Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs <i>Evaluating projects on cybersecurity expertise, privacy standards, dataset integrity, user data control, algorithm transparency, and enabling DRG realization.</i>	3.5/5
Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact <i>Assessing business viability, scalability, and impact through unique selling points, market research, competitor analysis, financial projections, and IP rights management.</i>	3/5
Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation <i>Assessing consortium capability and qualifications, including work plan clarity, milestone definition, resource allocation, and expertise for development.</i>	4/5
TOTAL POINTS	13.5/20

STATUS: NOT SELECTED FOR FUNDING

Feedback and Areas for Improvement

Technology Excellence and Innovation

The proposal elaborates on a basic level how the proposal aligns with the specific challenges of DRG4FOOD. There is a rather vague outline of the proposals' technological approach; the innovative character of the solution could have been more pronounced. Elaborations on the development of the TRL seem feasible while it remains to be seen if there is demand for a consumer-facing honey-tracing solution due to its narrow use case. The proposal provides some measures for user engagement and co-design. Ethical considerations are briefly addressed. Open-source contributions are addressed; however, it remains a bit vague how and what the proposals will provide to the DRG4FOOD toolbox and open-source community in general.

Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs

The proposal provides very basic answers to some relevant criteria and proposes arguments how DRGs will be enabled. Despite providing these answers little concrete connection is drawn between digital responsibility and the actual proposed solution. The proposal fails to go into detail on how (technically) digital responsibility will be implemented.

Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact

The proposed USPs do not seem to be supported by research and make some debatable assumptions. The competitive analysis, however, goes into more detail. Elaborations on the business model remain underdeveloped and rather opaque regarding underlying assumptions.

Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation

The workplan is basic but feasible given time and resources available. Description of the qualifications of the consortium partners is sufficient. No reference is made to risk management and mitigation.

Appraisal Scale per Criterion

Each criterion is evaluated on a scale up to 5, detailed as follows:

- 1 / POOR** *The proposal addresses the criterion in an inadequate manner or there are significant weaknesses.*
- 2 / FAIR** *The proposal addresses the criterion broadly, but there are still several weaknesses.*
- 3 / GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion well, but improvements are necessary.*
- 4 / VERY GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion very well, but some improvements are still possible.*
- 5 / EXCELLENT** *The proposal successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the criterion. Any shortcomings are minor.*

The overall threshold for the total score is 12/20.

Evaluation Summary Report

DRG4Food Open Call #1

Proposal Title: B-WELL

Outcome of Phase 2 – Remote Evaluation

Criterion	Average Points
Technology Excellence and Innovation <i>Assessing projects on innovation, compliance with EU food policies, advancements in data-driven technology, user collaboration, ethical standards, and open-source contributions.</i>	2.5/5
Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs <i>Evaluating projects on cybersecurity expertise, privacy standards, dataset integrity, user data control, algorithm transparency, and enabling DRG realization.</i>	3/5
Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact <i>Assessing business viability, scalability, and impact through unique selling points, market research, competitor analysis, financial projections, and IP rights management.</i>	4/5
Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation <i>Assessing consortium capability and qualifications, including work plan clarity, milestone definition, resource allocation, and expertise for development.</i>	3/5
TOTAL POINTS	12.5/20

STATUS: NOT SELECTED FOR FUNDING

Feedback and Areas for Improvement

Technology Excellence and Innovation

The B-WELL proposal showcases an innovative approach by integrating AI and NLP to enhance sustainable and health-conscious shopping experiences. However, the lack of a detailed explanation of how AI and NLP technologies will be specifically used to deliver the promised functionalities weakens the proposal's technological credibility. The proposal's TRL at the start and end of the project remains unclear, affecting the assessment of its innovation trajectory. The proposal lacks a comparison with existing blockchain solutions, detailed plan for achieving TRL 7, and specific end-user engagement strategies

Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs

B-WELL exhibits a strong commitment to data responsibility, aligning with DRGs through a comprehensive approach to user privacy, data security, and ethical AI use. The proposal outlines clear strategies for user control over data, mitigation of biases, and transparent data policies, which are commendable. However, further elaboration on the implementation of these strategies, particularly regarding algorithmic transparency and user data control, would strengthen the proposal.

Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact

The business model appears robust, targeting a growing market of health and sustainability-conscious consumers. The open-source approach and IPR management strategy demonstrate a forward-thinking commitment to innovation and community engagement. Market analysis and financial projections indicate a viable and scalable business. The

proposal requires deeper market analysis, competitor comparison, consumer adoption strategies, and elaboration on scalability beyond the initial market.

Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation

The consortium brings together diverse expertise in healthcare, digital marketing, and AI, which is positive. However, the small team size and the perceived lack of cybersecurity expertise concerns about the project's capacity to meet its ambitious objectives. While the involvement of certified cybersecurity professionals is planned, the proposal would benefit from expanding the core team to include dedicated cybersecurity and AI ethics roles. The proposal is missing detailed risk assessment and mitigation strategies.

Appraisal Scale per Criterion

Each criterion is evaluated on a scale up to 5, detailed as follows:

- 1 / POOR** *The proposal addresses the criterion in an inadequate manner or there are significant weaknesses.*
- 2 / FAIR** *The proposal addresses the criterion broadly, but there are still several weaknesses.*
- 3 / GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion well, but improvements are necessary.*
- 4 / VERY GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion very well, but some improvements are still possible.*
- 5 / EXCELLENT** *The proposal successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the criterion. Any shortcomings are minor.*

The overall threshold for the total score is 12/20.

Evaluation Summary Report

DRG4Food Open Call #1

Proposal Title: BYTE BITES

Outcome of Phase 2 – Remote Evaluation

Criterion	Average Points
Technology Excellence and Innovation <i>Assessing projects on innovation, compliance with EU food policies, advancements in data-driven technology, user collaboration, ethical standards, and open-source contributions.</i>	4
Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs <i>Evaluating projects on cybersecurity expertise, privacy standards, dataset integrity, user data control, algorithm transparency, and enabling DRG realization.</i>	4
Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact <i>Assessing business viability, scalability, and impact through unique selling points, market research, competitor analysis, financial projections, and IP rights management.</i>	3
Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation <i>Assessing consortium capability and qualifications, including work plan clarity, milestone definition, resource allocation, and expertise for development.</i>	4
TOTAL POINTS	15/20

STATUS: NOT SELECTED FOR FUNDING

Feedback and Areas for Improvement

Technology Excellence and Innovation

The proposal aligns well with DRG4Food's personal nutrition challenge, employing an innovative gamification and federated learning approach, engaging the community, and specifically targeting youngsters. However, while it suggests an intriguing concept with a European social enterprise for its open-source strategy, clarity on this approach is somewhat lacking. Additionally, the proposal's contribution to advancing the technology landscape could benefit from a more detailed exposition to fully capture its potential impact and innovation.

Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs

The proposal effectively justifies its approach to Digital Responsibility Goals (DRGs) and their application, providing a thorough overview of DRGs. However, the strategy for the actual realization of DRGs appears more conceptual than operational, lacking specific tactical details. This feedback suggests a need for a clearer, more actionable plan to operationalize DRGs within the project's framework.

Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact

The proposal outlines a comprehensive educational model, highlighting unique selling points and adopting a holistic approach through user experience, technology, community involvement, and engagement strategies. However, its scalability and business viability aspects remain somewhat ambiguous, suggesting a need for a more detailed exploration of these areas to fully assess the project's long-term potential and implementation strategy.

Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation

The proposal showcases a comprehensive consortium with detailed expertise and a well-defined resource allocation. However, the utilization of resources is at its peak, indicating a need for optimizing resource management to balance ambition with practical execution capabilities. The work plan and milestones are well-defined, however, the KPIs are not quantified. Risk assessment strategies could be further detailed. Enhancements in risk mitigation and a more detailed discussion on collaborative processes could fortify the proposal.

Appraisal Scale per Criterion

Each criterion is evaluated on a scale up to 5, detailed as follows:

- 1 / POOR** *The proposal addresses the criterion in an inadequate manner or there are significant weaknesses.*
- 2 / FAIR** *The proposal addresses the criterion broadly, but there are still several weaknesses.*
- 3 / GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion well, but improvements are necessary.*
- 4 / VERY GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion very well, but some improvements are still possible.*
- 5 / EXCELLENT** *The proposal successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the criterion. Any shortcomings are minor.*

The overall threshold for the total score is 12/20.

Evaluation Summary Report

DRG4Food Open Call #1

Proposal Title: Cacao TEES

Outcome of Phase 2 – Remote Evaluation

Criterion	Average Points
Technology Excellence and Innovation <i>Assessing projects on innovation, compliance with EU food policies, advancements in data-driven technology, user collaboration, ethical standards, and open-source contributions.</i>	4/5
Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs <i>Evaluating projects on cybersecurity expertise, privacy standards, dataset integrity, user data control, algorithm transparency, and enabling DRG realization.</i>	3.5/5
Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact <i>Assessing business viability, scalability, and impact through unique selling points, market research, competitor analysis, financial projections, and IP rights management.</i>	4/5
Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation <i>Assessing consortium capability and qualifications, including work plan clarity, milestone definition, resource allocation, and expertise for development.</i>	5/5
TOTAL POINTS	16.5/20

STATUS: NOT SELECTED FOR FUNDING

Feedback and Areas for Improvement

Technology Excellence and Innovation

The CacaoTEES project aligns well with DRG4Food challenges by promoting sustainable practices and enhancing smallholder farmers' livelihoods. Its use of near-infrared spectroscopy for cacao pulp is innovative, advancing the state of the art in food processing technology. However, the proposal could benefit from more details on market launch feasibility and end-user engagement strategies. Ethical considerations seem to be addressed, but the plan for open-source contributions could be clearer.

Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs

The CacaoTEES project's approach to data responsibility and transparency is not fully detailed in the available information. To improve, it should explicitly address team expertise in cybersecurity, outline specific strategies for data privacy, integrity, and user control, and clarify how it plans to align with DRGs. The proposal would benefit from a clearer explanation of how it intends to mitigate potential cybersecurity threats and biases.

Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact

CacaoTEES demonstrates a unique approach by utilizing cacao pulp, addressing waste and enhancing farmer income, which aligns with user needs and sustainability goals. The claim of limited competitor applications for CacaoTEES could indicate a niche market opportunity, potentially positioning the project advantageously. However, it's essential to critically assess market dynamics and potential indirect competitors or alternative solutions addressing similar challenges. A thorough competitor analysis, even in seemingly unique markets, can uncover insights into market trends, consumer behavior, and potential challenges, enhancing the project's strategy and resilience. The business model shows promise, particularly in

creating new value streams, but would benefit from clearer financial projections and scaling strategies. While IPR management is crucial and well developed, details on this and how results will be exploited are less clear.

Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation

The CacaoTEES consortium demonstrates a strong mix of technical and commercial expertise, crucial for the project's success. The work plan, KPIs and milestones seem well-defined, though risk assessment and mitigation strategies could be further detailed. Resource allocation appears adequate, but the clarity on how resources are matched to tasks could be improved. The collaboration among partners is a strength, yet more details on synergies could enhance the proposal.

Appraisal Scale per Criterion

Each criterion is evaluated on a scale up to 5, detailed as follows:

- 1 / POOR** *The proposal addresses the criterion in an inadequate manner or there are significant weaknesses.*
- 2 / FAIR** *The proposal addresses the criterion broadly, but there are still several weaknesses.*
- 3 / GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion well, but improvements are necessary.*
- 4 / VERY GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion very well, but some improvements are still possible.*
- 5 / EXCELLENT** *The proposal successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the criterion. Any shortcomings are minor.*

The overall threshold for the total score is 12/20.

Evaluation Summary Report

DRG4Food Open Call #1

Proposal Title: ChooseYFood

Outcome of Phase 2 – Remote Evaluation

Criterion	Average Points
Technology Excellence and Innovation <i>Assessing projects on innovation, compliance with EU food policies, advancements in data-driven technology, user collaboration, ethical standards, and open-source contributions.</i>	3/5
Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs <i>Evaluating projects on cybersecurity expertise, privacy standards, dataset integrity, user data control, algorithm transparency, and enabling DRG realization.</i>	2.5/5
Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact <i>Assessing business viability, scalability, and impact through unique selling points, market research, competitor analysis, financial projections, and IP rights management.</i>	3/5
Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation <i>Assessing consortium capability and qualifications, including work plan clarity, milestone definition, resource allocation, and expertise for development.</i>	4/5
TOTAL POINTS	12.5/20

STATUS: NOT SELECTED FOR FUNDING

Feedback and Areas for Improvement

Technology Excellence and Innovation

The proposal aligns with some of the challenges of DRG4FOOD, however, the elaboration on technological excellence remains vague or incomplete (e.g. it is not clear what data exactly will be put on blockchain). Especially, in terms of innovation the proposal lacks novelty. The plan TRL advancement seems feasible. The proposal mentions measures for user testing but it remains unclear how this will be realized. There is a strong focus on open-sourcing.

Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs

Despite providing very basic answers to all relevant criteria little concrete connection is drawn between digital responsibility and the actual proposed solution. There is the potential of the proposal to enable the DRGs.

Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact

USP of the proposal remains underdeveloped and business model is described in vague terms. While other criteria were not addressed, the open-source approach can be mentioned as a notable characteristic.

Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation

The workplan is clear and feasible given time and resources available. The proposal transparently sets out a clear roadmap and timeline for deliverables. Risks and their mitigation are, however, not discussed. The proposed budget does not entirely match the ambition of the proposal. The consortium partners are well qualified, and their fields of

expertise provide for useful synergies. In terms of risk management only delays were mentioned.

Appraisal Scale per Criterion

Each criterion is evaluated on a scale up to 5, detailed as follows:

- 1 / POOR** *The proposal addresses the criterion in an inadequate manner or there are significant weaknesses.*
- 2 / FAIR** *The proposal addresses the criterion broadly, but there are still several weaknesses.*
- 3 / GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion well, but improvements are necessary.*
- 4 / VERY GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion very well, but some improvements are still possible.*
- 5 / EXCELLENT** *The proposal successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the criterion. Any shortcomings are minor.*

The overall threshold for the total score is 12/20.

Evaluation Summary Report

DRG4Food Open Call #1

Proposal Title: CityVeg

Outcome of Phase 2 – Remote Evaluation

Criterion	Average Points
Technology Excellence and Innovation <i>Assessing projects on innovation, compliance with EU food policies, advancements in data-driven technology, user collaboration, ethical standards, and open-source contributions.</i>	4/5
Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs <i>Evaluating projects on cybersecurity expertise, privacy standards, dataset integrity, user data control, algorithm transparency, and enabling DRG realization.</i>	4/5
Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact <i>Assessing business viability, scalability, and impact through unique selling points, market research, competitor analysis, financial projections, and IP rights management.</i>	4/5
Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation <i>Assessing consortium capability and qualifications, including work plan clarity, milestone definition, resource allocation, and expertise for development.</i>	4.5/5
TOTAL POINTS	16.5/20

STATUS: NOT SELECTED FOR FUNDING

Feedback and Areas for Improvement

Technology Excellence and Innovation

CityVeg's proposal exhibits a strong alignment with DRG4Food challenges, particularly in fostering trust and engagement through innovative AI-driven urban farming technology.

The project's objectives are clear, innovative, and directly respond to urban agriculture's current needs. Technical aspects of the solution are well described. There is room for improvement in detailing the market launch plan and demonstrating feasibility at a higher TRL. User engagement is central to the project, but specifics on co-design activities could be enhanced. Ethical considerations and intentions for open source contributions are mentioned but would benefit from further elaboration.

Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs

CityVeg's strengths in data responsibility and transparency likely include plans for secure data handling and privacy. However, the proposal would benefit from a more detailed explanation of the team's cybersecurity expertise and the specific mitigation strategies for identified threats. User control over data and transparency measures are acknowledged but could be more explicitly defined. The proposal's alignment with DRGs seems apparent, yet further details on the implementation would strengthen it.

The foundational elements of data responsibility and transparency are solid, and the areas for improvement, while necessary, do not critically undermine the core strengths of the proposal in this criterion.

Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact

CityVeg's unique selling point lies in its AI-driven urban farming system, which strongly aligns with current user needs for sustainable urban agriculture. The business model is innovative, suggesting scalability and impact, but could be bolstered by an even more detailed competitor analysis. Basically, proposal lacks a detailed comparison and does not address how CityVeg will capture market share from these existing. The proposal suggests a clear strategy for commercialization, with a thought through financial projections.

Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation

The CityVeg consortium is well-equipped with a multidisciplinary team and a clear work plan, featuring comprehensive risk assessment and mitigation strategies. The project's strengths lie in its detailed planning and the diverse expertise of team members, covering all necessary aspects from technical development to community engagement. Although the roles and contributions of individual team members could be more explicitly defined, as well as milestones defined at the proposal stage, the overall consortium capability and resource allocation are robust, justifying a high evaluation score.

Appraisal Scale per Criterion

Each criterion is evaluated on a scale up to 5, detailed as follows:

- 1 / POOR** *The proposal addresses the criterion in an inadequate manner or there are significant weaknesses.*
- 2 / FAIR** *The proposal addresses the criterion broadly, but there are still several weaknesses.*
- 3 / GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion well, but improvements are necessary.*
- 4 / VERY GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion very well, but some improvements are still possible.*
- 5 / EXCELLENT** *The proposal successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the criterion. Any shortcomings are minor.*

The overall threshold for the total score is 12/20.

Evaluation Summary Report

DRG4Food Open Call #1

Proposal Title: CTC4DFT

Outcome of Phase 2 – Remote Evaluation

Criterion	Average Points
Technology Excellence and Innovation <i>Assessing projects on innovation, compliance with EU food policies, advancements in data-driven technology, user collaboration, ethical standards, and open-source contributions.</i>	3.5/5
Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs <i>Evaluating projects on cybersecurity expertise, privacy standards, dataset integrity, user data control, algorithm transparency, and enabling DRG realization.</i>	3/5
Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact <i>Assessing business viability, scalability, and impact through unique selling points, market research, competitor analysis, financial projections, and IP rights management.</i>	2.5/5
Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation <i>Assessing consortium capability and qualifications, including work plan clarity, milestone definition, resource allocation, and expertise for development.</i>	3/5
TOTAL POINTS	12/20

STATUS: NOT SELECTED FOR FUNDING

Feedback and Areas for Improvement

Technology Excellence and Innovation

The proposal presents a novel integration of physical and digital technologies to improve the transparency and safety of the cold food supply chain, using smart labels with CTI indicators and QR codes for real-time temperature monitoring. The use of smart data models for interoperable data exchange is innovative and supports digital accountability and transparency. The approach to integrating analog and digital monitoring methods is good and has the potential to set a new standard for the industry. While the technology is promising, the proposal could benefit from exploring advances in sensor technology and IoT devices for more automated, real-time data collection without manual scanning. In addition, detailing the specifics of the patent-pending smart label could further substantiate the innovation claim of the proposal.

Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs

The commitment to data stewardship and transparency is evident, with a focus on interoperable smart data models and user-centric data control. The approach aligns with the principles of digital responsibility and transparency, facilitating access to temperature history and product journey. However, the proposal lacks technical details on how the security measures and data integrity measures will be implemented. It would benefit from a more detailed explanation of the cybersecurity frameworks, encryption methods and access control mechanisms to protect the data lake and API services.

Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact

The proposal identifies a clear market need and presents a scalable solution with environmental benefits, such as reduced food waste and improved food safety. The SaaS

business model and tiered pricing strategy demonstrate a thoughtful approach to market entry and scalability. While the business model is well-articulated, a more detailed market analysis and competitor comparison could strengthen the proposal. Furthermore, addressing the scalability of the technology in terms of manufacturing and deployment logistics would provide a clearer path to market expansion.

Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation

The detailed work plan and distribution of tasks demonstrate a well-organized approach to project management. The consortium brings together partners with complementary skills, from technology development to sustainability consultancy. In particular, the project team appears to be strong, but the presence of only one developer raises concerns about the technical capacity to deliver the project within the proposed timeframe. Expanding the technical team or detailing external support for development tasks could mitigate this concern.

Appraisal Scale per Criterion

Each criterion is evaluated on a scale up to 5, detailed as follows:

- 1 / POOR** *The proposal addresses the criterion in an inadequate manner or there are significant weaknesses.*
- 2 / FAIR** *The proposal addresses the criterion broadly, but there are still several weaknesses.*
- 3 / GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion well, but improvements are necessary.*
- 4 / VERY GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion very well, but some improvements are still possible.*
- 5 / EXCELLENT** *The proposal successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the criterion. Any shortcomings are minor.*

The overall threshold for the total score is 12/20.

Evaluation Summary Report

DRG4Food Open Call #1

Proposal Title: DDS4Honey

Outcome of Phase 2 – Remote Evaluation

Criterion	Average Points
Technology Excellence and Innovation <i>Assessing projects on innovation, compliance with EU food policies, advancements in data-driven technology, user collaboration, ethical standards, and open-source contributions.</i>	3.5/5
Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs <i>Evaluating projects on cybersecurity expertise, privacy standards, dataset integrity, user data control, algorithm transparency, and enabling DRG realization.</i>	3.5/5
Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact <i>Assessing business viability, scalability, and impact through unique selling points, market research, competitor analysis, financial projections, and IP rights management.</i>	2/5
Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation <i>Assessing consortium capability and qualifications, including work plan clarity, milestone definition, resource allocation, and expertise for development.</i>	4/5
TOTAL POINTS	13/20

STATUS: NOT SELECTED FOR FUNDING

Feedback and Areas for Improvement

Technology Excellence and Innovation

The proposal addresses the DRG4Food specific challenge area “Tracking Food”, while keeping an eye on trust and citizen engagement. The aspect of user sovereignty is not entirely clearly addressed.

The proposal has a somewhat ambitious technological approach, but not it’s not very clear in what extend it goes beyond the current state of the art. The level of sophistication of some parts of the solution is not appropriately substantiated.

The concept has a level of novelty and its relevant to the call.

More details would be needed to properly assess the market launch of the proposed solution as feasible.

The extent and effectiveness of planned engagement with end users in co-designing and testing the solution appears to be appropriate. Some of the measures for dissemination that refer to the “publication of the outcomes in technical journals that deal with blockchain technologies” appear to be more appropriate for longer projects with a more research scope.

It's not entirely clear how the proposal has addresses ethical and legal considerations relevant to the project.

There is no clear indication of whether the proposed project will contribute to the DRG4Food toolbox with open source solutions.

Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs

The team’s expertise in cybersecurity is not presented in detail. The identification of

cybersecurity threats and the strategies for their mitigation are thorough. A point that remains unclear is how blockchain is expected to be used to store the actual data.

The proposal's approach to privacy, including how personal data is handled securely and transparently, appears to be appropriate.

The strategies for ensuring dataset integrity and mitigating potential biases presented by the proposal, appear to be appropriate.

A process for reviewing the clarity of algorithmic outputs and the assessment and mitigation of algorithmic bias, is in place.

The proposal adequately facilitates user control over data and establishes transparency measures.

There is no clear indication that the proposal has the potential to realize at least one DRG.

Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact

The presented USPs of the proposed solution, their alignment with user needs, and the value proposition of the solution, are fine.

The market analysis and the competitor analysis are not sufficiently comprehensive.

The credibility of the business model is not appropriate and there are no financial projections. Furthermore, the proposal presents a focus on raising “future funding, donations and/or sponsors”, while a subscription-based approach is presented as a “possible exploitation venue” that “would give a commercial aspect to the platform”.

The proposal's approach to IPR management is presented in a somewhat appropriate level of detail.

Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation

The clarity and feasibility of the proposed work plan is not supported with the appropriate amount of details and the same applies to the definition and feasibility of milestones and deliverables.

The procedures for risk assessment and the strategies for risk mitigation have not been described.

The resource allocation appears to be appropriate. The strength of collaboration is appropriate, and the individual capacities of the team members appear to be relevant, although more detail would be appreciated. In terms of gender balance in the consortium, all 3 team members that we have CVs and gender information on, are male. Therefore, there is no gender balance.

Appraisal Scale per Criterion

Each criterion is evaluated on a scale up to 5, detailed as follows:

- 1 / POOR** *The proposal addresses the criterion in an inadequate manner or there are significant weaknesses.*
- 2 / FAIR** *The proposal addresses the criterion broadly, but there are still several weaknesses.*
- 3 / GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion well, but improvements are necessary.*
- 4 / VERY GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion very well, but some improvements are still possible.*
- 5 / EXCELLENT** *The proposal successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the criterion. Any shortcomings are minor.*

The overall threshold for the total score is 12/20.

Evaluation Summary Report

DRG4Food Open Call #1

Proposal Title: DIGFOA

Outcome of Phase 2 – Remote Evaluation

Criterion	Average Points
Technology Excellence and Innovation <i>Assessing projects on innovation, compliance with EU food policies, advancements in data-driven technology, user collaboration, ethical standards, and open-source contributions.</i>	4
Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs <i>Evaluating projects on cybersecurity expertise, privacy standards, dataset integrity, user data control, algorithm transparency, and enabling DRG realization.</i>	4
Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact <i>Assessing business viability, scalability, and impact through unique selling points, market research, competitor analysis, financial projections, and IP rights management.</i>	4
Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation <i>Assessing consortium capability and qualifications, including work plan clarity, milestone definition, resource allocation, and expertise for development.</i>	3.5
TOTAL POINTS	15.5

STATUS: NOT SELECTED FOR FUNDING

Feedback and Areas for Improvement

Technology Excellence and Innovation

The proposal outlines a comprehensive approach combining blockchain technology for traceability with advanced analytical techniques for authenticity verification in the food industry, a sector where fraud can have significant health and economic impacts. This innovative blend addresses both the traceability of the food supply chain and the verification of the food product's authenticity, leveraging technologies such as Isotope Ratio Mass Spectrometry, Gas Chromatography, and blockchain. The proposal's reliance on external experts for the development of the blockchain-based solution is a concern. While the project team includes a professor with very extensive expertise in blockchain, the absence of dedicated blockchain developers within the core team could present a risk to the project's successful implementation.

Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs

The proposal shows a strong commitment to data stewardship and transparency, which aligns well with the DRGs. It emphasises the importance of protecting user privacy, ensuring authentication and real-time validation of food certificates without the processing of personal data, thereby enhancing trust. While the proposal outlines a robust framework for data responsibility and transparency, the implementation details of these principles, especially regarding data validation before entering the blockchain (to mitigate the garbage-in, garbage-out problem), could be further elaborated to strengthen trust in data integrity.

Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact

The proposal convincingly describes the business viability and potential impact of the DFA platform, citing a significant market for both traceability and authenticity in the food

industry. The inclusion of analytical tokens (ATs) for risk management and the potential for significant cost reductions and performance improvements across the supply chain are particularly compelling. While the market potential and scalability are well-articulated, the proposal could benefit from a more detailed strategy for overcoming consumer acceptance challenges, especially regarding user interfaces and the adoption of new technologies by the food industry's stakeholders.

Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation

The consortium brings together a diverse team with expertise in marketing, blockchain research, food authenticity, and quality management. This multidisciplinary approach is well-suited to tackling the complex challenges of food fraud. The critical weakness is the current absence of blockchain developers within the team. While the project plans to hire external experts, the lack of in-house expertise in a key technology area could impact the project's agility and the ability to adapt to technical challenges.

Appraisal Scale per Criterion

Each criterion is evaluated on a scale up to 5, detailed as follows:

- 1 / POOR** *The proposal addresses the criterion in an inadequate manner or there are significant weaknesses.*
- 2 / FAIR** *The proposal addresses the criterion broadly, but there are still several weaknesses.*
- 3 / GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion well, but improvements are necessary.*
- 4 / VERY GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion very well, but some improvements are still possible.*
- 5 / EXCELLENT** *The proposal successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the criterion. Any shortcomings are minor.*

The overall threshold for the total score is 12/20.

Evaluation Summary Report

DRG4Food Open Call #1

Proposal Title: DiRRAS

Outcome of Phase 2 – Remote Evaluation

Criterion	Average Points
Technology Excellence and Innovation <i>Assessing projects on innovation, compliance with EU food policies, advancements in data-driven technology, user collaboration, ethical standards, and open-source contributions.</i>	4/5
Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs <i>Evaluating projects on cybersecurity expertise, privacy standards, dataset integrity, user data control, algorithm transparency, and enabling DRG realization.</i>	5/5
Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact <i>Assessing business viability, scalability, and impact through unique selling points, market research, competitor analysis, financial projections, and IP rights management.</i>	4/5
Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation <i>Assessing consortium capability and qualifications, including work plan clarity, milestone definition, resource allocation, and expertise for development.</i>	4/5
TOTAL POINTS	17/20

STATUS: NOT SELECTED FOR FUNDING

Feedback and Areas for Improvement

Technology Excellence and Innovation

The DiRRAS project demonstrates strong alignment with DRG4Food's objectives, leveraging innovative AI and machine learning technologies to enhance trust and transparency in the food sector. It excels in applying state-of-the-art tools for risk and reputation analysis, with clear and robust objectives. However, to secure a higher score, the proposal could benefit from elaborating on its end-user engagement, and expanding on its ethical considerations and open-source contributions.

Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs

The DiRRAS project showcases robust cybersecurity expertise and a comprehensive approach to data protection, with a team experienced in secure software design. Their commitment to GDPR compliance and user data control is clear, yet the proposal would benefit from more enhanced clarity on maintaining dataset integrity. The project's dedication to transparency, user control over data, and the ethical use of AI align with DRG4Food's objectives, enhancing user sovereignty and trust in technology within the food industry.

Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact

The DiRRAS proposal showcases several strong unique selling points that distinguish its approach to digital reputation and risk management within the food industry, particularly with its advanced scoring system and inclusive user experience. The project is committed to ethical transparency and explainability in AI decision-making, aligning with industry standards. While DiRRAS has identified a clear niche in combining reputation management with food safety and has outlined a scalability plan.

Additionally, while the financial projections and commercialization strategy are addressed, further details would strengthen the proposal (such as commercialization and path-to-market strategy and distribution channels). The approach to IPR management and result exploitation is thoughtful but would benefit from more explicit details on how the results will be used and the potential revenue streams.

Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation

The DiRRAS consortium brings together a multidisciplinary team with substantial expertise in AI, ML, data analytics, and the food industry, particularly olive oil. The project is structured to reach TRL7 within 12 months, with clear milestones for development, beta testing, feature integration, and operational testing. Strengths include a strong focus on responsible technology use, user-centric development, and adaptability to industry changes. However, the work plan could benefit from more detailed risk assessment strategies and specific mitigation plans. While the allocation of resources appears well-managed, further clarification on the roles and contributions of each consortium member could enhance the proposal. The collaboration with industry partners like Filaios is a significant advantage, providing real-world insights and validation opportunities.

Appraisal Scale per Criterion

Each criterion is evaluated on a scale up to 5, detailed as follows:

- 1 / POOR** *The proposal addresses the criterion in an inadequate manner or there are significant weaknesses.*
- 2 / FAIR** *The proposal addresses the criterion broadly, but there are still several weaknesses.*
- 3 / GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion well, but improvements are necessary.*
- 4 / VERY GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion very well, but some improvements are still possible.*
- 5 / EXCELLENT** *The proposal successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the criterion. Any shortcomings are minor.*

The overall threshold for the total score is 12/20.

Evaluation Summary Report

DRG4Food Open Call #1

Proposal Title: DISH

Outcome of Phase 2 – Remote Evaluation

Criterion	Average Points
Technology Excellence and Innovation <i>Assessing projects on innovation, compliance with EU food policies, advancements in data-driven technology, user collaboration, ethical standards, and open-source contributions.</i>	4/5
Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs <i>Evaluating projects on cybersecurity expertise, privacy standards, dataset integrity, user data control, algorithm transparency, and enabling DRG realization.</i>	4/5
Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact <i>Assessing business viability, scalability, and impact through unique selling points, market research, competitor analysis, financial projections, and IP rights management.</i>	3/5
Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation <i>Assessing consortium capability and qualifications, including work plan clarity, milestone definition, resource allocation, and expertise for development.</i>	3/5
TOTAL POINTS	14/5

STATUS: NOT SELECTED FOR FUNDING

Feedback and Areas for Improvement

Technology Excellence and Innovation

The proposal addresses well the DRG4Food specific challenge area “Targeted Nutrition”, while having strong emphasis on trust, citizen engagement, and user sovereignty. The proposal has an ambitious technological approach, which promised to go beyond the current state of the art.

The market launch of the proposed solution appears to be feasible.

The information level about the extent and effectiveness of planned engagement with end users in co-designing and testing the solution, is not appropriate.

The proposal has in place a plan for addressing ethical and legal considerations relevant to the project.

The proposed project is willing to contribute to the DRG4Food toolbox with open source solutions.

Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs

The proposal outlines strong commitments to data privacy, user sovereignty, and ethical data practices, with a clear focus on securing personal data and ensuring transparency. The approach to handling special category data on-device and the consideration of ethics in data collection are strengths. A more detailed plan for user engagement in data decisions could further improve this score. However, the proposal could provide more clarity on how data will be anonymized and aggregated to ensure compliance with regulations, and it lacks a comprehensive strategy for addressing potential breaches and ensuring long-term data integrity.

Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact

The proposal effectively highlights its USPs, demonstrating alignment with user needs and a compelling value proposition. Market and competitor analyses are considered adequate. However, the proposal lacks detailed information regarding its business model and does not include financial projections, which are crucial for assessing its economic feasibility. Additionally, the strategy for IPR management is not described with sufficient detail, indicating an area that requires further elaboration to ensure a comprehensive understanding of the proposal's approach to protecting and managing its innovations.

Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation

The project plan is well-structured with clear phases, KPIs. The procedures for risk assessment and have been described in detail but there no clear indication of risks and respective mitigation strategies.

The resource allocation appears to be appropriate but there is lack of information on what each of the category entails.

The strength of collaboration is appropriate and the individual capacities of the team members appear to be relevant, although more detail would be needed. The consortium has a gender balance.

Appraisal Scale per Criterion

Each criterion is evaluated on a scale up to 5, detailed as follows:

- 1 / POOR** *The proposal addresses the criterion in an inadequate manner or there are significant weaknesses.*
- 2 / FAIR** *The proposal addresses the criterion broadly, but there are still several weaknesses.*
- 3 / GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion well, but improvements are necessary.*
- 4 / VERY GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion very well, but some improvements are still possible.*
- 5 / EXCELLENT** *The proposal successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the criterion. Any shortcomings are minor.*

The overall threshold for the total score is 12/20.

Evaluation Summary Report

DRG4Food Open Call #1

Proposal Title: DNA4Olive

Outcome of Phase 2 – Remote Evaluation

Criterion	Average Points
Technology Excellence and Innovation <i>Assessing projects on innovation, compliance with EU food policies, advancements in data-driven technology, user collaboration, ethical standards, and open-source contributions.</i>	3.5/5
Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs <i>Evaluating projects on cybersecurity expertise, privacy standards, dataset integrity, user data control, algorithm transparency, and enabling DRG realization.</i>	3.5/5
Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact <i>Assessing business viability, scalability, and impact through unique selling points, market research, competitor analysis, financial projections, and IP rights management.</i>	3.5/5
Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation <i>Assessing consortium capability and qualifications, including work plan clarity, milestone definition, resource allocation, and expertise for development.</i>	3.5/5
TOTAL POINTS	14/20

STATUS: NOT SELECTED FOR FUNDING

Feedback and Areas for Improvement

Technology Excellence and Innovation

The proposal addresses well the DRG4Food specific challenge area “Food Tracking”.

Moreover, there is emphasis on trust, citizen engagement, and user sovereignty, although the last is mostly focused on the producers' side.

Although the proposal has a somewhat ambitious technological approach, it's not entirely clear how it goes beyond the current state of the art in the area of origin identification and traceability in the olive oil sector. Furthermore, it's not clear how integrating “digital twins” technologies can actually enhance transparency and therefore traceability in every step of the value chain.

Although the concept is not very novel, it's useful and it's definitely relevant to the call.

Due to the number of different technologies that are mentioned for building the solution (e.g digital twins, blockchain etc), it's not easy to assess the actual feasibility for market launch. More information and clarity on what would be actually used to deliver the promised solution, would be needed to convince the market launch is feasible.

The extent and effectiveness of planned engagement with end users in co-designing and testing the solution appears to be appropriate.

The proposal has in place a plan for addressing ethical and legal considerations relevant to the project.

There is no indication that the proposed project will contribute to the DRG4Food toolbox with open source solutions.

Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs

The team's expertise in cybersecurity is good, as the identification of cybersecurity threats and the strategies for their mitigation appear to be appropriate.

In terms of privacy and data handling, the proposed approach appears to be appropriate, although it's a bit more common in research projects than when building commercial applications.

The strategies for ensuring dataset integrity and mitigating potential biases presented by the proposal, appear to be appropriate.

A process for reviewing the clarity of algorithmic outputs and the assessment and mitigation of algorithmic bias, is in place.

The proposal adequately facilitates user control over data and establishes transparency measures.

The proposal has the potential to realize at least one DRG criterion.

Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact

The USPs of the proposed solution, their alignment with user needs on olive oil traceability and sustainability, and the value proposition of the solution, are presented adequately.

What is not clear is what is the value proposition of the solution in terms of consumers' reach.

Although there is a market analysis, including competitor analysis, it also includes applications like Gaiasense, which is not relevant because it's a smart farming solution.

The credibility of the business model and the financial projections is not sufficiently justified, as there are not sufficient data about the producers that would be willing to pay a starting fee of 5000 and an annual fee of 1400 from the 2nd year onwards. To make this more credible, more information about how the products and the data will be promoted to the consumers would be needed.

The proposal's approach to IPR management within the consortium is clear. Moreover, the strategy for disseminating the project results and exploiting the results appears to be very focused on the scientific community, something that is not aligned with the proposed business plan.

Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation

The clarity and feasibility of the proposed work plan is adequate. Although milestones are not specifically mentioned, it's clear what will be delivered in each phase.

There is no clear indication on the procedures for risk assessment and the strategies for risk mitigation. The resource allocation cannot be assessed, as the table with the project costs is missing. The strength of collaboration is appropriate and the individual capacities of the team members appear to be relevant, although some more detail would be appreciated. In terms of gender balance in the consortium, more than 1/3 of the team members are female and the rest are male.

Appraisal Scale per Criterion

Each criterion is evaluated on a scale up to 5, detailed as follows:

- 1 / POOR** *The proposal addresses the criterion in an inadequate manner or there are significant weaknesses.*
- 2 / FAIR** *The proposal addresses the criterion broadly, but there are still several weaknesses.*
- 3 / GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion well, but improvements are necessary.*
- 4 / VERY GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion very well, but some improvements are still possible.*
- 5 / EXCELLENT** *The proposal successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the criterion. Any shortcomings are minor.*

The overall threshold for the total score is 12/20.

Evaluation Summary Report

DRG4Food Open Call #1

Proposal Title: DRG4Salmon

Outcome of Phase 2 – Remote Evaluation

Criterion	Average Points
Technology Excellence and Innovation <i>Assessing projects on innovation, compliance with EU food policies, advancements in data-driven technology, user collaboration, ethical standards, and open-source contributions.</i>	4/5
Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs <i>Evaluating projects on cybersecurity expertise, privacy standards, dataset integrity, user data control, algorithm transparency, and enabling DRG realization.</i>	3/5
Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact <i>Assessing business viability, scalability, and impact through unique selling points, market research, competitor analysis, financial projections, and IP rights management.</i>	5/5
Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation <i>Assessing consortium capability and qualifications, including work plan clarity, milestone definition, resource allocation, and expertise for development.</i>	4.5/5
TOTAL POINTS	16.5/20

STATUS: NOT SELECTED FOR FUNDING

Feedback and Areas for Improvement

Technology Excellence and Innovation

The proposal is well-aligned with the challenge of food tracking, showcasing an innovative technological approach using InfraRed Sensor technology and plans for conducting focus groups. However, it needs to clarify its connection to citizen rights and digital responsibility. Additionally, the proposal does not detail its approach to open source contributions and community engagement, areas that could enhance its impact and foster broader collaboration within the digital and food sectors.

Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs

The proposal effectively highlights DRGs with a particular emphasis on privacy. However, it does not sufficiently articulate how it plans to enhance the understanding or application of digital responsibility principles and approaches, suggesting a need for a clearer exposition of its innovative contributions to the field of digital responsibility.

Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact

The proposal effectively outlines the logic behind the fish case, boasts a strong partner network conducive to scalability, and details USPs alongside a clear growth calculation. However, it predominantly adopts a commercial stance, raising questions about its broader societal and economic benefits. Highlighting the proposal's impact beyond commercial success could provide a more holistic view of its value.

Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation

The proposal showcases a well-documented consortium with defined capabilities, qualifications, and expertise, alongside a meticulously detailed resource allocation. However,

the use of resources is noted to be at its maximum potential, suggesting a need for optimization to ensure efficiency and sustainability in project execution.

Appraisal Scale per Criterion

Each criterion is evaluated on a scale up to 5, detailed as follows:

- 1 / POOR** *The proposal addresses the criterion in an inadequate manner or there are significant weaknesses.*
- 2 / FAIR** *The proposal addresses the criterion broadly, but there are still several weaknesses.*
- 3 / GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion well, but improvements are necessary.*
- 4 / VERY GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion very well, but some improvements are still possible.*
- 5 / EXCELLENT** *The proposal successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the criterion. Any shortcomings are minor.*

The overall threshold for the total score is 12/20.

Evaluation Summary Report

DRG4Food Open Call #1

Proposal Title: ECO4EDU

Outcome of Phase 2 – Remote Evaluation

Criterion	Average Points
Technology Excellence and Innovation <i>Assessing projects on innovation, compliance with EU food policies, advancements in data-driven technology, user collaboration, ethical standards, and open-source contributions.</i>	4.5/5
Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs <i>Evaluating projects on cybersecurity expertise, privacy standards, dataset integrity, user data control, algorithm transparency, and enabling DRG realization.</i>	4/5
Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact <i>Assessing business viability, scalability, and impact through unique selling points, market research, competitor analysis, financial projections, and IP rights management.</i>	3.5/5
Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation <i>Assessing consortium capability and qualifications, including work plan clarity, milestone definition, resource allocation, and expertise for development.</i>	3.5/5
TOTAL POINTS	15.5/20

STATUS: NOT SELECTED FOR FUNDING

Feedback and Areas for Improvement

Technology Excellence and Innovation

ECO4EDU indicates strong alignment with the Open Call #1 Challenges for Consumers' Food Choices, indicating strong understanding of the current practices, demonstrating citizen engagement, user sovereignty and establishment of a trusted environment with innovation. The technological approach seems innovative, combining GIS-based scenarios with personal and big data. Proposed Infrastructure as well as both human and end user involvement are well described and sound. Metropolitan Foodscape Planner indicates high innovation promise and the proposed project is valid for its advancement to TRL 7-8. An additional technical overview of the infrastructure could have been useful, however, outlined information is sound. Ethical consideration and open-source contributions exist. However, areas for improvement might include detailing the feasibility for market launch, clarifying the extent of end-user engagement in co-design, and elaborating on ethical and legal considerations.

Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs

The ECO4EDU proposal demonstrates a strong approach to data responsibility and transparency, highlighting a commitment to privacy and secure data management. It suggests a team with a solid understanding of cybersecurity, yet calls for more detailed strategies on dataset integrity and bias mitigation, alongside improved user data control and transparency. The proposal is commended for its thorough integration with Digital Responsibility Goals and its ambition to upgrade to a more digitally responsible platform. However, it's noted that the project's lofty ambitions might exceed the detail and feasibility of its outlined implementation strategies.

Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact

The ECO4EDU proposal effectively communicates its unique selling points and its community-oriented approach, showcasing a robust European presence through its consortium partners. It shines in its educational approach tailored to sustainability, aligning closely with user needs. Nevertheless, it could enhance its strategy by offering a more in-depth market analysis, a clearer path to commercialization, and finer details on IPR management. While it demonstrates features appealing to end users, the differentiation between users and paying customers, particularly in a B2G context, requires further clarity. Additionally, the proposal would benefit from more precise financial projections and an expanded strategy for scalability and reaching potential customers.

Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation

The ECO4EDU consortium demonstrates strengths in expertise and potential synergies among members, contributing to collaborative innovation. KPIs follow the work plan, however the project could have some of the KPIS as milestones instead. The proposal could improve in detailing a clear work plan with clearer tasks description. Comprehensive risk assessment and mitigation strategy is missing. A5 work package could have additional tasks on its commercialization.

Appraisal Scale per Criterion

Each criterion is evaluated on a scale up to 5, detailed as follows:

- 1 / POOR** *The proposal addresses the criterion in an inadequate manner or there are significant weaknesses.*
- 2 / FAIR** *The proposal addresses the criterion broadly, but there are still several weaknesses.*
- 3 / GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion well, but improvements are necessary.*
- 4 / VERY GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion very well, but some improvements are still possible.*
- 5 / EXCELLENT** *The proposal successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the criterion. Any shortcomings are minor.*

The overall threshold for the total score is 12/20.

Evaluation Summary Report

DRG4Food Open Call #1

Proposal Title: EMA Trust

Outcome of Phase 2 – Remote Evaluation

Criterion	Average Points
Technology Excellence and Innovation <i>Assessing projects on innovation, compliance with EU food policies, advancements in data-driven technology, user collaboration, ethical standards, and open-source contributions.</i>	4/5
Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs <i>Evaluating projects on cybersecurity expertise, privacy standards, dataset integrity, user data control, algorithm transparency, and enabling DRG realization.</i>	3/5
Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact <i>Assessing business viability, scalability, and impact through unique selling points, market research, competitor analysis, financial projections, and IP rights management.</i>	4/5
Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation <i>Assessing consortium capability and qualifications, including work plan clarity, milestone definition, resource allocation, and expertise for development.</i>	3/5
TOTAL POINTS	14/20

STATUS: NOT SELECTED FOR FUNDING

Feedback and Areas for Improvement

Technology Excellence and Innovation

The proposal is aligned with DRG4Food challenges. It addresses very well the specific challenges, such as trust citizen engagement, and user sovereignty. The proposed technological approach is sound, each main pillar is credibly explained. However, progress beyond the state of the art is not sufficiently provided. The objectives are clear. The objectives are pertinent with the call, as the proposal aims at providing a digital solution for food waste reduction, while staying aligned with Digital Responsibility Goals and principles. However, the novelty of the solution is not sufficiently justified.

The timeline for advancing the Technology Readiness Level (TRL) is credible and the timing for market introduction is appropriately provided. End-user engagement is well planned in testing the solution via pilots. However, the involvement of end users in co-designing is not sufficiently addressed. The ethical and legal considerations relevant to the project are only broadly addressed. Open-source contribution of the proposed solution is not sufficiently addressed in the proposal.

Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs

The expertise of the team expertise in secure software design and cybersecurity is good. Cybersecurity threats are not sufficiently identified in the proposal, consequently, the proposal does not provide sufficient strategies for their mitigation. This is an important shortcoming. The proposed approach for privacy is credible, including how personal data is handled securely and transparently. The proposed strategies for ensuring dataset integrity by the use of blockchain technology is credible.

The user control over data and establishment of transparency measures are not properly provided in the proposal. The clarity of algorithmic outputs and the assessment and mitigation of algorithmic bias is not sufficiently provided by the proposal, which is an important shortcoming. The proposal has the potential to realize mostly DRG #6.

Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact

The scalability plan is well articulated, with a clear business model and a coherent business plan aligned with the proposed solution, although some financial estimates may be overly optimistic. The specific impacts align with the solution, but some operational KPIs lack definition.

The proposal convincingly outlines Unique Selling Points (USPs), yet the market analysis and competitor comparison are superficially handled, indicating a need for deeper market insight. The proposal falls short in addressing IPR management and partner exploitation strategies, marking critical areas for improvement.

Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation

The proposal demonstrates that the most competencies for the project are in place. The work plan is logical, although it lacks specific technical details. The budget is appropriate, with resource allocation being well-balanced across the project. Procedures for risk assessment and strategies for risk mitigation are not sufficiently provided either. This is an important weakness.

Appraisal Scale per Criterion

Each criterion is evaluated on a scale up to 5, detailed as follows:

- 1 / POOR** *The proposal addresses the criterion in an inadequate manner or there are significant weaknesses.*
- 2 / FAIR** *The proposal addresses the criterion broadly, but there are still several weaknesses.*
- 3 / GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion well, but improvements are necessary.*
- 4 / VERY GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion very well, but some improvements are still possible.*
- 5 / EXCELLENT** *The proposal successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the criterion. Any shortcomings are minor.*

The overall threshold for the total score is 12/20.

Evaluation Summary Report

DRG4Food Open Call #1

Proposal Title: *FEDERATOR*

Outcome of Phase 2 – Remote Evaluation

Criterion	Average Points
Technology Excellence and Innovation <i>Assessing projects on innovation, compliance with EU food policies, advancements in data-driven technology, user collaboration, ethical standards, and open-source contributions.</i>	4/5
Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs <i>Evaluating projects on cybersecurity expertise, privacy standards, dataset integrity, user data control, algorithm transparency, and enabling DRG realization.</i>	4.5/5
Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact <i>Assessing business viability, scalability, and impact through unique selling points, market research, competitor analysis, financial projections, and IP rights management.</i>	3/5
Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation <i>Assessing consortium capability and qualifications, including work plan clarity, milestone definition, resource allocation, and expertise for development.</i>	4/5
TOTAL POINTS	15.5/20

STATUS: NOT SELECTED FOR FUNDING

Feedback and Areas for Improvement

Technology Excellence and Innovation

The proposal addresses well the DRG4Food specific challenges focusing on responsible use of technology, enhancing trust and transparency, promoting digital responsibility, and aligning with European standards of sustainability and digital rights for Food Tracking. The proposal has an ambitious technological approach, which promised to go beyond the current state of the art. A minor shortcoming is that the proposal mentions that IoT devices can track usage of fertilization, without explaining how.

The market launch of the proposed solution appears to be feasible.

The extent and effectiveness of planned engagement with end users in co-designing and testing the solution is not presented at an appropriate level of information.

The proposal has in place a plan for addressing ethical and legal considerations relevant to the project. It's not clear whether the proposed project will contribute to the DRG4Food toolbox with open source solutions. However, in a different section (Section 4), it's mentioned that "The Open Source community will also get a benefit, thanks to the release of FEDERATOR under a permissive license like Apache 2.0 or CC BY-4.0".

Improvement: Link from chatbot to platform not clear. What is the benefit?;

Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs

The level of team's expertise in cybersecurity is not clearly defined. Moreover, the identification of cybersecurity threats and the strategies for their mitigation are somewhat generic.

The proposal's approach to privacy, including how personal data is handled securely and transparently, appears to be appropriate. The strategies for ensuring dataset integrity and mitigating potential biases presented by the proposal, appear to be appropriate. A process for reviewing the clarity of algorithmic outputs and the assessment and mitigation of algorithmic bias, is in place. The proposal adequately facilitates user control over data and establishes transparency measures. The proposal has the potential to realize multiple DRGs.

Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact

The presented USPs of the proposed solution, their alignment with user needs, and the value proposition of the solution, are presented adequately. The market analysis is comprehensive, but this is not the case with the competitor analysis. The credibility of the business model is somewhat adequate but there are no financial projections.

The proposal's approach to IPR management is presented in detail and appears to be appropriate.

Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation

The clarity and feasibility of the proposed work plan is good and the same applies to the definition and feasibility of milestones and deliverables. The procedures for risk assessment and have not been described and the same applies to risks and the strategies for risk mitigation. The resource allocation appears to be somewhat appropriate. The strength of collaboration is appropriate and the individual capacities of the team members appear to be relevant, although some more detail would be appreciated. Gender balance is achieved in the consortium.

Appraisal Scale per Criterion

Each criterion is evaluated on a scale up to 5, detailed as follows:

- 1 / POOR** *The proposal addresses the criterion in an inadequate manner or there are significant weaknesses.*
- 2 / FAIR** *The proposal addresses the criterion broadly, but there are still several weaknesses.*
- 3 / GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion well, but improvements are necessary.*
- 4 / VERY GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion very well, but some improvements are still possible.*
- 5 / EXCELLENT** *The proposal successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the criterion. Any shortcomings are minor.*

The overall threshold for the total score is 12/20.

Evaluation Summary Report

DRG4Food Open Call #1

Proposal Title: FERMERS

Outcome of Phase 2 – Remote Evaluation

Criterion	Average Points
Technology Excellence and Innovation <i>Assessing projects on innovation, compliance with EU food policies, advancements in data-driven technology, user collaboration, ethical standards, and open-source contributions.</i>	3/5
Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs <i>Evaluating projects on cybersecurity expertise, privacy standards, dataset integrity, user data control, algorithm transparency, and enabling DRG realization.</i>	3.5/5
Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact <i>Assessing business viability, scalability, and impact through unique selling points, market research, competitor analysis, financial projections, and IP rights management.</i>	2.5/5
Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation <i>Assessing consortium capability and qualifications, including work plan clarity, milestone definition, resource allocation, and expertise for development.</i>	3/5
TOTAL POINTS	12/20

STATUS: NOT SELECTED FOR FUNDING

Feedback and Areas for Improvement

Technology Excellence and Innovation

The proposal is not aligned with any of the 3 DRG4Food specific challenge areas. Instead, it focused on an e-Commerce platform bringing together farmers, consumers, service providers etc, but not with the intension to support the traceability of food productions or empower consumers to make healthier and more sustainable dietary selections.

The proposal does emphasize trust, citizen engagement, and user sovereignty.

The proposal's technological approach, including the quality, relevance, and how it advances over the current state of the art, are not very convincing.

The concept is not very novel and its not relevant to the call.

More details would be needed to properly assess the market launch of the proposed solution as feasible.

The planned engagement with end users in co-designing and testing the solution is not presented at a sufficient level of detail.

It's not entirely clear how the proposal has addresses ethical and legal considerations relevant to the project.

There is no indication that the proposed project will contribute to the DRG4Food toolbox with open source solutions.

Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs

The team's expertise in cybersecurity is not presented in detail. The identification of cybersecurity threats and the strategies for their mitigation are thorough, although in some cases the measures proposed are too generic.

The proposal's approach to privacy, including how personal data is handled securely and transparently, appears to be adequate.

The strategies for ensuring dataset integrity and mitigating potential biases presented by the proposal, appear to be adequate.

A process for reviewing the clarity of algorithmic outputs and the assessment and mitigation of algorithmic bias, is in place. Nevertheless, the focus is mainly on making the algorithms understandable to scientific users and not the the majority of the solution's users.

The proposal adequately facilitates user control over data and establishes transparency measures.

There is an indication that the proposal has the potential to realize at least one DRG.

Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact

The presented USPs of the proposed solution, their alignment with user needs, and the value proposition of the solution, are not entirely convincing.

The market analysis and the competitor analysis are not sufficiently comprehensive.

The clarity and credibility of the business model is not appropriate and there are no financial projections.

The proposal's approach to IPR management is presented in a somewhat appropriate level of detail. However, it's not clear how the IPR of the common results of this project will be divided between the consortium partners.

Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation

The clarity and feasibility of the proposed work plan is not supported with the appropriate amount of details and the same applies to the definition and feasibility of milestones and deliverables.

The procedures for risk assessment and the strategies for risk mitigation have not been described.

The resource allocation doesn't appear to be appropriate, as for example the indirect costs seem to be more than 25% of personnel and other direct costs.

The strength of collaboration is appropriate. However, not enough information is present about the individual capacities of the team members. In terms of gender balance in the consortium, although it's written that 30% of the team are "women and others", only 1 from the 8 core team members that we have CVs and gender information on, is female.

Therefore, there is no gender balance.

Appraisal Scale per Criterion

Each criterion is evaluated on a scale up to 5, detailed as follows:

- 1 / POOR** *The proposal addresses the criterion in an inadequate manner or there are significant weaknesses.*
- 2 / FAIR** *The proposal addresses the criterion broadly, but there are still several weaknesses.*
- 3 / GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion well, but improvements are necessary.*
- 4 / VERY GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion very well, but some improvements are still possible.*

5 / EXCELLENT *The proposal successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the criterion. Any shortcomings are minor.*

The overall threshold for the total score is 12/20.

Evaluation Summary Report

DRG4Food Open Call #1

Proposal Title: FoodCHAIN.org

Outcome of Phase 2 – Remote Evaluation

Criterion	Average Points
Technology Excellence and Innovation <i>Assessing projects on innovation, compliance with EU food policies, advancements in data-driven technology, user collaboration, ethical standards, and open-source contributions.</i>	3/5
Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs <i>Evaluating projects on cybersecurity expertise, privacy standards, dataset integrity, user data control, algorithm transparency, and enabling DRG realization.</i>	2.5/5
Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact <i>Assessing business viability, scalability, and impact through unique selling points, market research, competitor analysis, financial projections, and IP rights management.</i>	3/5
Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation <i>Assessing consortium capability and qualifications, including work plan clarity, milestone definition, resource allocation, and expertise for development.</i>	3/5
TOTAL POINTS	11.5/20

STATUS: NOT SELECTED FOR FUNDING

Feedback and Areas for Improvement

Technology Excellence and Innovation

The proposal demonstrates a concrete understanding of the potential application of blockchain technology for food traceability in supply chains. The integration of a blockchain-based architecture to ensure transparency, security and accountability throughout the supply chain is innovative and addresses key issues in current food traceability systems. However, while the proposal outlines a comprehensive plan for the use of blockchain technology, it lacks a description of specific features that differentiate it from existing solutions.

Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs

The proposal's approach to data responsibility and alignment with DRGs is mentioned but lacks specificity and depth. While the project aims to promote digital literacy, cybersecurity, privacy, data fairness, and transparency, the description of how these goals will be achieved is generic. There's a need for a more detailed explanation of the mechanisms and practices that will be put in place to ensure data responsibility and transparency.

Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact

The proposal outlines a value model that emphasizes consumer empowerment, efficiency gains, and compliance with regulatory standards, which are all critical components of a viable business model. The scalability of the solution and its adaptability across various segments of the food supply chain are also well-considered. However, the plan for achieving business viability and scalability appears optimistic without detailed market analysis or consideration of potential barriers to adoption.

Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation

The composition of the consortium and the expertise of its members suggest a capable team with a wide range of skills relevant to the success of the project. However, the reliance on a key figure to be hired for blockchain development poses a significant risk, especially given the project's ambitious timeline. In addition, detailed CVs of team members have not been provided, making it difficult to fully assess their qualifications and the appropriateness of resource allocation.

Appraisal Scale per Criterion

Each criterion is evaluated on a scale up to 5, detailed as follows:

- 1 / POOR** *The proposal addresses the criterion in an inadequate manner or there are significant weaknesses.*
- 2 / FAIR** *The proposal addresses the criterion broadly, but there are still several weaknesses.*
- 3 / GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion well, but improvements are necessary.*
- 4 / VERY GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion very well, but some improvements are still possible.*
- 5 / EXCELLENT** *The proposal successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the criterion. Any shortcomings are minor.*

The overall threshold for the total score is 12/20.

Evaluation Summary Report

DRG4Food Open Call #1

Proposal Title: FOODCHAIN

Outcome of Phase 2 – Remote Evaluation

Criterion	Average Points
Technology Excellence and Innovation <i>Assessing projects on innovation, compliance with EU food policies, advancements in data-driven technology, user collaboration, ethical standards, and open-source contributions.</i>	4/5
Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs <i>Evaluating projects on cybersecurity expertise, privacy standards, dataset integrity, user data control, algorithm transparency, and enabling DRG realization.</i>	4.5/5
Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact <i>Assessing business viability, scalability, and impact through unique selling points, market research, competitor analysis, financial projections, and IP rights management.</i>	4/5
Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation <i>Assessing consortium capability and qualifications, including work plan clarity, milestone definition, resource allocation, and expertise for development.</i>	4.5/5
TOTAL POINTS	17/20

STATUS: NOT SELECTED FOR FUNDING

Feedback and Areas for Improvement

Technology Excellence and Innovation

- The proposal elaborates well how the proposal aligns with the specific challenges of DRG4FOOD.
- There is a detailed outline of the proposals' technological approach, not only for basic functionalities but also for elements working towards the digitally responsible design of the solution.
- Overall, the technological excellence of the proposal is more pronounced than the innovative character.
- Given advanced TRL of some components and the clear plan of implementation for the development of the proposed solution the TRL plan seems feasible.
- The proposal provides good measures for user engagement and co-design.
- Ethical, legal/policy considerations very well addressed.
- Open-source contributions are addressed, however, it remains a bit vague how and what the proposals will provide to the DRG4FOOD toolbox.

Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs

- The proposal provides answers to all relevant criteria and proposes well-founded and comprehensible arguments how DRGs will be enabled, demonstrating a high technical knowledge of implementing responsible technologies.

Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact

- USPs of the proposal are debatable, as the overall proposal's novelty is limited. However, the advanced and professional approach to an established idea can be seen as a USP in itself.

- The market and competitor analysis is well-founded and the elaboration of the business model is well done.
- IPR management and exploitation strategy is sufficiently discussed.

Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation

- The workplan is basic but feasible and cost-efficient. Description of the qualifications of the consortium partners is sufficient.
- In terms of risk management and mitigation the proposal sets the right priorities without going too much into details.

Appraisal Scale per Criterion

Each criterion is evaluated on a scale up to 5, detailed as follows:

- 1 / POOR** *The proposal addresses the criterion in an inadequate manner or there are significant weaknesses.*
- 2 / FAIR** *The proposal addresses the criterion broadly, but there are still several weaknesses.*
- 3 / GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion well, but improvements are necessary.*
- 4 / VERY GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion very well, but some improvements are still possible.*
- 5 / EXCELLENT** *The proposal successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the criterion. Any shortcomings are minor.*

The overall threshold for the total score is 12/20.

Evaluation Summary Report

DRG4Food Open Call #1

Proposal Title: FoodTrust

Outcome of Phase 2 – Remote Evaluation

Criterion	Average Points
Technology Excellence and Innovation <i>Assessing projects on innovation, compliance with EU food policies, advancements in data-driven technology, user collaboration, ethical standards, and open-source contributions.</i>	4/5
Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs <i>Evaluating projects on cybersecurity expertise, privacy standards, dataset integrity, user data control, algorithm transparency, and enabling DRG realization.</i>	5/5
Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact <i>Assessing business viability, scalability, and impact through unique selling points, market research, competitor analysis, financial projections, and IP rights management.</i>	3.5/5
Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation <i>Assessing consortium capability and qualifications, including work plan clarity, milestone definition, resource allocation, and expertise for development.</i>	4.5/5
TOTAL POINTS	17/20

STATUS: NOT SELECTED FOR FUNDING

Feedback and Areas for Improvement

Technology Excellence and Innovation

The proposal elaborates well how the proposal aligns with the specific challenges of DRG4FOOD. There is a basic outline of the proposals' technological approach, however, the overall innovative character of the proposal is very high. Unfortunately, some parts mentioned in the introduction, such as "immersive virtual experiences" for users are not mentioned anymore at a later stage. Given the prior planning and already existing resources the TRL advancement seems feasible. The proposal provides extensive measures for user engagement and co-design. Ethical considerations and open sourcing are sufficiently addressed.

Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs

The proposal provides answers to all relevant criteria and proposes well-founded and comprehensible arguments how DRGs will be enabled, demonstrating clear focus on user-centricity.

Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact

While some USPs are debatable, the overall proposal demonstrates novelty in approach and intended outcome. The market and competitor analysis is rather basic and elaboration of the business model remained a bit vague. IPR management and exploitation strategy is sufficiently discussed.

Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation

The workplan is clear and feasible given time and resources available. The proposal very transparently sets out a comprehensible roadmap and timeline for deliverables with

sufficient human resources for the proposed solution. Description of the qualifications of the consortium partners, however, is shallow. In terms of risk management and mitigation only very basic considerations are mentioned.

Appraisal Scale per Criterion

Each criterion is evaluated on a scale up to 5, detailed as follows:

- 1 / POOR** *The proposal addresses the criterion in an inadequate manner or there are significant weaknesses.*
- 2 / FAIR** *The proposal addresses the criterion broadly, but there are still several weaknesses.*
- 3 / GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion well, but improvements are necessary.*
- 4 / VERY GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion very well, but some improvements are still possible.*
- 5 / EXCELLENT** *The proposal successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the criterion. Any shortcomings are minor.*

The overall threshold for the total score is 12/20.

Evaluation Summary Report

DRG4Food Open Call #1

Proposal Title: FoodVault

Outcome of Phase 2 – Remote Evaluation

Criterion	Average Points
Technology Excellence and Innovation <i>Assessing projects on innovation, compliance with EU food policies, advancements in data-driven technology, user collaboration, ethical standards, and open-source contributions.</i>	2.5/5
Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs <i>Evaluating projects on cybersecurity expertise, privacy standards, dataset integrity, user data control, algorithm transparency, and enabling DRG realization.</i>	3.5/5
Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact <i>Assessing business viability, scalability, and impact through unique selling points, market research, competitor analysis, financial projections, and IP rights management.</i>	2.5/5
Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation <i>Assessing consortium capability and qualifications, including work plan clarity, milestone definition, resource allocation, and expertise for development.</i>	2.5/5
TOTAL POINTS	11/20

STATUS: NOT SELECTED FOR FUNDING

Feedback and Areas for Improvement

Technology Excellence and Innovation

The proposal appears to be related to the DRG4Food specific challenge area “Food Tracking”, while having strong emphasis on trust, citizen engagement, and user sovereignty. However, the degree that this proposal is actually linked to this specific challenge area is not clear. Although it’s a technological solution that supports traceability systems for the agrifood sector, on its own it doesn’t take into account “both environmental aspects such as CO2 emissions, waste generation, and water and land use, as well as societal considerations, including fair income for farmers” as mention by the guidelines of the DRG4FOOD Open Call. The proposal has an ambitious technological approach, which promises to go beyond the current state of the art. The market launch of the proposed solution appears to be feasible, mainly since CTIC has a traceability solution that can make use of it. There is no sufficient information about the planned engagement with end users in co- designing and testing the solution. The same applies to the plan for addressing ethical and legal considerations relevant to the project. The proposed project is willing to contribute to the DRG4Food toolbox with open source solutions.

Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs

The team’s expertise in cybersecurity appears to be strong and the same applies to the identification of cybersecurity threats and the strategies for their mitigation. The proposal's approach to privacy, including how personal data is handled securely and transparently, appears to be appropriate.

According to the proposal, the solution is not dealing with strategies for ensuring dataset integrity and mitigating potential biases, as they are currently not relevant to its offering. The same applies to the clarity of algorithmic outputs and the assessment and mitigation of algorithmic bias. The proposal adequately facilitates user control over data and establishes transparency measures.

Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact

The project demonstrates potential for considerable impact within the agri-food sector through its clear value proposition for secure and transparent digital transactions. The open-source nature and modular design of the technology are clear strengths. However, the proposal's market analysis and adoption strategy appear underdeveloped, lacking in-depth competitor analysis and detailed financial projections. A more thorough exploration of market dynamics and consumer adoption strategies would provide a clearer path to business success. The proposal's approach to IPR management is not presented in an appropriate level of detail.

Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation

The clarity of the proposed work plan is adequate, although more information would be appreciated. The procedures for risk assessment and have not been described and there no indication of risks and respective mitigation strategies. The resource allocation appears to be aligned with the described project and the different shortcomings presented below. The strength of collaboration is appropriate and the individual capacities of the team members appear to be relevant, although more detail would be needed. There is a lack of team members with business expertise. The consortium doesn't have an appropriate gender balance, as only 2 of the 9 team members are female.

Appraisal Scale per Criterion

- 1 / POOR** *The proposal addresses the criterion in an inadequate manner or there are significant weaknesses.*
- 2 / FAIR** *The proposal addresses the criterion broadly, but there are still several weaknesses.*
- 3 / GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion well, but improvements are necessary.*
- 4 / VERY GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion very well, but some improvements are still possible.*
- 5 / EXCELLENT** *The proposal successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the criterion. Any shortcomings are minor.*

The overall threshold for the total score is 12/20.

Evaluation Summary Report

DRG4Food Open Call #1

Proposal Title: Gastro Quest

Outcome of Phase 2 – Remote Evaluation

Criterion	Average Points
Technology Excellence and Innovation <i>Assessing projects on innovation, compliance with EU food policies, advancements in data-driven technology, user collaboration, ethical standards, and open-source contributions.</i>	3.5/5
Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs <i>Evaluating projects on cybersecurity expertise, privacy standards, dataset integrity, user data control, algorithm transparency, and enabling DRG realization.</i>	4.5/5
Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact <i>Assessing business viability, scalability, and impact through unique selling points, market research, competitor analysis, financial projections, and IP rights management.</i>	3.5/5
Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation <i>Assessing consortium capability and qualifications, including work plan clarity, milestone definition, resource allocation, and expertise for development.</i>	3.5/5
TOTAL POINTS	15/20

STATUS: NOT SELECTED FOR FUNDING

Feedback and Areas for Improvement

Technology Excellence and Innovation

The Gastro Quest proposal presents an innovative and comprehensive approach by integrating gamification, storytelling and AI to promote sustainable eating habits. The use of a generative AI language model to personalize the user experience is a significant technological innovation. Despite this, even if the project demonstrates a good level of technology, it could further explore cutting-edge technologies and clearly define the gamification mechanisms intended to be used. The proposed advancement of the Technology Readiness Level (TRL) is credible. However, timing for market introduction is not sufficiently provided. The ethical and legal considerations relevant to the project are not sufficiently addressed. This is a shortcoming.

Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs

The expertise of the team expertise in secure software design and cybersecurity is appropriate. Cybersecurity threats are credibly identified in the proposal, and appropriate mitigation strategy is proposed.

The effective approach for handling privacy is credibly proposed.

The proposed strategies for ensuring dataset integrity are overall credible. However, the mitigation of potential biases is not fully addressed.

User control over data and establishment of transparency measures are appropriate.

However, mitigation of algorithmic bias is not sufficiently addressed.

The potential of the proposal to realize DRG criteria are only superficially elaborated.

Nevertheless, the proposed project has the potential to realize some DRG criteria.

Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact

Gastro Quest shows a clear value proposition through a combination of gamification, storytelling, and AI-driven personalization to provide digital culinary education services. The business model, focusing on a mix of freemium and premium features along with potential partnerships, suggests a viable path to scalability and sustainability. The project's focus on a specific target audience with room for expansion adds to its market potential. However, a more detailed analysis of competitive differentiation and market entry strategy could further strengthen its business viability.

Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation

The consortium showcases a comprehensive skill set essential for the project's success, including gamification, education, cybersecurity, and sustainable food practices. The collaboration presents a structured work plan and resource management, emphasizing the necessity of efficient communication and teamwork among its diverse members to achieve its objectives. Despite the robust foundation and execution strategy, a discrepancy in the project's budgeting and resource allocation against the expected workload (PMs) raises concerns about cost efficiency and resource use. A more detailed task and cost breakdown is recommended to align the budget with the workload, ensuring resource optimization and project efficacy.

Appraisal Scale per Criterion

Each criterion is evaluated on a scale up to 5, detailed as follows:

- 1 / POOR** *The proposal addresses the criterion in an inadequate manner or there are significant weaknesses.*
- 2 / FAIR** *The proposal addresses the criterion broadly, but there are still several weaknesses.*
- 3 / GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion well, but improvements are necessary.*
- 4 / VERY GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion very well, but some improvements are still possible.*
- 5 / EXCELLENT** *The proposal successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the criterion. Any shortcomings are minor.*

The overall threshold for the total score is 12/20.

Evaluation Summary Report

DRG4Food Open Call #1

Proposal Title: GW - Grow Wild

Outcome of Phase 2 – Remote Evaluation

Criterion	Average Points
Technology Excellence and Innovation <i>Assessing projects on innovation, compliance with EU food policies, advancements in data-driven technology, user collaboration, ethical standards, and open-source contributions.</i>	3/5
Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs <i>Evaluating projects on cybersecurity expertise, privacy standards, dataset integrity, user data control, algorithm transparency, and enabling DRG realization.</i>	2.5/5
Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact <i>Assessing business viability, scalability, and impact through unique selling points, market research, competitor analysis, financial projections, and IP rights management.</i>	2.5/5
Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation <i>Assessing consortium capability and qualifications, including work plan clarity, milestone definition, resource allocation, and expertise for development.</i>	3/5
TOTAL POINTS	11/20

STATUS: NOT SELECTED FOR FUNDING

Feedback and Areas for Improvement

Technology Excellence and Innovation

The proposed solution is innovative and aligns with the call's objectives, though it lacks comprehensive details on achieving specific impacts and results. Significant technical information is missing, and the proposal does not thoroughly explain the added value of the solution. Strengths include a novel approach that connects food quality with biodiversity, the integration of databases with visualization tools, and a focus on standardized protocols. Areas for improvement include unclear contributions to the open-source community and to technological advancement.

Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs

Only a broad overview is presented without establishing a clear, quantified relationship between the project outcomes and the DRGs. Strengths include a user-centric approach and the ambition to adhere to the FAIR principle. However, the application and justification of the DRGs are lacking, with details on their integration and realization remaining vague.

Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact

The proposal includes limited details on scalability, specific impacts, and business development. It lacks a concrete business plan for post-project sustainability and a clear market entry strategy, missing critical information. Strengths are its well-described distinguishing features. However, improvements are needed in clearly identifying the business value and unique selling points (USPs), clarifying the target market, and defining commercialization and development (C&D) activities.

Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation

Although the project partners possess the necessary competencies to execute the proposed actions, critical elements are either missing or only adequately addressed. The description of how partner cooperation will be managed and how results will be delivered is incomplete. Strengths include a diverse consortium with a strong track record in the food sector. However, the proposal needs to clarify its engagement with digital technologies.

Appraisal Scale per Criterion

Each criterion is evaluated on a scale up to 5, detailed as follows:

- 1 / POOR** *The proposal addresses the criterion in an inadequate manner or there are significant weaknesses.*
- 2 / FAIR** *The proposal addresses the criterion broadly, but there are still several weaknesses.*
- 3 / GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion well, but improvements are necessary.*
- 4 / VERY GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion very well, but some improvements are still possible.*
- 5 / EXCELLENT** *The proposal successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the criterion. Any shortcomings are minor.*

The overall threshold for the total score is 12/20.

Evaluation Summary Report

DRG4Food Open Call #1

Proposal Title: IMT_BL

Outcome of Phase 2 – Remote Evaluation

Criterion	Average Points
Technology Excellence and Innovation <i>Assessing projects on innovation, compliance with EU food policies, advancements in data-driven technology, user collaboration, ethical standards, and open-source contributions.</i>	3/5
Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs <i>Evaluating projects on cybersecurity expertise, privacy standards, dataset integrity, user data control, algorithm transparency, and enabling DRG realization.</i>	3.5/5
Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact <i>Assessing business viability, scalability, and impact through unique selling points, market research, competitor analysis, financial projections, and IP rights management.</i>	3/5
Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation <i>Assessing consortium capability and qualifications, including work plan clarity, milestone definition, resource allocation, and expertise for development.</i>	3.5/5
TOTAL POINTS	13/20

STATUS: NOT SELECTED FOR FUNDING

Feedback and Areas for Improvement

Technology Excellence and Innovation

The proposal addresses well the DRG4Food specific challenge area “Food Tracking” but also the area “Consumer’ Food Choices”. In addressing these areas, there is strong emphasis on trust, citizen engagement, and user sovereignty (from the side of the food producer). The proposal has an ambitious technological approach, which promised to go beyond the current state of the art. However, it’s not entirely clear on how this will be accomplished. The concept has a good level of novelty and its relevant to the call. Due to the complexity of the solution to be developed, it’s not easy to assess the actual feasibility for market launch. Part of the description is convincing but other parts seem to suggest there is some uncertainty. The extent and effectiveness of planned engagement with end users in co-designing and testing the solution appears to be appropriate. Numbers are missing but the approach is presented. The proposal has in place a plan for addressing ethical and legal considerations relevant to the project. Gender and inclusivity are properly addressed, although the first part of the relevant description was more focused on the consortium team member than to the actual stakeholders of the solution. There is no indication that the proposed project will contribute to the DRG4Food toolbox with open source solutions.

Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs

The team’s expertise in cybersecurity is good, and the identification of cybersecurity threats and the strategies for their mitigation appear to be appropriate. The proposal’s approach for privacy appears to be appropriate. The same applies to the strategies for ensuring dataset integrity and mitigating potential biases. There is no process for reviewing the clarity of algorithmic outputs and the assessment and mitigation of algorithmic bias, as, accordin to

the applicant, in this “project there will not be any algorithm used so there is no risk for any biases, the only mechanism will be AI”. The proposal adequately facilitates user control over data and establishes transparency measures. The proposal has the potential to realize multiple DRG criteria.

Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact

The presented USPs of the proposed solution, their alignment with user needs, and the value proposition of the solution, appear to be adequate. Both the market analysis and the competitor analysis are sufficient. Some more details on the business model and how the numbers of customers used in the financial projections were calculated, would be appreciated. It’s not clear how these numbers will be achieved. This is a shortcoming. The proposal’s approach to IPR management and the strategy for exploiting the results appears to be appropriate. The impact on local food producers is positive, but quantifying the expected impact could enhance the proposal.

Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation

The clarity and feasibility of the proposed work plan is good and the same applies to the definition and feasibility deliverables. Specific risks are identified and the strategies for risk mitigation are described. The resource allocation appears to be appropriate. The strength of collaboration is appropriate and there is sufficient explanation of the individual capacities of the team members. However, there is a lack of people with business background.

Appraisal Scale per Criterion

Each criterion is evaluated on a scale up to 5, detailed as follows:

- 1 / POOR** *The proposal addresses the criterion in an inadequate manner or there are significant weaknesses.*
- 2 / FAIR** *The proposal addresses the criterion broadly, but there are still several weaknesses.*
- 3 / GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion well, but improvements are necessary.*
- 4 / VERY GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion very well, but some improvements are still possible.*
- 5 / EXCELLENT** *The proposal successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the criterion. Any shortcomings are minor.*

The overall threshold for the total score is 12/20.

Evaluation Summary Report

DRG4Food Open Call #1

Proposal Title: ISOChain

Outcome of Phase 2 – Remote Evaluation

Criterion	Average Points
Technology Excellence and Innovation <i>Assessing projects on innovation, compliance with EU food policies, advancements in data-driven technology, user collaboration, ethical standards, and open-source contributions.</i>	4.5/5
Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs <i>Evaluating projects on cybersecurity expertise, privacy standards, dataset integrity, user data control, algorithm transparency, and enabling DRG realization.</i>	5/5
Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact <i>Assessing business viability, scalability, and impact through unique selling points, market research, competitor analysis, financial projections, and IP rights management.</i>	3.5/5
Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation <i>Assessing consortium capability and qualifications, including work plan clarity, milestone definition, resource allocation, and expertise for development.</i>	4.5/5
TOTAL POINTS	17.5/5

STATUS: NOT SELECTED FOR FUNDING

Feedback and Areas for Improvement

Technology Excellence and Innovation

The proposal is fully aligned with DRG4Food challenges, for example increase trust and citizen engagement.

The proposed technological approach is very sound. Very credible approach is provided for the proposed modules: (i) Food Product passport mobile application; (ii) secure hologram tamper-resistant labels; (iii) Food Environment impact module; (iv) Food social impact assessment module. However, the progress beyond the state of the art is not sufficiently provided. This is a minor shortcoming.

The objectives are very clear and excellently defined with KPIs. The objectives are very pertinent to the call and aligned with all Digital Responsibility Goals. This is a strength of the proposal.

The proposed advancement of the Technology Readiness Level (TRL) is realistically achievable and very well justified. Timing for market introduction is appropriately provided.

The engagement of end-users (producers, retail, and consumers) and their involvement in co-designing is very credibly proposed.

Ethical and legal considerations relevant to the project are appropriately addressed.

Open source contributions and the willingness to contribute to the DRG4Food toolbox is convincingly provided.

Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs

The level of team's expertise in cybersecurity is strong and the identification of cybersecurity threats and the strategies for their mitigation is very thorough.

The proposal's approach to privacy, including how personal data is handled securely and transparently, appears to be appropriate.

The strategies for ensuring dataset integrity and mitigating potential biases presented by the proposal, appear to be appropriate.

A process for reviewing the clarity of algorithmic outputs and the assessment and mitigation of algorithmic bias, is in place.

The proposal adequately facilitates user control over data and establishes transparency measures. The proposal has the potential to realize multiple DRGs.

Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact

The presented USPs of the proposed solution, their alignment with user needs, and the value proposition of the solution, are presented adequately. The market analysis and the competitor analysis do not have an appropriate level of detail. The credibility of the business model is somewhat adequate but there are no financial projections.

The proposal's approach to IPR management is not entirely clear.

Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation

The clarity and feasibility of the proposed work plan is good and the same applies to the definition and feasibility of milestones and deliverables. Although the procedures for risk assessment have not been described, there is a comprehensive list of risks and strategies for risk mitigation. The resource allocation appears to be appropriate. The strength of collaboration is appropriate, and the individual capacities of the team members appear to be relevant, although there appears to be a lack of business expertise, something that is also apparent in the previous section. Gender balance is achieved in the consortium.

Appraisal Scale per Criterion

Each criterion is evaluated on a scale up to 5, detailed as follows:

- 1 / POOR** *The proposal addresses the criterion in an inadequate manner or there are significant weaknesses.*
- 2 / FAIR** *The proposal addresses the criterion broadly, but there are still several weaknesses.*
- 3 / GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion well, but improvements are necessary.*
- 4 / VERY GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion very well, but some improvements are still possible.*
- 5 / EXCELLENT** *The proposal successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the criterion. Any shortcomings are minor.*

The overall threshold for the total score is 12/20.

Evaluation Summary Report

DRG4Food Open Call #1

Proposal Title: MATTO

Outcome of Phase 2 – Remote Evaluation

Criterion	Average Points
Technology Excellence and Innovation <i>Assessing projects on innovation, compliance with EU food policies, advancements in data-driven technology, user collaboration, ethical standards, and open-source contributions.</i>	3.5/20
Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs <i>Evaluating projects on cybersecurity expertise, privacy standards, dataset integrity, user data control, algorithm transparency, and enabling DRG realization.</i>	3.5/20
Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact <i>Assessing business viability, scalability, and impact through unique selling points, market research, competitor analysis, financial projections, and IP rights management.</i>	2.5/20
Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation <i>Assessing consortium capability and qualifications, including work plan clarity, milestone definition, resource allocation, and expertise for development.</i>	3.5/20
TOTAL POINTS	13/20

STATUS: NOT SELECTED FOR FUNDING

Feedback and Areas for Improvement

Technology Excellence and Innovation

The MATTO project proposal effectively showcases technological innovation by integrating blockchain technology into the tomato supply chain, offering enhanced transparency, traceability, and data integrity. This multidisciplinary collaboration between a blockchain software house, a tomato production company, and an academic institution presents a comprehensive solution to current challenges. However, advancing from a Technology Readiness Level (TRL) of 3 to 7 within the project's timeline is notably ambitious. The proposal's lack of comparison with existing market solutions limits understanding of its innovative edge. Additionally, it does not thoroughly address technological scalability or system interoperability challenges. A more detailed technical roadmap, potentially including pilot studies with current supply chains, could significantly strengthen the proposal by clarifying strategies to surmount these hurdles, ensuring the project's practical applicability and integration capability.

Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs

The MATTO project demonstrates a strong commitment to Digital Responsibility Goals (DRGs) through its focus on cybersecurity, privacy, transparency, and digital literacy, leveraging blockchain's secure design, data anonymization, and immutability. However, the proposal would benefit significantly from an expanded strategy addressing the evolving nature of privacy laws and cybersecurity threats to maintain DRG alignment over time.

Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact

The proposal convincingly outlines the business model, targeting small to medium-sized producers with a SaaS model that promises ease of use and affordability. The unique selling

points and competitive analysis are not analysed in detail . Scalability is addressed through the adaptable SaaS framework, which could potentially extend beyond the tomato supply chain. Nonetheless, the financial projections and assumptions remain vague, and the scalability beyond the initial target market could be further elaborated.

Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation

The consortium presents a wide range of expertise, including technical skills, market knowledge and academic research. The structure of the consortium and the allocation of responsibilities demonstrate a sound management framework and execution strategy. The team's credentials, particularly in blockchain technology and the agri-food sector, highlight their ability to achieve the project's objectives. However, the allocation of person-months is not balanced, and suggests a significant reliance on certain members. In addition, the lack of target values for KPIs prevents evaluation of the project during implementation. The inclusion of values associated with KPIs would significantly strengthen the proposal by providing measurable indicators of success.

Appraisal Scale per Criterion

Each criterion is evaluated on a scale up to 5, detailed as follows:

- 1 / POOR** *The proposal addresses the criterion in an inadequate manner or there are significant weaknesses.*
- 2 / FAIR** *The proposal addresses the criterion broadly, but there are still several weaknesses.*
- 3 / GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion well, but improvements are necessary.*
- 4 / VERY GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion very well, but some improvements are still possible.*
- 5 / EXCELLENT** *The proposal successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the criterion. Any shortcomings are minor.*

The overall threshold for the total score is 12/20.

Evaluation Summary Report

DRG4Food Open Call #1

Proposal Title: MEDiTAiNaaS

Outcome of Phase 2 – Remote Evaluation

Criterion	Average Points
Technology Excellence and Innovation <i>Assessing projects on innovation, compliance with EU food policies, advancements in data-driven technology, user collaboration, ethical standards, and open-source contributions.</i>	4/4
Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs <i>Evaluating projects on cybersecurity expertise, privacy standards, dataset integrity, user data control, algorithm transparency, and enabling DRG realization.</i>	4/4
Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact <i>Assessing business viability, scalability, and impact through unique selling points, market research, competitor analysis, financial projections, and IP rights management.</i>	3.5/4
Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation <i>Assessing consortium capability and qualifications, including work plan clarity, milestone definition, resource allocation, and expertise for development.</i>	4.5/4
TOTAL POINTS	16/20

STATUS: NOT SELECTED FOR FUNDING

Feedback and Areas for Improvement

Technology Excellence and Innovation

The proposal elaborates well how the proposal aligns with the specific challenges of DRG4FOOD. There is a detailed and comprehensible outline of the proposals' technological approach, proposing an innovative take on user-centric digital dieting coaching. The proposal provides basic measures for user engagement, however, ethical and legal considerations – that might be especially relevant given that health data will be used - are underdeveloped. Open sourcing is not sufficiently addressed.

Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs

The proposal provides answers to all relevant criteria and proposes well-founded and comprehensible arguments how DRGs will be enabled. Small omissions on transparency measures.

Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact

USPs and market fitness of the proposal are backed up by comprehensive research and analysis. The proposal sets out a basic business model and will elaborate a more detailed business plan as a deliverable of the project. IPR management is briefly mentioned.

Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation

The workplan is clear and feasible given time and resources available. The proposal very transparently sets out a comprehensible roadmap and timeline for deliverables with ample human resources for the proposed solution. The consortium partners are expertly qualified and their fields of expertise provide for useful synergies. In terms of risk management only delays were mentioned.

Appraisal Scale per Criterion

Each criterion is evaluated on a scale up to 5, detailed as follows:

- 1 / POOR** *The proposal addresses the criterion in an inadequate manner or there are significant weaknesses.*
- 2 / FAIR** *The proposal addresses the criterion broadly, but there are still several weaknesses.*
- 3 / GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion well, but improvements are necessary.*
- 4 / VERY GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion very well, but some improvements are still possible.*
- 5 / EXCELLENT** *The proposal successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the criterion. Any shortcomings are minor.*

The overall threshold for the total score is 12/20.

Evaluation Summary Report

DRG4Food Open Call #1

Proposal Title: MyHealthyApp

Outcome of Phase 2 – Remote Evaluation

Criterion	Average Points
Technology Excellence and Innovation <i>Assessing projects on innovation, compliance with EU food policies, advancements in data-driven technology, user collaboration, ethical standards, and open-source contributions.</i>	2.5/5
Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs <i>Evaluating projects on cybersecurity expertise, privacy standards, dataset integrity, user data control, algorithm transparency, and enabling DRG realization.</i>	3/5
Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact <i>Assessing business viability, scalability, and impact through unique selling points, market research, competitor analysis, financial projections, and IP rights management.</i>	2.5/5
Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation <i>Assessing consortium capability and qualifications, including work plan clarity, milestone definition, resource allocation, and expertise for development.</i>	3.5/5
TOTAL POINTS	11.5/20

STATUS: NOT SELECTED FOR FUNDING

Feedback and Areas for Improvement

Technology Excellence and Innovation

The proposal showcases an innovative solution that aligns with the call's objectives. However, it does not sufficiently detail the added value of this solution over those already available in the market. While the main developments are thoroughly outlined, the proposal falls short of clearly distinguishing its innovations from similar existing solutions. Additionally, in some instances, particularly concerning data, certain technical developments are not fully described. On the strengths, the proposal is well-suited to the 'targeted nutrition' use case and presents a solid commercial business model. As for areas needing improvement, the contributions to the open-source community and technological advancement remain unclear.

Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs

The proposal effectively outlines alignment with the DRGs, yet it lacks specific KPIs for monitoring these achievements, and the methods for monitoring these aspects during project implementation are not clearly described. In terms of transparency, while all principal information is provided, the management of data, given the project's nature, requires more detailed explanation. Strengths include a strong focus on user-centric applications and an emphasis on cybersecurity and privacy. Areas for improvement include the incomplete application and justification of DRGs, with details on their application and realization remaining ambiguous.

Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact

Although the proposed solution meets specific market needs, its scalability plan is only vaguely defined. The proposal offers only general information regarding potential business

models, and the preliminary business plan lacks a forward-looking perspective beyond the project's conclusion. While the impacts of the project are clearly articulated, it fails to specify KPIs for monitoring these impacts during implementation. Strengths include well-described unique selling points (USPs). Areas for improvement are the unclearly articulated market and business value, ambiguous market analysis, and undefined commercialization and development (C&D) activities.

Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation

The team possesses all necessary competencies to execute the proposed actions. The work plan is adequately defined and aligns with the project's main objectives, though some critical information is only minimally detailed. Partnership cooperation is well articulated. The budget aligns with the project's primary implementation needs, although the person-month (PM) allocation for some activities appears overestimated. Strengths include a diverse consortium with a strong track record in digital technologies and analysis. An area for improvement is the insufficient detail on the consortium's experience with food-related aspects.

Appraisal Scale per Criterion

Each criterion is evaluated on a scale up to 5, detailed as follows:

- 1 / POOR** *The proposal addresses the criterion in an inadequate manner or there are significant weaknesses.*
- 2 / FAIR** *The proposal addresses the criterion broadly, but there are still several weaknesses.*
- 3 / GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion well, but improvements are necessary.*
- 4 / VERY GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion very well, but some improvements are still possible.*
- 5 / EXCELLENT** *The proposal successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the criterion. Any shortcomings are minor.*

The overall threshold for the total score is 12/20.

Evaluation Summary Report

DRG4Food Open Call #1

Proposal Title: NECTAR

Outcome of Phase 2 – Remote Evaluation

Criterion	Average Points
Technology Excellence and Innovation <i>Assessing projects on innovation, compliance with EU food policies, advancements in data-driven technology, user collaboration, ethical standards, and open-source contributions.</i>	2.5/5
Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs <i>Evaluating projects on cybersecurity expertise, privacy standards, dataset integrity, user data control, algorithm transparency, and enabling DRG realization.</i>	2.5/5
Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact <i>Assessing business viability, scalability, and impact through unique selling points, market research, competitor analysis, financial projections, and IP rights management.</i>	2/5
Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation <i>Assessing consortium capability and qualifications, including work plan clarity, milestone definition, resource allocation, and expertise for development.</i>	1.5/5
TOTAL POINTS	8.5/20

STATUS: NOT SELECTED FOR FUNDING

Feedback and Areas for Improvement

Technology Excellence and Innovation

The proposal is aiming to address all 3 DRG4Food specific challenge areas, focusing on trust, citizen engagement, and user sovereignty. The proposal's technological approach, including the quality, relevance, and how it advances over the current state of the art, are not convincing. The novelty of the concept is not easy to be verified, as the description of the solution lacks sufficient clarity. The market launch of the proposed solution appears not to be feasible. The planned engagement with end users in co-designing and testing the solution is not presented at a sufficient level of detail. The proposal addresses ethical and legal considerations relevant to the project, somewhat adequately. There is no indication that the proposed project will contribute to the DRG4Food toolbox with open source solutions.

Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs

The team's expertise in cybersecurity is not presented in detail. The description of the identification of cybersecurity threats and the strategies for their mitigation are too generic. The proposal's approach to privacy, including how personal data is handled securely and transparently, appears to be adequate. The strategies for ensuring dataset integrity and mitigating potential biases presented by the proposal, are not adequately described. A process for reviewing the clarity of algorithmic outputs and the assessment and mitigation of algorithmic bias, is missing. It's not clear whether the proposal adequately facilitates user control over data and establishes transparency measures. There is an indication that the proposal has the potential to realize at least one DRG.

Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact

The presented USPs of the proposed solution, their alignment with user needs, and the value proposition of the solution, are not entirely convincing. The market analysis and the competitor analysis are not sufficiently comprehensive. The clarity and credibility of the business model is not appropriate and there are no financial projections. The proposal's approach to IPR management is presented in a somewhat appropriate level of detail. However, it's not clear how the IPR of the common results of this project will be divided between the consortium partners.

Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation

The clarity and feasibility of the proposed work plan is not supported with the appropriate amount of details and the same applies to the definition and feasibility of milestones and deliverables. The procedures for risk assessment and the strategies for risk mitigation have not been described.

Text in tables 1-5 is not readable as it is in Italian. Therefore, the key information related to the workplan and KPIs cannot be assessed.

Appraisal Scale per Criterion

Each criterion is evaluated on a scale up to 5, detailed as follows:

- 1 / POOR** *The proposal addresses the criterion in an inadequate manner or there are significant weaknesses.*
- 2 / FAIR** *The proposal addresses the criterion broadly, but there are still several weaknesses.*
- 3 / GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion well, but improvements are necessary.*
- 4 / VERY GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion very well, but some improvements are still possible.*
- 5 / EXCELLENT** *The proposal successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the criterion. Any shortcomings are minor.*

The overall threshold for the total score is 12/20.

Evaluation Summary Report

DRG4Food Open Call #1

Proposal Title: NeuroData.VR

Outcome of Phase 2 – Remote Evaluation

Criterion	Average Points
Technology Excellence and Innovation <i>Assessing projects on innovation, compliance with EU food policies, advancements in data-driven technology, user collaboration, ethical standards, and open-source contributions.</i>	3/5
Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs <i>Evaluating projects on cybersecurity expertise, privacy standards, dataset integrity, user data control, algorithm transparency, and enabling DRG realization.</i>	3.5/5
Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact <i>Assessing business viability, scalability, and impact through unique selling points, market research, competitor analysis, financial projections, and IP rights management.</i>	4.5/5
Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation <i>Assessing consortium capability and qualifications, including work plan clarity, milestone definition, resource allocation, and expertise for development.</i>	5/5
TOTAL POINTS	16/20

STATUS: NOT SELECTED FOR FUNDING

Feedback and Areas for Improvement

Technology Excellence and Innovation

While the concept is described with reasonably clarity, crucially it partially fails to connect with DRG4FOODs challenges and mission. This is because the proposal is mainly geared towards serving the (neuro)marketing industry without clear benefits to consumers beyond an unspecified mechanism to make their “voice” heard via the platform component of the proposal. While the innovative character is pronounced the topic fails to match the intention of DRG4FOOD. Given advanced TRL of some components and the clear plan of implementation for the development of the proposed solution the TRL plan seems feasible. The proposal provides limited measures for user engagement or co-design. Open-source contributions are addressed; however, it remains vague how and what the proposal will provide to the DRG4FOOD toolbox.

Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs

The proposal provides well-grounded answers to relevant criteria and describes some basic measures on how digital responsibility will be implemented. However, as the proposal has little relevance or touchpoints for active participation of the consumer answers to relevant digital responsibility criteria partially miss the target.

In general, the proposed solution as a whole has little relevance for enabling the DRGs.

Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact

The consortium demonstrates experience in the market that the proposal caters to and provides credible elaborations on viability and business model as well as financial projections, providing a detailed analysis of USPs.

IPR management and exploitation are sufficiently addressed.

Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation

The workplan is clear and feasible. The proposal sets out a comprehensible roadmap and timeline for deliverables. The consortium partners are qualified, and their fields of expertise provide for useful synergies.

In terms of risk management, a comprehensible discussion is provided.

Appraisal Scale per Criterion

Each criterion is evaluated on a scale up to 5, detailed as follows:

- 1 / POOR** *The proposal addresses the criterion in an inadequate manner or there are significant weaknesses.*
- 2 / FAIR** *The proposal addresses the criterion broadly, but there are still several weaknesses.*
- 3 / GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion well, but improvements are necessary.*
- 4 / VERY GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion very well, but some improvements are still possible.*
- 5 / EXCELLENT** *The proposal successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the criterion. Any shortcomings are minor.*

The overall threshold for the total score is 12/20.

Evaluation Summary Report

DRG4Food Open Call #1

Proposal Title: NutriCare

Outcome of Phase 2 – Remote Evaluation

Criterion	Average Points
Technology Excellence and Innovation <i>Assessing projects on innovation, compliance with EU food policies, advancements in data-driven technology, user collaboration, ethical standards, and open-source contributions.</i>	4
Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs <i>Evaluating projects on cybersecurity expertise, privacy standards, dataset integrity, user data control, algorithm transparency, and enabling DRG realization.</i>	3.5/5
Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact <i>Assessing business viability, scalability, and impact through unique selling points, market research, competitor analysis, financial projections, and IP rights management.</i>	3.51/5
Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation <i>Assessing consortium capability and qualifications, including work plan clarity, milestone definition, resource allocation, and expertise for development.</i>	3/5
TOTAL POINTS	14/20

STATUS: NOT SELECTED FOR FUNDING

Feedback and Areas for Improvement

Technology Excellence and Innovation

The proposal addresses well the DRG4Food specific challenge area “Targeted Nutrition”, while having strong emphasis on citizen engagement. Nevertheless, the focus on trust and user sovereignty over their data, could benefit from additional details. The proposal has an ambitious technological approach, which promised to go beyond the current state of the art. The market launch of the proposed solution appears to be feasible. The extent and effectiveness of planned engagement with end users in co-designing and testing the solution appears to be appropriate. The proposal has in place a plan for addressing ethical and legal considerations relevant to the project. It’s not clear whether the proposed project will contribute to the DRG4Food toolbox with open source solutions.

Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs

The team’s expertise in cybersecurity is not presented in detail. Moreover, the identification of cybersecurity threats and the strategies for their mitigation appear to be somewhat generic. The proposal's approach to privacy, including how personal data is handled securely and transparently, appears to be appropriate. The strategies for ensuring dataset integrity and mitigating potential biases presented by the proposal, lacks details and clarity. It’s not clear if a process for reviewing the clarity of algorithmic outputs and the assessment and mitigation of algorithmic bias, is in place. The proposal adequately facilitates user control over data and establishes transparency measures. The proposal has the potential to realize multiple DRGs.

Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact

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The presented USPs of the proposed solution, their alignment with user needs, and the value proposition of the solution, appear to be strong. The market analysis and the competitor analysis are not comprehensive. As this is an EU- funded project, it needs to have a European dimension and the fact that “This uniquely crafted application is the first of its kind in Bosnia and Herzegovina” is not enough. The business model is not presented in sufficient detail and there are no financial projections. The proposal’s approach to IPR management appears to be appropriate. The same applies in the exploitation strategy.

Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation

The clarity and feasibility of the proposed work plan is mostly adequate and the same applies to the definition and feasibility of milestones and deliverables. The fact that the timeplan doesn’t match the specification of the open call is a shortcoming. The procedures for risk assessment and have not been described in detail. Some identified risks and the strategies for risk mitigation are presented briefly but lack information and clarity. The resource allocation appears to be appropriate when it comes to direct costs but the indirect costs are calculated as equal to 10%, not following the instruction of the open call. The strength of collaboration is appropriate, and the individual capacities of the team members appear to be relevant, although some more detail would be appreciated.

Appraisal Scale per Criterion

Each criterion is evaluated on a scale up to 5, detailed as follows:

- 1 / POOR** *The proposal addresses the criterion in an inadequate manner or there are significant weaknesses.*
- 2 / FAIR** *The proposal addresses the criterion broadly, but there are still several weaknesses.*
- 3 / GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion well, but improvements are necessary.*
- 4 / VERY GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion very well, but some improvements are still possible.*
- 5 / EXCELLENT** *The proposal successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the criterion. Any shortcomings are minor.*

The overall threshold for the total score is 12/20.

Evaluation Summary Report

DRG4Food Open Call #1

Proposal Title: NutriChain

Outcome of Phase 2 – Remote Evaluation

Criterion	Average Points
Technology Excellence and Innovation <i>Assessing projects on innovation, compliance with EU food policies, advancements in data-driven technology, user collaboration, ethical standards, and open-source contributions.</i>	3.5/5
Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs <i>Evaluating projects on cybersecurity expertise, privacy standards, dataset integrity, user data control, algorithm transparency, and enabling DRG realization.</i>	4/5
Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact <i>Assessing business viability, scalability, and impact through unique selling points, market research, competitor analysis, financial projections, and IP rights management.</i>	3.5/5
Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation <i>Assessing consortium capability and qualifications, including work plan clarity, milestone definition, resource allocation, and expertise for development.</i>	4/5
TOTAL POINTS	15/20

STATUS: NOT SELECTED FOR FUNDING

Feedback and Areas for Improvement

Technology Excellence and Innovation

The proposal is fully aligned with DRG4Food challenges, by focusing on responsibility, user sovereignty, and trust in technology. The proposal targets a specific user base, health-conscious individuals with a clear need for comprehensive information on food health and sustainability aspects. The proposed technological approach is sound, however, the progress beyond the state of the art is not sufficiently provided. The engagement of end-users is appropriately addressed. Open-source contributions are appropriately addressed.

Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs

The expertise of the team expertise in secure software design and cybersecurity is sufficiently demonstrated. The potential cybersecurity threats or attack vectors are very well defined. The proposed mitigation strategies are very convincing.

The proposed approach to privacy, including handing personal data, is very good. The proposed strategies for ensuring dataset integrity are credible. The mitigation of potential biases addressed from a high-level perspective. User control over data and establishment of transparency measures are very good. The proposed project has the potential to realize all DRG criteria.

Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact

The project's USPs are closely aligned with the DRG4Food challenges, focusing on data quality, blockchain integration for security, user-friendly reports, and features that promote informed choices and sustainability awareness. The project's competitive edge is further defined by its comprehensive solution that integrates data on antinutrients, sustainability, carbon footprint, and progress tracking, setting it apart from singularly focused alternatives.

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Collaborations with academic institutions enhance its data quality and credibility, while an open-source commitment fosters community involvement and transparency. NutriChain's business model is designed around a freemium approach, offering core functionalities for free and generating revenue through premium services. Financial projections are credible. What is missing is a clear overview of its direct and indirect competitors and more specific IPR strategy between partners.

Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation

The NutriChain project has established a well-structured work plan and implementation strategy, aligning with the DRG4Food guidelines and strategically guiding the project through its phases. The NutriChain team has identified potential challenges and has proactively established mitigation actions, such as ensuring data accuracy through academic collaborations. The consortium composition suggests a strong foundation for developing impactful solutions that drive efficiency, sustainability, and positive social outcomes. However, while the work plan is clearly outlined, the exact mechanisms for risk mitigation.

Appraisal Scale per Criterion

Each criterion is evaluated on a scale up to 5, detailed as follows:

- 1 / POOR** *The proposal addresses the criterion in an inadequate manner or there are significant weaknesses.*
- 2 / FAIR** *The proposal addresses the criterion broadly, but there are still several weaknesses.*
- 3 / GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion well, but improvements are necessary.*
- 4 / VERY GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion very well, but some improvements are still possible.*
- 5 / EXCELLENT** *The proposal successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the criterion. Any shortcomings are minor.*

The overall threshold for the total score is 12/20.

Evaluation Summary Report

DRG4Food Open Call #1

Proposal Title: NuTriGuide

Outcome of Phase 2 – Remote Evaluation

Criterion	Average Points
Technology Excellence and Innovation <i>Assessing projects on innovation, compliance with EU food policies, advancements in data-driven technology, user collaboration, ethical standards, and open-source contributions.</i>	5/5
Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs <i>Evaluating projects on cybersecurity expertise, privacy standards, dataset integrity, user data control, algorithm transparency, and enabling DRG realization.</i>	5/5
Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact <i>Assessing business viability, scalability, and impact through unique selling points, market research, competitor analysis, financial projections, and IP rights management.</i>	4/5
Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation <i>Assessing consortium capability and qualifications, including work plan clarity, milestone definition, resource allocation, and expertise for development.</i>	4.5/5
TOTAL POINTS	18.5/20

STATUS: NOT SELECTED FOR FUNDING

Feedback and Areas for Improvement

Technology Excellence and Innovation

NuTriGuide's approach to integrating AI in food data processing aligns well with DRG4Food's focus on trust and user empowerment, showcasing innovation with its advanced technology for food tracking and nutrition guidance. Contributions to the open-source community and the DRG4Food toolbox are planned.

Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs

The NuTriGuide project earns a strong score of 5 out of 5 in Data Responsibility, Transparency, and Alignment with DRGs, reflecting a deep commitment to cybersecurity, privacy, and ethical AI. Leveraging expert data encryption and GDPR compliance, the team prioritizes user data control and transparent data handling, avoiding personal data usage. They've instituted clear strategies for cybersecurity, dataset integrity, and bias mitigation, with plans for open-source contributions. NuTriGuide's alignment with DRG4Food objectives is clear, ensuring user empowerment and algorithmic transparency as core project tenets.

Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact

The NuTriGuide proposal demonstrates a well-thought-out approach to delivering technological innovation that aligns with DRG4Food's objectives, particularly in fostering trust and transparency in food choices through advanced AI methods. While they offer unique selling points (USPs) in terms of a trustworthy, explainable AI methodology and a human-centric design, the project could benefit from a more in-depth competitive analysis and a detailed market fitness assessment. Despite a solid value proposition and a clear path to integration and scalability through the DRG4Food Toolbox, the financial projections and

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commercialization strategy, though briefly mentioned, would be enhanced by more specificity and detail, especially regarding customer acquisition, costs, and market penetration strategies. Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) management is briefly. Overall, the proposal presents strong USPs and state of the art innovation.

Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation

The NuTriGuide proposal presents a cohesive and multidisciplinary consortium comprising expertise in computer science, data science, cybersecurity, human-computer interaction, usability testing, as well as food science and nutrition. The team's qualifications are robust, drawing from academic and research-driven backgrounds, which ensures a comprehensive approach to project development and management. The work plan is structured with clear objectives, deliverables, and key performance indicators, which align with the project's stages and goals. Mitigation plans for potential risks are well-considered, showcasing a proactive stance towards project challenges. Resource allocation appears judiciously planned, with personnel and financial resources strategically distributed to fulfill project objectives. The consortium's partnership with industry stakeholders like Filaios adds practical value and real-world applicability, enhancing the potential for successful project outcomes. More explicit discussion on how the project's milestones and deliverables will be monitored and achieved would strengthen the proposal. Despite these areas for enhancement, the consortium's strong technical foundation and strategic resource allocation contribute to a promising project outlook.

Appraisal Scale per Criterion

Each criterion is evaluated on a scale up to 5, detailed as follows:

- 1 / POOR** *The proposal addresses the criterion in an inadequate manner or there are significant weaknesses.*
- 2 / FAIR** *The proposal addresses the criterion broadly, but there are still several weaknesses.*
- 3 / GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion well, but improvements are necessary.*
- 4 / VERY GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion very well, but some improvements are still possible.*
- 5 / EXCELLENT** *The proposal successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the criterion. Any shortcomings are minor.*

The overall threshold for the total score is 12/20.

Evaluation Summary Report

DRG4Food Open Call #1

Proposal Title: NUTRIPAL

Outcome of Phase 2 – Remote Evaluation

Criterion	Average Points
Technology Excellence and Innovation <i>Assessing projects on innovation, compliance with EU food policies, advancements in data-driven technology, user collaboration, ethical standards, and open-source contributions.</i>	3.5/5
Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs <i>Evaluating projects on cybersecurity expertise, privacy standards, dataset integrity, user data control, algorithm transparency, and enabling DRG realization.</i>	3/5
Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact <i>Assessing business viability, scalability, and impact through unique selling points, market research, competitor analysis, financial projections, and IP rights management.</i>	4/5
Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation <i>Assessing consortium capability and qualifications, including work plan clarity, milestone definition, resource allocation, and expertise for development.</i>	4/5
TOTAL POINTS	14.5/20

STATUS: NOT SELECTED FOR FUNDING

Feedback and Areas for Improvement

Technology Excellence and Innovation

While the technology proposed to support personalized nutrition is commendable, the proposal lacks a description of how it offers something innovative with respect to current existing solutions. The proposal could significantly benefit from a clearer explanation of what makes its technology unique, including specific advances in its algorithm that differentiate it from competitors.

Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs

The project outlines a comprehensive approach to data security and user privacy that meets the required standards. The approach to data handling is robust, incorporating encryption, secure authentication and real-time DDoS attack mitigation, demonstrating a strong commitment to data security and privacy. However, the proposal does not fully address the potential risks associated with bias in AI algorithms and the implications for personalized dietary recommendations. Furthermore, even though the proposal takes into account the use of user consent and data withdrawal mechanisms, which seem to be in line with DRG in general, there's room for further elaboration on user consent mechanisms and how users can control or withdraw their data.

Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact

The proposal presents a viable business model with potential for scalability, particularly through its subscription and freemium models designed to incentivize healthy lifestyles. The focus on personalized nutrition is in line with market trends towards individualization and health consciousness. While the business model is strong, a more detailed analysis of the

competitive landscape and a clearer go-to-market strategy for scaling beyond Cluj Napoca could further strengthen the proposal.

Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation

The consortium brings together a multidisciplinary team with expertise in nutrition, technology development and market research that is well placed to deliver the project. The allocation of roles and responsibilities is clear and the qualifications of the team are directly relevant to the objectives of the project. Resource allocation is described, but there's a lack of detail on risk management, contingency planning and adaptability to project challenges.

Appraisal Scale per Criterion

Each criterion is evaluated on a scale up to 5, detailed as follows:

- 1 / POOR** *The proposal addresses the criterion in an inadequate manner or there are significant weaknesses.*
- 2 / FAIR** *The proposal addresses the criterion broadly, but there are still several weaknesses.*
- 3 / GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion well, but improvements are necessary.*
- 4 / VERY GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion very well, but some improvements are still possible.*
- 5 / EXCELLENT** *The proposal successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the criterion. Any shortcomings are minor.*

The overall threshold for the total score is 12/20.

Evaluation Summary Report

DRG4Food Open Call #1

Proposal Title: NutriReform

Outcome of Phase 2 – Remote Evaluation

Criterion	Average Points
Technology Excellence and Innovation <i>Assessing projects on innovation, compliance with EU food policies, advancements in data-driven technology, user collaboration, ethical standards, and open-source contributions.</i>	3.5/5
Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs <i>Evaluating projects on cybersecurity expertise, privacy standards, dataset integrity, user data control, algorithm transparency, and enabling DRG realization.</i>	3/5
Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact <i>Assessing business viability, scalability, and impact through unique selling points, market research, competitor analysis, financial projections, and IP rights management.</i>	3.5/5
Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation <i>Assessing consortium capability and qualifications, including work plan clarity, milestone definition, resource allocation, and expertise for development.</i>	4/5
TOTAL POINTS	14/20

STATUS: NOT SELECTED FOR FUNDING

Feedback and Areas for Improvement

Technology Excellence and Innovation

The proposal outlines a forward-thinking approach by incorporating AI-driven models for recipe reformulation and allergen detection, enhancing Nutrikator’s capabilities significantly. The integration of carbon footprint calculations is a notable innovation. However, the technology's novelty would benefit from further details on the AI methodologies to be used, ensuring they represent state-of-the-art advances.

Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs

The commitment to GDPR compliance, user data control, and the innovative approach towards minimizing data storage and processing are commendable. The project outlines a strong framework for data responsibility and transparency. Further elaboration on the modular application’s specifics could enhance understanding of its impact on data minimization.

Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact

The proposal adeptly identifies market needs and crafts a strategy for regional then global expansion, highlighting a subscription model aimed at engaging users, which suggests strong growth and sustainability potential. While financial projections are optimistic, augmenting the proposal with an in-depth risk analysis could offer a more balanced view. Additionally, expanding market analysis and detailing the commercialization strategy would provide a clearer roadmap for achieving its business objectives, enhancing the proposal's overall robustness and appeal to stakeholders. The business model's scalability, particularly how it plans to adapt and grow beyond its initial scope, requires further elaboration.

Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation

The consortium brings together a diverse team with complementary skills, from AI and software development to nutrition and market strategy. The detailed plan for resource allocation and the experience gained from the consortium members in previous projects suggest a high capability to execute the project successfully. Details on how the consortium will manage potential risks and their mitigation strategies are missing.

Appraisal Scale per Criterion

Each criterion is evaluated on a scale up to 5, detailed as follows:

- 1 / POOR** *The proposal addresses the criterion in an inadequate manner or there are significant weaknesses.*
- 2 / FAIR** *The proposal addresses the criterion broadly, but there are still several weaknesses.*
- 3 / GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion well, but improvements are necessary.*
- 4 / VERY GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion very well, but some improvements are still possible.*
- 5 / EXCELLENT** *The proposal successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the criterion. Any shortcomings are minor.*

The overall threshold for the total score is 12/20.

Evaluation Summary Report

DRG4Food Open Call #1

Proposal Title: NutriSight

Outcome of Phase 2 – Remote Evaluation

Criterion	Average Points
Technology Excellence and Innovation <i>Assessing projects on innovation, compliance with EU food policies, advancements in data-driven technology, user collaboration, ethical standards, and open-source contributions.</i>	5/5
Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs <i>Evaluating projects on cybersecurity expertise, privacy standards, dataset integrity, user data control, algorithm transparency, and enabling DRG realization.</i>	4/5
Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact <i>Assessing business viability, scalability, and impact through unique selling points, market research, competitor analysis, financial projections, and IP rights management.</i>	4/5
Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation <i>Assessing consortium capability and qualifications, including work plan clarity, milestone definition, resource allocation, and expertise for development.</i>	4.5/5
TOTAL POINTS	17.5/20

STATUS: SELECTED FOR FUNDING

Feedback and Areas for Improvement

Technology Excellence and Innovation

The proposal is perfectly aligned with the specific challenges of DRG4FOOD. There is a reasonably detailed and very clear outline of the proposals' technological approach. The proposal has further high (societal) relevance and innovative character. The plan for the advancement of TRL is feasible.

The proposal has great potential for user engagement and co-design. Ethical considerations are not particularly relevant, however, a discussion is lacking.

Open-source contributions are expertly addressed as the whole proposal is geared towards being open-source and open data.

Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs

The proposal provides concise answers to all relevant criteria and proposes well-founded and comprehensible arguments for how digital responsibility will be implemented.

Additional elaboration on e.g. how the accuracy of the output is maximized or false output mitigated would have scored even better.

Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact

The USP of the proposal is strong and demand on the market/in the community demonstrated through the consortium's experience as a central hub for food information. The result is exploitation is helped by already existing communities of consortium.

Business model, commercialisation strategy are not discussed as this proposal intends to provide their result to the community for free.

Value is created for their “brand”.

Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation

The workplan is detailed, feasible and cost-efficient. Qualifications of the consortium partners are suited for the project and sufficiently described. Risk management and mitigation is only sparsely addressed.

Appraisal Scale per Criterion

Each criterion is evaluated on a scale up to 5, detailed as follows:

- 1 / POOR** *The proposal addresses the criterion in an inadequate manner or there are significant weaknesses.*
- 2 / FAIR** *The proposal addresses the criterion broadly, but there are still several weaknesses.*
- 3 / GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion well, but improvements are necessary.*
- 4 / VERY GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion very well, but some improvements are still possible.*
- 5 / EXCELLENT** *The proposal successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the criterion. Any shortcomings are minor.*

The overall threshold for the total score is 12/20.

Evaluation Summary Report

DRG4Food Open Call #1

Proposal Title: NutriWell

Outcome of Phase 2 – Remote Evaluation

Criterion	Average Points
Technology Excellence and Innovation <i>Assessing projects on innovation, compliance with EU food policies, advancements in data-driven technology, user collaboration, ethical standards, and open-source contributions.</i>	4/5
Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs <i>Evaluating projects on cybersecurity expertise, privacy standards, dataset integrity, user data control, algorithm transparency, and enabling DRG realization.</i>	5/5
Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact <i>Assessing business viability, scalability, and impact through unique selling points, market research, competitor analysis, financial projections, and IP rights management.</i>	4.5/5
Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation <i>Assessing consortium capability and qualifications, including work plan clarity, milestone definition, resource allocation, and expertise for development.</i>	5/5
TOTAL POINTS	18.5

STATUS: SELECTED FOR FUNDING

Feedback and Areas for Improvement

Technology Excellence and Innovation

The NutriWell project presents a comprehensive approach aligning with DRG4Food's mission, focusing on AI-driven solutions for personalized nutrition, particularly for the elderly. They aim to enhance user empowerment through technology, promoting social inclusion and well-being. The objectives and technology infrastructure are well-articulated, with potential for clear market differentiation and user engagement, with ethical considerations and GDPR compliance embedded in the design. Plans for open-source contribution could be further detailed for complete evaluation. The proposal suggests a sound progression towards market introduction, but could benefit from a more granular rollout strategy.

Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs

The NutriWell project presents a robust approach to data responsibility, transparency, and alignment with Digital Resilience Guidelines (DRGs), showcasing its strength in secure software design and cybersecurity expertise. Their team includes certified professionals with a history of involvement in secure data-sharing infrastructures and projects emphasizing GDPR compliance and secure personal data handling. Transparency and user control over data are embedded within the project's framework, providing users the capacity to manage their personal data with explicit consent. Their mitigation strategy for algorithmic bias and commitment to transparent algorithmic outputs is clear, with the implementation of tools like Data Cards for dataset documentation and the alignment with the Assessment List for Trustworthy AI (ALTAI). Moreover, the proposal plans to contribute to the open-source community with several enablers intended for the DRG4Food toolbox, demonstrating a

commitment to the broader ecosystem. In terms of the realization of DRGs, the proposal actively incorporates several specific DRGs into its solution, ensuring that the objectives of user empowerment, trust, and ethical AI are met.

Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact

The NutriWell proposal demonstrates a multifaceted approach to creating a health and nutrition-focused platform, aligning strongly with DRG4Food's emphasis on trust, user empowerment, and innovative solutions. With a suite of tools including a Nutrition Data Space, AI-powered nutrition plan generator, and social cooking organizer, the project targets enhancing healthy eating habits and social interaction among the elderly. The Unique Selling Points (USPs) revolve around personalized nutrition plans and community-building through cooking, aiming to alleviate social isolation among the elderly. The competitive analysis identifies a niche in non-medical, socially driven services which set NutriWell apart from existing medical-focused solutions. Their market strategy highlights the integration with established data-sharing platforms like i4Trust and dataU, ensuring GDPR-compliant data management. IPR overviewed. However, while financial projections are mentioned, there is room for more detailed breakdowns and specific market strategies.

Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation

The project demonstrates a structured approach with a well-defined work plan that includes specific activities, tools, modules, and integration strategies. The activities are clearly categorized. The proposal outlines a comprehensive plan for communication, dissemination, and exploitation, ensuring the project's results reach relevant stakeholders and the broader community. The consortium is composed of a mix of non-profit NGOs, SMEs, and NGOs, bringing together a diverse range of expertise from AI and ICT-based solutions to user-centered design and social innovation. The detailed listing of team members, their roles, expertise, and contributions to the project, underscores a strong foundation for successful project implementation. The allocation of person-months and project costs indicates a careful consideration of resource distribution among tasks and consortium members.

Appraisal Scale per Criterion

Each criterion is evaluated on a scale up to 5, detailed as follows:

- 1 / POOR** *The proposal addresses the criterion in an inadequate manner or there are significant weaknesses.*
- 2 / FAIR** *The proposal addresses the criterion broadly, but there are still several weaknesses.*
- 3 / GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion well, but improvements are necessary.*
- 4 / VERY GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion very well, but some improvements are still possible.*
- 5 / EXCELLENT** *The proposal successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the criterion. Any shortcomings are minor.*

The overall threshold for the total score is 12/20.

Evaluation Summary Report

DRG4Food Open Call #1

Proposal Title: OFDN

Outcome of Phase 2 – Remote Evaluation

Criterion	Average Points
Technology Excellence and Innovation <i>Assessing projects on innovation, compliance with EU food policies, advancements in data-driven technology, user collaboration, ethical standards, and open-source contributions.</i>	3.5
Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs <i>Evaluating projects on cybersecurity expertise, privacy standards, dataset integrity, user data control, algorithm transparency, and enabling DRG realization.</i>	3.5
Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact <i>Assessing business viability, scalability, and impact through unique selling points, market research, competitor analysis, financial projections, and IP rights management.</i>	3.5
Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation <i>Assessing consortium capability and qualifications, including work plan clarity, milestone definition, resource allocation, and expertise for development.</i>	4
TOTAL POINTS	14.5

STATUS: NOT SELECTED FOR FUNDING

Feedback and Areas for Improvement

Technology Excellence and Innovation

The project proposes to build upon an already developed open-source technology stack and also proposed dissemination will be managed through a well-established network – and while above mentioned insights, and development are deemed highly relevant there is missing any clear mention or interest to directly contribute or connect to the DRG4FOOD project goals and/or DRG4FOOD toolbox. As such the proposal reads more as a well-established initiative primarily interested in gaining funding to continue running and/or upgrade a currently running program. While Open-source requirement is well met there is nevertheless an apparent lack of understanding (interest) or connection to the DRG4FOOD project goals, and in particular DRG4FOOD toolbox development, or contribution to the Open Call #2 which would require some effort to better enable others to develop new and innovative solutions with OFDN as an enabler, with documentation, testing set-ups etc. delivered for this purpose. This may risk being a more closed, standalone project not expecting to engage with the DRG4FOOD project goals of open development.

Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs

Proposal highlights well where data and security risks lie and have clear expertise and approaches to mitigate as well as actively apply a data minimizing strategy to use-case development. While there is note of a decentralized food network and data transparency, it is not clear if there are any innovations anticipated with respect to the further development or integration of innovative, decentralized architectures, consideration of decentralized or customized identity and authentication enablers/approaches or other innovations to support data transparency, privacy as trust, user agency and sovereignty or GDPR rights.

Data fairness, transparency and trust are mentioned in the proposal but it was not clear of any explicit connection to technology enabler innovation or integrations that might be further tested and/or more widely applicable (beyond DFC protocol) also seem to be leaning on users and use cases (untrustworthy producers lose their market/correctness of data validated by the consumers).

There is mention of integrating modern AI tools in future versions but not clear if that is relevant for this project although there is mention of creating “an algorithm that is exactly based on quality and quantity of food data that is entered by the producers themselves, and to make the customers understand what and why we show in various product lists” – but somewhat missing detail on AI and algorithmic trustworthiness developments.

Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact

Good attention is given to business competitive edge and opportunities to ensure business viability. Scalability is facilitated through a modular design although one possible weakness (but also a potential strength through focus) is the short chain and local food hub focus and heavy reliance on food hub personnel and customers to validate data.

Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation

Consortium brings a very good mix of expertise and necessary experience focus from software development, digital innovation and research capability as well as short food supply and IT solutions for farmers. Further the express inclusion of UX design and development as well as community development and marketing indicate a well-considered balance of team skills and allocation to achieve stated goals.

The budget is adequate and in line with the main project results, however, for some activities the allocated resources seem to be a bit over estimated.

Appraisal Scale per Criterion

Each criterion is evaluated on a scale up to 5, detailed as follows:

- 1 / POOR** *The proposal addresses the criterion in an inadequate manner or there are significant weaknesses.*
- 2 / FAIR** *The proposal addresses the criterion broadly, but there are still several weaknesses.*
- 3 / GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion well, but improvements are necessary.*
- 4 / VERY GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion very well, but some improvements are still possible.*
- 5 / EXCELLENT** *The proposal successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the criterion. Any shortcomings are minor.*

The overall threshold for the total score is 12/20.

Evaluation Summary Report

DRG4Food Open Call #1

Proposal Title: OilTrace

Outcome of Phase 2 – Remote Evaluation

Criterion	Average Points
Technology Excellence and Innovation <i>Assessing projects on innovation, compliance with EU food policies, advancements in data-driven technology, user collaboration, ethical standards, and open-source contributions.</i>	4.5/5
Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs <i>Evaluating projects on cybersecurity expertise, privacy standards, dataset integrity, user data control, algorithm transparency, and enabling DRG realization.</i>	5/5
Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact <i>Assessing business viability, scalability, and impact through unique selling points, market research, competitor analysis, financial projections, and IP rights management.</i>	3.5/5
Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation <i>Assessing consortium capability and qualifications, including work plan clarity, milestone definition, resource allocation, and expertise for development.</i>	4/5
TOTAL POINTS	17

STATUS: NOT SELECTED FOR FUNDING

Feedback and Areas for Improvement

Technology Excellence and Innovation

The OilTrace proposal showcases a commendable level of technological innovation, particularly through its proposal to integrate IoT sensors with AI-driven predictive analytics and QR code-based consumer engagement to trace the quality of food oil throughout the supply chain. The project's comprehensive technological strategy for monitoring and predicting the oxidative state of oils to ensure food quality is noteworthy. However, the project's success depends heavily on the precise coordination and seamless integration of its various technological components, which may face unforeseen challenges. Therefore, it is advisable to include a risk analysis, along with associated mitigation actions for each identified risk. Moreover, while the technology is innovative, the proposal would benefit from an in-depth exploration of the complexity and adaptability of the AI models to real-world variations in food oil storage conditions. The proposal details technological innovation with AI and IoT for oil oxidation monitoring but lacks comparative analysis with existing solutions and a detailed plan for achieving TRL 7.

Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs

OilTrace demonstrates a good commitment to data responsibility and transparency, aligning well with DRGs. The proposal outlines comprehensive measures for cybersecurity, user-friendly implementation of data rights, and algorithmic bias mitigation.

Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact

OilTrace showcases promising business viability and scalability, particularly in its potential application beyond food oil to other perishable products. The proposal reports a comprehensive analysis, indicating a strong market position. While the business model and

scalability are discussed, financial projections and assumptions are vague, and scalability beyond the initial target market requires further elaboration.

Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation

The consortium behind OilTrace is well-composed, with a mix of SMEs and academic institutions with complementary expertise. The team qualifications are very good, and the distribution of roles and responsibilities is well-defined. Somewhat to be appreciated is the inclusion of a complete list of KPIs with associated target values that will allow to monitor the project advancements, even if, the proposal would benefit from a more detailed risk management plan, addressing potential delays and outlining contingency measures for resource reallocation.

Appraisal Scale per Criterion

Each criterion is evaluated on a scale up to 5, detailed as follows:

- 1 / POOR** *The proposal addresses the criterion in an inadequate manner or there are significant weaknesses.*
- 2 / FAIR** *The proposal addresses the criterion in an inadequate manner or there are significant weaknesses.*
- 3 / GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion well, but improvements are necessary.*
- 4 / VERY GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion very well, but some improvements are still possible.*
- 5 / EXCELLENT** *The proposal successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the criterion. Any shortcomings are minor.*

The overall threshold for the total score is 12/20.

Evaluation Summary Report

DRG4Food Open Call #1

Proposal Title: OpenBatra

Outcome of Phase 2 – Remote Evaluation

Criterion	Average Points
Technology Excellence and Innovation <i>Assessing projects on innovation, compliance with EU food policies, advancements in data-driven technology, user collaboration, ethical standards, and open-source contributions.</i>	3/5
Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs <i>Evaluating projects on cybersecurity expertise, privacy standards, dataset integrity, user data control, algorithm transparency, and enabling DRG realization.</i>	3/5
Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact <i>Assessing business viability, scalability, and impact through unique selling points, market research, competitor analysis, financial projections, and IP rights management.</i>	2.5/5
Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation <i>Assessing consortium capability and qualifications, including work plan clarity, milestone definition, resource allocation, and expertise for development.</i>	2.5/5
TOTAL POINTS	11/20

STATUS: NOT SELECTED FOR FUNDING

Feedback and Areas for Improvement

Technology Excellence and Innovation

The OpenBatra 3.0 proposal offers alignment with with DRG4Food Challenges. OpenBatra 3.0 aims to revolutionize access to local food product information, enhancing transparency and traceability, which aligns well with DRG4Food's focus on digital food tracking.

It proposes an advanced technological solution, utilizing blockchain for decentralized identity verification, AI for automated data capture, and P2P/IPFS for distributed data storage, showcasing a forward-thinking approach to technological advancement.

User Engagement: The project plans to actively involve end-users in the development process through interviews, focus groups, and pilot testing, ensuring the solution meets user needs.

Areas for Improvement: The proposal could benefit from deeper insights into the technical infrastructure, specifically how blockchain, AI, and decentralized storage will be implemented and integrated. While the proposal mentions addressing these considerations, more detailed plans and examples of how ethical and legal standards will be upheld are needed. The willingness to contribute to the DRG4Food toolbox is mentioned, but specific plans on how OpenBatra 3.0 will achieve this could be expanded. While the project is focused on the TRL5 to TRL7 path, its market path and strategy are not showcased.

Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs

The OpenBatra 3.0 proposal showcases a strong commitment to data responsibility and transparency, with key strengths including a well-qualified cybersecurity team, comprehensive cybersecurity mitigation strategies, and a clear focus on privacy and data

handling. The proposal also emphasizes dataset integrity, user control, algorithmic clarity, and bias mitigation, aligning well with DRGs. However, it could benefit from more detailed descriptions of the team's cybersecurity experience, specifics of cybersecurity implementations, expanded dataset integrity measures, and further details on algorithmic bias mitigation.

Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact

The proposal relies heavily on the inherent qualities of blockchain, which, while beneficial, are not unique to this project. The USPs seem generic and not sufficiently differentiated. The competitive analysis lacks depth, missing a detailed comparison with existing solutions, user adoption barriers, and potential market risks. The proposal would benefit from a more granular market segmentation and identification of specific customer pain points. The financial projections and scaling strategy are not thoroughly developed, with no details on revenue streams, cost structure, and break-even analysis. A more detailed roadmap for market entry and expansion, especially in diverse geographies, is needed. While the proposal mentions a hybrid IPR approach, it lacks a clear strategy for protecting proprietary technology and maximizing the commercial potential of the project's outcomes. Detailed plans for licensing, partnerships, and market positioning are necessary to ensure sustainable competitive advantage.

Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation

The consortium comprises SMEs and research centers with a strong background in blockchain, AI, and cybersecurity, indicating a robust foundation of technical expertise. Resources are clearly delineated among consortium members, ensuring dedicated efforts towards specific project components. The work plan, while structured into phases, lacks detailed task breakdowns, timelines, and specific responsibilities, making it challenging to assess overall feasibility. Milestones are outlined, but deliverables lack specificity in terms of measurable outcomes and impact, reducing the clarity on project progression. The proposal does not provide a comprehensive risk assessment or detailed mitigation strategies for technical, market, or operational risks. Lacks exploitation work package.

Appraisal Scale per Criterion

Each criterion is evaluated on a scale up to 5, detailed as follows:

- 1 / POOR** *The proposal addresses the criterion in an inadequate manner or there are significant weaknesses.*
- 2 / FAIR** *The proposal addresses the criterion broadly, but there are still several weaknesses.*
- 3 / GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion well, but improvements are necessary.*
- 4 / VERY GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion very well, but some improvements are still possible.*
- 5 / EXCELLENT** *The proposal successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the criterion. Any shortcomings are minor.*

The overall threshold for the total score is 12/20.

Evaluation Summary Report

DRG4Food Open Call #1

Proposal Title: ORACLE

Outcome of Phase 2 – Remote Evaluation

Criterion	Average Points
Technology Excellence and Innovation <i>Assessing projects on innovation, compliance with EU food policies, advancements in data-driven technology, user collaboration, ethical standards, and open-source contributions.</i>	4/5
Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs <i>Evaluating projects on cybersecurity expertise, privacy standards, dataset integrity, user data control, algorithm transparency, and enabling DRG realization.</i>	3/5
Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact <i>Assessing business viability, scalability, and impact through unique selling points, market research, competitor analysis, financial projections, and IP rights management.</i>	3.5/5
Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation <i>Assessing consortium capability and qualifications, including work plan clarity, milestone definition, resource allocation, and expertise for development.</i>	4/5
TOTAL POINTS	14.5/20

STATUS: NOT SELECTED FOR FUNDING

Feedback and Areas for Improvement

Technology Excellence and Innovation

The project proposal matches well with the DRG4Food challenges Food Tracking and Consumers Food choices. The project is focused on a very specific solution development for the table grape value chain, from growers to consumers. Innovative developments are proposed to build upon previous research and pilot developments.

The integration of all the different innovation enablers into a working solution is seen as very strong aspect of this proposal, as well as the proposed application of innovative technology to address key DRG challenges. However, there is a lack of satisfactory focus on what this proposal intends to contribute to the DRG4FOOD project and in particular Call#1 ambitions and goals, or clarity into how proposal will be pro-actively contributing the DR4FOOD Toolbox and supporting potential wider application of enablers in Call#2 solutions. There is summary mention of contributing two open-source enablers to the toolbox, but lack clarity in the wider application value these bring – much of the solution development will remain closed and proprietary, with enablers that will be open assumed to be limited and grape (data) oriented – with no further integration enablers, tools or documentation to be provided – no evidence to ensure DRG validation, or wider applicability and usage within the DRG4FOOD project.

Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs

The proposal, while incorporating digital rights governance (DRG) indicators, falls short of actively developing and testing DRG enabler assumptions within its solution for a table grape context, revealing a mismatch in focus. It lacks detailed methodologies for validating how DRGs are specifically addressed as part of its research and development objectives. Merely

stating that technologies like Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT) or an analytics platform will enhance trust does not sufficiently explain the mechanisms for building and testing these assumptions. Similarly, the mention of leveraging federated learning for distributed data processing fails to adequately address how it will tackle data sensitivity challenges.

Moreover, while privacy standards are mentioned to be upheld through compliance audits, the proposal does not delve into innovative research methods or enablers for advancing privacy beyond regulatory necessities or how such privacy enhancements could influence trust and acceptance of the solution. This approach suggests a passive interpretation of innovating with DRG in mind, focusing more on developing a solution for table grapes without a strong emphasis on citizen-centric goals aligned with the European Data Strategy's vision of empowering society through data in a manner that prioritizes individual rights and reflects European values.

Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact

The impacts related with the project are coherent with the results and with the proposed activities.

A clear business model have been defined and all the main elements are present.

The preliminary business plan is in line with the market and the cost and revenues structure is in line with the specific project results.

The described competitive landscape and value model highlight a set of unique selling points that will allow the proposed solution to deliver value to the table grape value chain. Data usage is seen as a focal point of its user experience and proposition to generate awareness and support decision making with the intention of creating trust through the value chain.

Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation

The proposed work plan is complete and well done.

The cooperation between the partners has been well defined even if, in some case, some responsibilities have been not declared.

The proposed deliverables are coherent with the activities and the results.

A clear risk mitigation plan misses of some details.

The budget is well balanced between the partners and in the different WPS.

In some case, there are an over estimation of the involved resources.

Appraisal Scale per Criterion

Each criterion is evaluated on a scale up to 5, detailed as follows:

- 1 / POOR** *The proposal addresses the criterion in an inadequate manner or there are significant weaknesses.*
- 2 / FAIR** *The proposal addresses the criterion broadly, but there are still several weaknesses.*
- 3 / GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion well, but improvements are necessary.*
- 4 / VERY GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion very well, but some improvements are still possible.*
- 5 / EXCELLENT** *The proposal successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the criterion. Any shortcomings are minor.*

The overall threshold for the total score is 12/20.

Evaluation Summary Report

DRG4Food Open Call #1

Proposal Title: Q-Tracklife

Outcome of Phase 2 – Remote Evaluation

Criterion	Average Points
Technology Excellence and Innovation <i>Assessing projects on innovation, compliance with EU food policies, advancements in data-driven technology, user collaboration, ethical standards, and open-source contributions.</i>	4/5
Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs <i>Evaluating projects on cybersecurity expertise, privacy standards, dataset integrity, user data control, algorithm transparency, and enabling DRG realization.</i>	4/5
Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact <i>Assessing business viability, scalability, and impact through unique selling points, market research, competitor analysis, financial projections, and IP rights management.</i>	3/5
Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation <i>Assessing consortium capability and qualifications, including work plan clarity, milestone definition, resource allocation, and expertise for development.</i>	3/5
TOTAL POINTS	14/20

STATUS: NOT SELECTED FOR FUNDING

Feedback and Areas for Improvement

Technology Excellence and Innovation

The proposal is fully aligned with DRG4Food challenges, for example trust and citizen engagement.

The proposed technological approach is sound, it aims to identify and analyse fruit quality parameters throughout the transportation and logistics stages to develop a model for predicting the evolution of product quality. However, the progress beyond the state of the art is not sufficiently provided.

The objectives are overall clear. The objectives are very pertinent to the call and aligned with all Digital Responsibility Goals.

The proposed advancement of the Technology Readiness Level (TRL) is very ambitious. However, timing for market introduction is not sufficiently provided.

The end-users are very well defined. However, their engagement and involvement in co-designing is not sufficiently proposed. This is a shortcoming.

Some ethical and legal considerations relevant to the project are appropriately addressed.

Open source contributions are appropriately targeted. However, the willingness to contribute to the DRG4Food toolbox is not convincingly provided. This is a shortcoming.

Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs

The expertise of the team expertise in secure software design and cybersecurity is not sufficiently demonstrated. This is a shortcoming.

Cybersecurity threats and mitigation strategy is not sufficiently explored. This is an important shortcoming.

The proposed approach to privacy, including handling personal data, is appropriate.

The proposed strategies for ensuring dataset integrity are overall credible. The mitigation of potential biases is appropriately addressed.

User control over data and establishment of transparency measures are appropriate.

Mitigation of algorithmic bias is sufficiently addressed.

The potential of the proposal to realize DRG criteria are very well addressed. The proposed project has the potential to realize several DRG criteria. This is a strength of the proposal.

Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact

The alignment of the proposed solution with user needs is properly demonstrated.

However, Unique Selling Points (USPs) are not sufficiently identified. This is an important shortcoming.

The market analysis is not sufficiently elaborated, for example competitor analysis is not sufficiently presented.

The proposed business model is conceptually convincing. However, financial projections, and strategy for scaling are not sufficiently presented. This is an important shortcoming.

IPR management is not sufficiently addressed. Individual exploitation strategies for partners are not sufficiently provided. These are important shortcomings.

Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation

The work plan is only broadly described. Timing is appropriate. Milestones and deliverables are not sufficiently provided. These are important shortcomings.

Procedures for risk assessment and the strategies for risk mitigation are not sufficiently provided. This is an important shortcoming.

Human and financial resources are credibly allocated and properly justified.

The consortium is appropriate and includes most of the necessary expertise to execute the project.

Appraisal Scale per Criterion

Each criterion is evaluated on a scale up to 5, detailed as follows:

- 1 / POOR** *The proposal addresses the criterion in an inadequate manner or there are significant weaknesses.*
- 2 / FAIR** *The proposal addresses the criterion broadly, but there are still several weaknesses.*
- 3 / GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion well, but improvements are necessary.*
- 4 / VERY GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion very well, but some improvements are still possible.*
- 5 / EXCELLENT** *The proposal successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the criterion. Any shortcomings are minor.*

The overall threshold for the total score is 12/20.

Evaluation Summary Report

DRG4Food Open Call #1

Proposal Title: ReviewBOT

Outcome of Phase 2 – Remote Evaluation

Criterion	Average Points
Technology Excellence and Innovation <i>Assessing projects on innovation, compliance with EU food policies, advancements in data-driven technology, user collaboration, ethical standards, and open-source contributions.</i>	4/5
Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs <i>Evaluating projects on cybersecurity expertise, privacy standards, dataset integrity, user data control, algorithm transparency, and enabling DRG realization.</i>	3/5
Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact <i>Assessing business viability, scalability, and impact through unique selling points, market research, competitor analysis, financial projections, and IP rights management.</i>	4.5/5
Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation <i>Assessing consortium capability and qualifications, including work plan clarity, milestone definition, resource allocation, and expertise for development.</i>	4.5/5
TOTAL POINTS	16/20

STATUS: NOT SELECTED FOR FUNDING

Feedback and Areas for Improvement

Technology Excellence and Innovation

The proposal sounds innovative and in line with the scope of the call. All the main details, related with the technical development have been well described and only in few case, specific information are missing. There is a clear development beyond the state of the art and all the main project results are coherent with the proposed development. One area of concern highlighted by the project is bias reduction but also an inherent risk that may be less easy to overcome or at worse inadvertently amplified due to the acknowledged structural bias in the scientific world (and therefore inherent in the proprietary knowledge base).

Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs

The alignment with DRGs are coherent and there is a good quantification of the final achievements. Also in this case, all the critical information are complete and well defined. Regarding the data responsibility and the transparency sufficient information are present. Further, current focus appears to be focused on a proprietary knowledge base that is not open (or if it is this is not clear) it is not clear how comprehensive this is for food and health data and research (access to global, paid research publications?) or any measures in place to mitigate risk of bias, data manipulation, data ageing, inclusion barriers etc.

Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact

The flexibility to plug into different indices, databases, or knowledge graphs, such as enterprise internal repositories or external databases like PubMed or DBPedia, ensures that

the ReviewBOT can adapt to evolving data landscapes. This adaptability is crucial for scalability as it allows the system to stay relevant with the continuous influx of new information. By creating the right ecosystem (i.e., ReviewBOT architecture should allow to “plug in” to other external knowledgebases; plus, open-source usage with a free version) its viability will be tied to both its community and its credibility.

IPR has been considered and outlined with respect to partners and their contributions, and agreement to open-source public launch version.

One key business challenge may be the reliance of ReviewBOT on existing, commercial (and not open source) LLMs – the growth and relevance of ReviewBot is dependent on interoperability, integration and even legality of existing solutions that it aims to review in a symbiotic business case.

Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation

The consortium seems to have all the needed competences to develop the proposed actions. The proposed work plan is well defined and the planned deliverable are in line with the actions.

However, in some case, the cooperation between the partners and the main responsibilities for each of them are no so clear.

The use of resources is well balanced and all the other costs are well described and in line with the project results.

Appraisal Scale per Criterion

Each criterion is evaluated on a scale up to 5, detailed as follows:

- 1 / POOR** *The proposal addresses the criterion in an inadequate manner or there are significant weaknesses.*
- 2 / FAIR** *The proposal addresses the criterion broadly, but there are still several weaknesses.*
- 3 / GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion well, but improvements are necessary.*
- 4 / VERY GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion very well, but some improvements are still possible.*
- 5 / EXCELLENT** *The proposal successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the criterion. Any shortcomings are minor.*

The overall threshold for the total score is 12/20.

Evaluation Summary Report

DRG4Food Open Call #1

Proposal Title: RFDA

Outcome of Phase 2 – Remote Evaluation

Criterion	Average Points
Technology Excellence and Innovation <i>Assessing projects on innovation, compliance with EU food policies, advancements in data-driven technology, user collaboration, ethical standards, and open-source contributions.</i>	2/5
Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs <i>Evaluating projects on cybersecurity expertise, privacy standards, dataset integrity, user data control, algorithm transparency, and enabling DRG realization.</i>	4/5
Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact <i>Assessing business viability, scalability, and impact through unique selling points, market research, competitor analysis, financial projections, and IP rights management.</i>	3/5
Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation <i>Assessing consortium capability and qualifications, including work plan clarity, milestone definition, resource allocation, and expertise for development.</i>	4/5
TOTAL POINTS	13/20

STATUS: NOT SELECTED FOR FUNDING

Feedback and Areas for Improvement

Technology Excellence and Innovation

The proposal outlines an innovative approach using web and mobile technologies to provide dietary information and advice. However, it does not fully demonstrate a significant technological leap beyond existing solutions on the market. The use of QR codes and a web portal to access food information is a practical approach, but lacks a detailed explanation of the AI or advanced technologies that differentiate it from other dietary apps and platforms. The proposal could be strengthened by providing more insight into the unique technological innovations or algorithms used to provide personalised dietary suggestions.

Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs

The proposal shows a somewhat adequate to data responsibility and transparency, particularly in its adherence to GDPR and plans for secure data handling. The approach towards user data rights, encryption of personal data, and efforts to mitigate common cybersecurity threats are commendable. This aspect of the proposal suggests a well-thought-out strategy for managing data ethically and responsibly, aligning with data regulation guidelines.

Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact

While the proposal identifies unique selling points and outlines a business model, it appears somewhat optimistic without a robust analysis of potential challenges in user adoption and market penetration. The financial projections and scalability plans are presented but lack a detailed assessment of market dynamics and competitive positioning. Greater emphasis on

validating the market demand and the feasibility of the subscription and API sales model would enhance the proposal's strength in this criterion.

Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation

This consortium presents the required operational capacity to carry out the work outlined in the proposal. Team qualifications are solid. Resource allocation is justified. Risks are not identified.

Appraisal Scale per Criterion

Each criterion is evaluated on a scale up to 5, detailed as follows:

- 1 / POOR** *The proposal addresses the criterion in an inadequate manner or there are significant weaknesses.*
- 2 / FAIR** *The proposal addresses the criterion broadly, but there are still several weaknesses.*
- 3 / GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion well, but improvements are necessary.*
- 4 / VERY GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion very well, but some improvements are still possible.*
- 5 / EXCELLENT** *The proposal successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the criterion. Any shortcomings are minor.*

The overall threshold for the total score is 12/20.

Evaluation Summary Report

DRG4Food Open Call #1

Proposal Title: SafeNutriKids

Outcome of Phase 2 – Remote Evaluation

Criterion	Average Points
Technology Excellence and Innovation <i>Assessing projects on innovation, compliance with EU food policies, advancements in data-driven technology, user collaboration, ethical standards, and open-source contributions.</i>	3.5/5
Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs <i>Evaluating projects on cybersecurity expertise, privacy standards, dataset integrity, user data control, algorithm transparency, and enabling DRG realization.</i>	4.5/5
Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact <i>Assessing business viability, scalability, and impact through unique selling points, market research, competitor analysis, financial projections, and IP rights management.</i>	5/5
Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation <i>Assessing consortium capability and qualifications, including work plan clarity, milestone definition, resource allocation, and expertise for development.</i>	4.5/5
TOTAL POINTS	17.5/20

STATUS: SELECTED FOR FUNDING

Feedback and Areas for Improvement

Technology Excellence and Innovation

The proposal is very well aligned with the specific challenges of DRG4FOOD. There is a reasonably detailed outline of the proposals' technological approach, however, some clarity is missing of the more detailed functioning of the concept, e.g. how zero-knowledge-proofs are employed specifically. The proposal has (societal) relevance and innovative character. The plan for the advancement of TRL is feasible. The proposal has great potential for user engagement and co-design. Ethical and legal considerations could have been more pronounced given not only the sensitive data involved but also working with minors. Open-source contributions are addressed, however, it remains a bit vague how and what the proposal will provide to the DRG4FOOD toolbox.

Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs

The proposal provides clear answers to all relevant criteria and proposes comprehensible measures on how to implement digital responsibility without going into much technical detail.

Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact

USPs are well-founded and plausible. The market and competitor analysis is elaborate and considerations around the business model are credible. IPR management and exploitation strategy is sufficiently discussed.

Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation

The workplan is detailed, feasible and cost-efficient. While it can be assumed that qualifications of the consortium partners are suited for the project more information on prior

experience of team members would have been preferable. Risk management and mitigation is well addressed.

Appraisal Scale per Criterion

Each criterion is evaluated on a scale up to 5, detailed as follows:

- 1 / POOR** *The proposal addresses the criterion in an inadequate manner or there are significant weaknesses.*
- 2 / FAIR** *The proposal addresses the criterion broadly, but there are still several weaknesses.*
- 3 / GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion well, but improvements are necessary.*
- 4 / VERY GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion very well, but some improvements are still possible.*
- 5 / EXCELLENT** *The proposal successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the criterion. Any shortcomings are minor.*

The overall threshold for the total score is 12/20.

Evaluation Summary Report

DRG4Food Open Call #1

Proposal Title: SAFE-TRACE

Outcome of Phase 2 – Remote Evaluation

Criterion	Average Points
Technology Excellence and Innovation <i>Assessing projects on innovation, compliance with EU food policies, advancements in data-driven technology, user collaboration, ethical standards, and open-source contributions.</i>	4/5
Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs <i>Evaluating projects on cybersecurity expertise, privacy standards, dataset integrity, user data control, algorithm transparency, and enabling DRG realization.</i>	4.5/5
Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact <i>Assessing business viability, scalability, and impact through unique selling points, market research, competitor analysis, financial projections, and IP rights management.</i>	3/5
Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation <i>Assessing consortium capability and qualifications, including work plan clarity, milestone definition, resource allocation, and expertise for development.</i>	3/5
TOTAL POINTS	14.5/20

STATUS: NOT SELECTED FOR FUNDING

Feedback and Areas for Improvement

Technology Excellence and Innovation

The proposal addresses well the DRG4Food specific challenge area “Food Tracking”, while having strong emphasis on trust, citizen engagement, and user sovereignty. The proposal has an ambitious technological approach, which promises to go beyond the current state-of-the-art. The market launch of the proposed solution appears to be feasible. The extent and effectiveness of planned engagement with end users in co-designing and testing the solution appears to be appropriate.

The proposal has in place a plan for addressing ethical and legal considerations relevant to the project.

There is no indication that the proposed project will contribute to the DRG4Food toolbox with open-source solutions.

Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs

The team’s expertise in cybersecurity is not described at an appropriate level of clarity. Moreover, the identification of cybersecurity threats and the strategies for their mitigation lack a sufficient level of detail.

The proposal’s approach to privacy, including how personal data is handled securely and transparently, appears to be appropriate. The strategies for ensuring dataset integrity and mitigating potential biases presented by the proposal, appear to be appropriate. A process for reviewing the clarity of algorithmic outputs and the assessment and mitigation of algorithmic bias is in place. The proposal adequately facilitates user control over data and

establishes transparency measures. The proposal has the potential to realize at least two DRGs.

Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact

The presented USPs of the proposed solution, their alignment with user needs, and the value proposition of the solution, appear to be strong. The market analysis and the competitor analysis are adequate but could benefit from additional details. This is an important shortcoming.

The credibility of the business model is mostly adequate. However, although there are some financial projections, they lack the clarity needed to be assessed as credible. More specifically, it's not clear how the "conservative estimate of 1000 app users" will be reached during the 1st year. Moreover, more information would be needed to understand which customers in Albania would be willing to pay "an average of \$1,500/year per subscription". This is a shortcoming.

The proposal's approach to IPR management is presented at an appropriate level of detail. The same applies to the exploitation strategy. This is an important shortcoming.

Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation

The work plan is only broadly described. Milestones and deliverables are not sufficiently provided. These are altogether weaknesses. The procedures for risk assessment have not been described in detail. The identified risks and the strategies for risk mitigation are presented and, although they appear to be somewhat generic, they are relevant. The resource allocation appears to be appropriate. The strength of collaboration cannot be positively assessed with the current level of information. The individual capacities of the team members appear to be relevant, although some more detail would be appreciated.

Appraisal Scale per Criterion

Each criterion is evaluated on a scale up to 5, detailed as follows:

- 1 / POOR** *The proposal addresses the criterion in an inadequate manner or there are significant weaknesses.*
- 2 / FAIR** *The proposal addresses the criterion broadly, but there are still several weaknesses.*
- 3 / GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion well, but improvements are necessary.*
- 4 / VERY GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion very well, but some improvements are still possible.*
- 5 / EXCELLENT** *The proposal successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the criterion. Any shortcomings are minor.*

The overall threshold for the total score is 12/20.

Evaluation Summary Report

DRG4Food Open Call #1

Proposal Title: S-ATE

Outcome of Phase 2 – Remote Evaluation

Criterion	Average Points
Technology Excellence and Innovation <i>Assessing projects on innovation, compliance with EU food policies, advancements in data-driven technology, user collaboration, ethical standards, and open-source contributions.</i>	2/5
Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs <i>Evaluating projects on cybersecurity expertise, privacy standards, dataset integrity, user data control, algorithm transparency, and enabling DRG realization.</i>	2.5/5
Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact <i>Assessing business viability, scalability, and impact through unique selling points, market research, competitor analysis, financial projections, and IP rights management.</i>	2.5/5
Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation <i>Assessing consortium capability and qualifications, including work plan clarity, milestone definition, resource allocation, and expertise for development.</i>	3/5
TOTAL POINTS	10/20

STATUS: NOT SELECTED FOR FUNDING

Feedback and Areas for Improvement

Technology Excellence and Innovation

Proposal has aligned with the DRG4FOOD food Challenges, primarily Targeted Nutrition, but also Consumer Food Choices. It however lacks clear alignment with the DRG4FOOD goals with respect to addressing innovation in the areas of data privacy, emphasizing trust and user sovereignty whilst developing open-source technology enablers for DRG focused solutions. The proposal does not communicate well enough a convincing level of technology readiness, innovation or insight into DRG-enablers with respect to the innovation goals and ambitions of the DRG4FOOD program and particular the goals of this open call and the DRG4FOOD toolbox.

It is not clear how this proposal proposes to support and develop the use case – app - with an advanced level of digital responsibility – and clarity on specific technology innovation is missing so difficult to evaluate. There is summary description of algorithms developed by an expert in nutrition but no clarity of TRL in relation to broader identity and data management in the application or solution and/or if elements are or will be open-source. The development of app/data/algorithm with some user feedback loops is considered relevant, but as described in the proposal it is not clear how (or with what) the research approach is directly contributing to the European Data strategy, in the way that data is collected and used, placing the individual first, in accordance with European values.

Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs

Approach proposed does not provide enough clarity on innovative or advanced approaches to data responsibility (DRGs') and transparency or trust building approaches which would

have been more applicable given the use case context- there is a lack of clarity on data sovereignty beyond proposed user opt-in consent (which appears to be low level GDPR minimum requirement) but not how this will work, how it is robust, transparent and trustworthy - while there is much focus proposed on user research and engagement which is great, further combined with specialized research expertise in the dietary aspects of the proposal, there is not enough clarity on the relevant integrations with the app-solution and AI-platform interactions - with users and with data - in particular as this is high risk (sensitive) personal data.

Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact

This is an interesting research project and the proposal itself highlights some potential ideas to develop features for an eventual commercial solution - however the path to get there is considered as having both a viability and scalability risk in its current status, especially with focus on more specific and sensitive health care data and application - in the proposal miss clarity on regulatory requirements and risks in this respect.

Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation

The main structure of the proposed work plan is well defined and its in line with the specific scope of the project.

However, also in this case, relevant and critical information are missing.

The cooperation between the partners are well defined but some management roles are missing.

The budget is adequate and the allocation of the resources are in line with the proposed WPs.

Some elements of the budget has not been well defined. Consortium has expert capabilities in nutrition research and an IT development team complemented by UX expertise. But based on level of technology innovation in proposal this is not deemed advanced enough in the areas of focus for DRG4FOOD.

Appraisal Scale per Criterion

Each criterion is evaluated on a scale up to 5, detailed as follows:

- 1 / POOR** *The proposal addresses the criterion in an inadequate manner or there are significant weaknesses.*
- 2 / FAIR** *The proposal addresses the criterion broadly, but there are still several weaknesses.*
- 3 / GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion well, but improvements are necessary.*
- 4 / VERY GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion very well, but some improvements are still possible.*
- 5 / EXCELLENT** *The proposal successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the criterion. Any shortcomings are minor.*

The overall threshold for the total score is 12/20.

Evaluation Summary Report

DRG4Food Open Call #1

Proposal Title: SDM4Food

Outcome of Phase 2 – Remote Evaluation

Criterion	Average Points
Technology Excellence and Innovation <i>Assessing projects on innovation, compliance with EU food policies, advancements in data-driven technology, user collaboration, ethical standards, and open-source contributions.</i>	4.5/5
Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs <i>Evaluating projects on cybersecurity expertise, privacy standards, dataset integrity, user data control, algorithm transparency, and enabling DRG realization.</i>	4.5/5
Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact <i>Assessing business viability, scalability, and impact through unique selling points, market research, competitor analysis, financial projections, and IP rights management.</i>	3/5
Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation <i>Assessing consortium capability and qualifications, including work plan clarity, milestone definition, resource allocation, and expertise for development.</i>	3.5/5
TOTAL POINTS	15.5/20

STATUS: NOT SELECTED FOR FUNDING

Feedback and Areas for Improvement

Technology Excellence and Innovation

The proposal demonstrates strong alignment with DRG4Food, highlighting digital responsibility, citizen rights, and the development of enablers for the toolbox. It's well-linked to the "food tracing" use case, showing clear innovation potential and contributions to both the technology landscape and Open Source communities. However, a minor area for improvement is the need for a clearer strategy on integrating additional partners to broaden the project's scope and impact. This suggests the proposal would benefit from outlining methods for expanding its consortium to include further expertise and resources.

Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs

The proposal effectively covers all Digital Responsibility Goals (DRGs), positioning ethics and DRGs as unique selling points and distinguishing features. However, it could be enhanced by adding specificity on the implementation of DRGs, detailing the exact measures planned to realize these goals within the project's framework. This suggests a need for a more explicit action plan to operationalize DRGs, ensuring their successful integration and impact.

Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact

The proposal effectively outlines its Unique Selling Points (USPs), identifies professional users for its pre-market technology, projects revenue streams with an acknowledgment of the need for deeper analysis, and establishes connections with other projects and communities. However, it requires further development in exploring scalability and business value, a challenge not uncommon for technologies still approaching market readiness. This

feedback highlights the necessity for a more detailed exploration of how the technology can grow and capture value in the broader market context.

Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation

The proposal showcases a strong consortium with diverse qualifications and expertise, alongside a high-level risk assessment and a clear outline of project plans and resources. However, it lacks detail on the consortium's specific expertise in the food sector, which is crucial for the project's success. Addressing this gap by highlighting the food-related qualifications and experiences within the team would strengthen the proposal, ensuring a comprehensive approach to the project's challenges and objectives.

Appraisal Scale per Criterion

Each criterion is evaluated on a scale up to 5, detailed as follows:

- 1 / POOR** *The proposal addresses the criterion in an inadequate manner or there are significant weaknesses.*
- 2 / FAIR** *The proposal addresses the criterion broadly, but there are still several weaknesses.*
- 3 / GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion well, but improvements are necessary.*
- 4 / VERY GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion very well, but some improvements are still possible.*
- 5 / EXCELLENT** *The proposal successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the criterion. Any shortcomings are minor.*

The overall threshold for the total score is 12/20.

Evaluation Summary Report

DRG4Food Open Call #1

Proposal Title: SPECTROSCOP

Outcome of Phase 2 – Remote Evaluation

Criterion	Average Points
Technology Excellence and Innovation <i>Assessing projects on innovation, compliance with EU food policies, advancements in data-driven technology, user collaboration, ethical standards, and open-source contributions.</i>	3.5/5
Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs <i>Evaluating projects on cybersecurity expertise, privacy standards, dataset integrity, user data control, algorithm transparency, and enabling DRG realization.</i>	3.5/5
Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact <i>Assessing business viability, scalability, and impact through unique selling points, market research, competitor analysis, financial projections, and IP rights management.</i>	3/5
Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation <i>Assessing consortium capability and qualifications, including work plan clarity, milestone definition, resource allocation, and expertise for development.</i>	2.5/5
TOTAL POINTS	12.5/20

STATUS: NOT SELECTED FOR FUNDING

Feedback and Areas for Improvement

Technology Excellence and Innovation

The proposal is not fully aligned with DRG4Food challenges, it does not sufficiently address emphasizing trust, citizen engagement, nor user sovereignty. This is an important shortcoming.

The proposed technological approach is sound, as it aims at certifying the quality of the olive oil by a series of spectroscopy-based sensors connected by an IoT platform, using AI-based algorithms, together with blockchain. However, the progress beyond the state of the art is not sufficiently provided.

The objectives are overall clear. The objectives are very pertinent to the call and aligned with all Digital Responsibility Goals.

The proposed advancement of the Technology Readiness Level (TRL) is very ambitious. However, timing for market introduction is not sufficiently provided.

The end-users are very well defined. However, their engagement and involvement in co-designing is not sufficiently proposed. This is an important shortcoming

The ethical and legal considerations relevant to the project are not sufficiently addressed. This is a shortcoming.

Open source contributions and willingness to contribute to the DRG4Food toolbox are not convincingly provided. This is an important shortcoming.

Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs

The expertise of the team expertise in secure software design and cybersecurity is appropriate.

Cybersecurity threats are very credibly identified in the proposal, and appropriate mitigation strategy is proposed.

The proposed approach to privacy, including handing personal data, is excellent.

The proposed strategies for ensuring dataset integrity are overall credible. However, the mitigation of potential biases is not fully addressed.

User control over data and establishment of transparency measures are appropriate.

Mitigation of algorithmic bias is sufficiently addressed.

The potential of the proposal to realize DRG criteria are very well addressed. The proposed project has the potential to realize several DRG criteria. This is a strength of the proposal.

Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact

Unique Selling Points (USPs) are not sufficiently identified, the alignment of the proposed solution with user needs are not properly demonstrated. This is a weakness.

The market analysis is not sufficiently elaborated, for example competitor analysis is not sufficiently presented.

The business model is only superficially provided, for example financial projections, and strategy for scaling are not sufficiently presented. This is an important shortcoming.

IPR management is not sufficiently addressed. Individual exploitation strategies for partners are not sufficiently provided. These are important shortcomings.

Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation

The work plan is only broadly described. Milestones and deliverables are not sufficiently provided. These are important shortcomings.

Procedures for risk assessment and the strategies for risk mitigation are overall appropriate.

Human and financial resources are credibly allocated and properly justified. The consortium is appropriate and includes all necessary expertise to execute the project.

Appraisal Scale per Criterion

Each criterion is evaluated on a scale up to 5, detailed as follows:

- 1 / POOR** *The proposal addresses the criterion in an inadequate manner or there are significant weaknesses.*
- 2 / FAIR** *The proposal addresses the criterion broadly, but there are still several weaknesses.*
- 3 / GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion well, but improvements are necessary.*
- 4 / VERY GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion very well, but some improvements are still possible.*
- 5 / EXCELLENT** *The proposal successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the criterion. Any shortcomings are minor.*

The overall threshold for the total score is 12/20.

Evaluation Summary Report

DRG4Food Open Call #1

Proposal Title: SPMS

Outcome of Phase 2 – Remote Evaluation

Criterion	Average Points
Technology Excellence and Innovation <i>Assessing projects on innovation, compliance with EU food policies, advancements in data-driven technology, user collaboration, ethical standards, and open-source contributions.</i>	3/5
Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs <i>Evaluating projects on cybersecurity expertise, privacy standards, dataset integrity, user data control, algorithm transparency, and enabling DRG realization.</i>	3/5
Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact <i>Assessing business viability, scalability, and impact through unique selling points, market research, competitor analysis, financial projections, and IP rights management.</i>	2.5/5
Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation <i>Assessing consortium capability and qualifications, including work plan clarity, milestone definition, resource allocation, and expertise for development.</i>	3/5
TOTAL POINTS	11.5/20

STATUS: NOT SELECTED FOR FUNDING

Feedback and Areas for Improvement

Technology Excellence and Innovation

The SPMS proposal demonstrates alignment with DRG4Food challenges by focusing on environmentally friendly and humane pest control solutions, which could potentially engage citizens and respect user sovereignty by avoiding harmful chemicals. The technology presented is innovative, especially with its smart multi-trap system that can catch multiple pests simultaneously and operates with a long battery life, ensuring constant monitoring and immediate problem notification. The proposal outlines a clear and human-centered project objective, aiming to improve the quality of food preservation while ensuring compliance with sanitary standards. The proposal could benefit from explanation of how it advances over current pest control technologies as well as a stronger, more technical overview of the solution. While the proposal mentions user engagement, it lacks a strategy for involving citizens in the co-design and testing phases, which is crucial for aligning with DRG4Food's emphasis on citizen engagement.

Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs

The team composition is robust, with ten specialists, including six programmers and engineers with experience in software and hardware solutions, which indicates a strong foundation for addressing cybersecurity and data handling practices. The proposal outlines a commitment to data privacy and security, including the use of HTTPS protocols and Amazon-hosted servers for data protection. It also emphasizes user-friendly data handling and privacy by default, ensuring a secure and transparent approach to personal data processing. While the team's expertise is highlighted, there's limited detail on specific cybersecurity measures and strategies for threat mitigation beyond the use of secure

protocols and general testing practices. The proposal could benefit from a more detailed explanation of how it will ensure dataset integrity and mitigate potential biases, particularly in the context of pest detection and environmental monitoring data.

Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact

The proposal identifies its unique selling points (USPs) highlighting features such as smart traps equipped with sensors, cloud-based analytics, and an intuitive CRM system. These USPs align well with user needs for efficient and humane pest control solutions, however as other competitors are not outlined, it is unclear their state of the art. The inclusion of financial projections and scalability strategies are performed, however, with the lack of data on the market, competitors, and user interaction, they serve as weak hypothesis. While the proposal outlines financial projections, it could provide more detailed information on revenue streams, cost structures, and potential risks. Additionally, the scalability strategy could benefit from more explicit plans for expanding into new markets or diversifying product offerings. The approach to IPR management and result exploitation is mentioned briefly, but it lacks depth. There is limited information on how intellectual property rights will be protected, commercialized, or leveraged to maximize the impact of the project outcomes.

Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation

The proposal demonstrates clarity and feasibility in the work plan by outlining a structured project development process, including roles and responsibilities within the team. While the work plan appears clear and feasible, more detailed information on specific tasks, timelines, and dependencies would enhance understanding and ensure effective project management. The definition of milestones and deliverables could be further refined to include specific measurable outcomes and success criteria, facilitating progress tracking and evaluation.

Appraisal Scale per Criterion

Each criterion is evaluated on a scale up to 5, detailed as follows:

- 1 / POOR** *The proposal addresses the criterion in an inadequate manner or there are significant weaknesses.*
- 2 / FAIR** *The proposal addresses the criterion broadly, but there are still several weaknesses.*
- 3 / GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion well, but improvements are necessary.*
- 4 / VERY GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion very well, but some improvements are still possible.*
- 5 / EXCELLENT** *The proposal successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the criterion. Any shortcomings are minor.*

The overall threshold for the total score is 12/20.

Evaluation Summary Report

DRG4Food Open Call #1

Proposal Title: SuslMeal

Outcome of Phase 2 – Remote Evaluation

Criterion	Average Points
Technology Excellence and Innovation <i>Assessing projects on innovation, compliance with EU food policies, advancements in data-driven technology, user collaboration, ethical standards, and open-source contributions.</i>	2.5/5
Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs <i>Evaluating projects on cybersecurity expertise, privacy standards, dataset integrity, user data control, algorithm transparency, and enabling DRG realization.</i>	3/5
Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact <i>Assessing business viability, scalability, and impact through unique selling points, market research, competitor analysis, financial projections, and IP rights management.</i>	2.5/5
Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation <i>Assessing consortium capability and qualifications, including work plan clarity, milestone definition, resource allocation, and expertise for development.</i>	3.5/5
TOTAL POINTS	11.5/20

STATUS: NOT SELECTED FOR FUNDING

Feedback and Areas for Improvement

Technology Excellence and Innovation

The proposal requires clearer articulation of its alignment with DRG4Food, especially concerning digital responsibility and citizen rights. Its innovation potential, impact on the technology landscape, and contributions to open-source development are also areas needing more detailed description and clarification to fully understand the proposal's value and distinctiveness within the context of digital advancements and community contributions.

Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs

The proposal showcases a strong emphasis on cybersecurity and GDPR compliance, positioning these elements as central strengths. However, it remains vague on the specifics of exceeding basic compliance requirements. The details of any advanced or innovative cybersecurity measures, strategies for surpassing GDPR standards, and the proactive safeguarding of citizen rights are not sufficiently outlined. This feedback indicates a need for elaboration on how the proposal plans to extend beyond standard compliance measures to offer enhanced security and privacy protections.

Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact

The proposal highlights a market rationale but lacks clarity on how it differentiates from traditional proprietary technology approaches, leaving the business outlook and overall benefit ambiguous. It presents more as a compilation of ideas rather than a cohesive strategy or concrete plan, with unique selling points (USPs) not distinctly articulated. This critique suggests a need for a more developed business model that clearly outlines the proposal's

market positioning, advantages over existing solutions, and a well-defined plan to realize its objectives.

Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation

The proposal effectively showcases the consortium's capabilities, qualifications, and expertise. However, it presents the project plan and resource needs at a very high level, without detailed risk assessment and mitigation strategies. Additionally, it lacks a thorough explanation of the consortium's expertise in the food sector, which is critical for the project's success. This feedback suggests a need for more detailed planning, explicit risk management approaches, and a clearer articulation of food-related knowledge within the team.

Appraisal Scale per Criterion

Each criterion is evaluated on a scale up to 5, detailed as follows:

- 1 / POOR** *The proposal addresses the criterion in an inadequate manner or there are significant weaknesses.*
- 2 / FAIR** *The proposal addresses the criterion broadly, but there are still several weaknesses.*
- 3 / GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion well, but improvements are necessary.*
- 4 / VERY GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion very well, but some improvements are still possible.*
- 5 / EXCELLENT** *The proposal successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the criterion. Any shortcomings are minor.*

The overall threshold for the total score is 12/20.

Evaluation Summary Report

DRG4Food Open Call #1

Proposal Title: SUSTAINCHAIN

Outcome of Phase 2 – Remote Evaluation

Criterion	Average Points
Technology Excellence and Innovation <i>Assessing projects on innovation, compliance with EU food policies, advancements in data-driven technology, user collaboration, ethical standards, and open-source contributions.</i>	3/5
Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs <i>Evaluating projects on cybersecurity expertise, privacy standards, dataset integrity, user data control, algorithm transparency, and enabling DRG realization.</i>	2.5/5
Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact <i>Assessing business viability, scalability, and impact through unique selling points, market research, competitor analysis, financial projections, and IP rights management.</i>	4/5
Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation <i>Assessing consortium capability and qualifications, including work plan clarity, milestone definition, resource allocation, and expertise for development.</i>	4/5
TOTAL POINTS	13.5/20

STATUS: NOT SELECTED FOR FUNDING

Feedback and Areas for Improvement

Technology Excellence and Innovation

While the concept is described with reasonably clarity, crucially it partially fails to connect with DRG4FOODs challenges and mission. This is because the proposal is mainly geared towards serving the peculiar regional cheese economy without clear benefits to consumers beyond an unspecified fraud risk and provision of information via QR code. The innovative character is not able to outweigh this fact either. Given advanced TRL of some components and the clear plan of implementation for the development of the proposed solution the TRL plan seems feasible.

The proposal provides limited measures for user engagement.

Open-source contributions are addressed, however, it remains a bit vague how and what the proposal will provide to the DRG4FOOD toolbox.

Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs

As the proposal has little relevance or touchpoints with consumers the answers to relevant digital responsibility criteria partially miss the target.

In general, the proposal has little relevance for enabling the DRGs.

Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact

The consortium has ample experience in the market that the proposal caters to and sufficiently explains viability.

The USP beyond the regional cheese market, however, remains vague and a competitor analysis remains underdeveloped.

IPR management and exploitation are well addressed.

Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation

The workplan is clear and feasible. Given the large number of personnel involved it remains unclear how PMs are distributed and calculated. The proposal sets out a comprehensible roadmap and timeline for deliverables. The consortium partners are qualified and their fields of expertise provide for useful synergies. In terms of risk management, a discussion is provided.

Appraisal Scale per Criterion

Each criterion is evaluated on a scale up to 5, detailed as follows:

- 1 / POOR** *The proposal addresses the criterion in an inadequate manner or there are significant weaknesses.*
- 2 / FAIR** *The proposal addresses the criterion broadly, but there are still several weaknesses.*
- 3 / GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion well, but improvements are necessary.*
- 4 / VERY GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion very well, but some improvements are still possible.*
- 5 / EXCELLENT** *The proposal successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the criterion. Any shortcomings are minor.*

The overall threshold for the total score is 12/20.

Evaluation Summary Report

DRG4Food Open Call #1

Proposal Title: T3FC

Outcome of Phase 2 – Remote Evaluation

Criterion	Average Points
Technology Excellence and Innovation <i>Assessing projects on innovation, compliance with EU food policies, advancements in data-driven technology, user collaboration, ethical standards, and open-source contributions.</i>	3.5/5
Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs <i>Evaluating projects on cybersecurity expertise, privacy standards, dataset integrity, user data control, algorithm transparency, and enabling DRG realization.</i>	4/5
Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact <i>Assessing business viability, scalability, and impact through unique selling points, market research, competitor analysis, financial projections, and IP rights management.</i>	3/5
Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation <i>Assessing consortium capability and qualifications, including work plan clarity, milestone definition, resource allocation, and expertise for development.</i>	4/5
TOTAL POINTS	14.5/20

STATUS: NOT SELECTED FOR FUNDING

Feedback and Areas for Improvement

Technology Excellence and Innovation

The proposal is well-aligned with the DRG4Food challenge of enhancing supply chain transparency, especially in food tracking, and proposes a technology approach mindful of suppliers' low tolerance for change, alongside a focus on standardization. However, it lacks a clear connection to citizen rights and digital responsibility, and does not address its approach to open source contributions and community engagement, areas critical for fostering broader adoption and impact within the digital and food sectors.

Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs

The proposal effectively addresses Digital Responsibility Goals (DRGs), with a notable emphasis on cybersecurity. However, it lacks a detailed explanation of how it advances our understanding and implementation of digital responsibility principles. Additionally, the approach to privacy is described as not being robust, indicating a need for strengthening this aspect to ensure comprehensive digital responsibility and user data protection.

Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact

The proposal provides a general overview of supply chain tracking logic but falls short in several key areas: the market context is not comprehensively explained, unique selling points (USPs) are not identified, European exposure is limited primarily to Italy, and commercialization and development (C&D) activities are not thoroughly outlined. This feedback suggests a need for a clearer market analysis, definition of USPs, broader European integration, and a detailed description of C&D strategies to enhance the proposal's comprehensiveness and appeal.

Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation

The proposal effectively outlines the consortium's capabilities, qualifications, and a well-considered resource allocation. However, it lacks a detailed risk assessment and mitigation strategy, and the resource usage is indicated to be at its maximum potential. This suggests a need for a more comprehensive risk management plan and a review of resource utilization to ensure project efficiency and sustainability.

Appraisal Scale per Criterion

Each criterion is evaluated on a scale up to 5, detailed as follows:

- 1 / POOR** *The proposal addresses the criterion in an inadequate manner or there are significant weaknesses.*
- 2 / FAIR** *The proposal addresses the criterion broadly, but there are still several weaknesses.*
- 3 / GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion well, but improvements are necessary.*
- 4 / VERY GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion very well, but some improvements are still possible.*
- 5 / EXCELLENT** *The proposal successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the criterion. Any shortcomings are minor.*

The overall threshold for the total score is 12/20.

Evaluation Summary Report

DRG4Food Open Call #1

Proposal Title: TeMePe

Outcome of Phase 2 – Remote Evaluation

Criterion	Average Points
Technology Excellence and Innovation <i>Assessing projects on innovation, compliance with EU food policies, advancements in data-driven technology, user collaboration, ethical standards, and open-source contributions.</i>	2/5
Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs <i>Evaluating projects on cybersecurity expertise, privacy standards, dataset integrity, user data control, algorithm transparency, and enabling DRG realization.</i>	1.5/5
Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact <i>Assessing business viability, scalability, and impact through unique selling points, market research, competitor analysis, financial projections, and IP rights management.</i>	2/5
Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation <i>Assessing consortium capability and qualifications, including work plan clarity, milestone definition, resource allocation, and expertise for development.</i>	2/5
TOTAL POINTS	7.5/20

STATUS: NOT SELECTED FOR FUNDING

Feedback and Areas for Improvement

Technology Excellence and Innovation

The project presents a novel approach to addressing malnutrition in Rwanda through a combination of telenutrition, melatonin supplementation, and public enlightenment. The proposal outlines the development of a telenutrition platform, which is an innovative solution considering the Rwandan context and the challenges in accessing pediatric and nutritional services in rural areas. The project aims to leverage local resources (coffee-derived melatonin), which shows an innovative approach to utilizing Rwanda's agricultural products for health benefits. The technical infrastructure for the proposed solutions, particularly the telenutrition platform, appears to be at a conceptual stage with limited details on the technological specifics, which may question the advancement over the current state of the art. The proposal does not provide a detailed competitor analysis, which is crucial for understanding the project's unique selling points and its position in the market. The extent and methods of user engagement in the co-design and testing phases are not clearly articulated, which is vital for ensuring the solutions are user-centered and meet the actual needs of the target population. The proposal does not explicitly mention the team's plan or willingness to contribute to the DRG4Food toolbox with open-source solutions. This aspect is important for the broader applicability and accessibility of the project's outputs. The proposal sets clear and ambitious goals but falls short in demonstrating alignment with DRG4Food, emphasizing the role of digital technologies, and detailing its contributions to the technology landscape and open-source community.

This feedback suggests a need for clearer articulation of how the project's objectives and technologies align with Digital Responsibility Goals, a deeper focus on the impact of digital

technologies within the project's scope, and more transparency regarding contributions to both the technology field and open-source initiatives.

Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs

The proposal mentions data policy, data collection, user control, algorithmic biases in a very basic way without any specifics. The expertise of the team in cybersecurity is not explicitly mentioned, making it difficult to assess their capability in secure software design and cybersecurity. While some strategies for dataset integrity and bias mitigation are outlined, there could be more detail on the specific cybersecurity threats identified and the comprehensive strategies for their mitigation. There is a lack of detail on how the project will ensure the realisation of DRGs, particularly in terms of facilitating user control over data and establishing transparency measures beyond the healthcare provider level.

Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact

The project presents a pioneering approach by establishing a country-wide telenutrition platform in Rwanda, which is a significant USP. It's also the first to explore the use of melatonin derived from Rwandan coffee to combat malnutrition, aligning with user needs and value proposition. It demonstrates potential for scalability beyond Rwanda, particularly with the East African regional integration, suggesting a strong commercialization strategy. The alignment with SDGs and national agendas emphasizes the project's broader impact and viability. The proposal could provide more details on market analysis, including a competitor analysis, to strengthen its market fitness assessment. The commercialization strategy and business value could be further detailed, particularly in terms of financial projections and market entry strategy. While the project mentions the use of Rwandan coffee for melatonin production, the specifics of IPR management and result exploitation are not extensively detailed.

Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation

The consortium consists of experts with diverse qualifications, including physiology, nutrition, pharmaceuticals, health informatics, and more, ensuring a multidisciplinary approach to the project. The proposal outlines a set of work packages that cover a wide range of activities from the development of a telenutrition platform to community outreach programs and the scientific exploration of melatonin from Rwandan coffee. However, the project does not quantify any KPIs, determine the timeline of activities, include management or dissemination and exploitation work packages. Cost distributions are unusual, where Other Direct costs dominate with over 60% of the budget.

Appraisal Scale per Criterion

Each criterion is evaluated on a scale up to 5, detailed as follows:

- 1 / POOR** *The proposal addresses the criterion in an inadequate manner or there are significant weaknesses.*
- 2 / FAIR** *The proposal addresses the criterion broadly, but there are still several weaknesses.*
- 3 / GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion well, but improvements are necessary.*
- 4 / VERY GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion very well, but some improvements are still possible.*
- 5 / EXCELLENT** *The proposal successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the criterion. Any shortcomings are minor.*

The overall threshold for the total score is 12/20.

Evaluation Summary Report

DRG4Food Open Call #1

Proposal Title: Trace4Food

Outcome of Phase 2 – Remote Evaluation

Criterion	Average Points
Technology Excellence and Innovation <i>Assessing projects on innovation, compliance with EU food policies, advancements in data-driven technology, user collaboration, ethical standards, and open-source contributions.</i>	4/5
Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs <i>Evaluating projects on cybersecurity expertise, privacy standards, dataset integrity, user data control, algorithm transparency, and enabling DRG realization.</i>	4/5
Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact <i>Assessing business viability, scalability, and impact through unique selling points, market research, competitor analysis, financial projections, and IP rights management.</i>	4/5
Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation <i>Assessing consortium capability and qualifications, including work plan clarity, milestone definition, resource allocation, and expertise for development.</i>	3.5/5
TOTAL POINTS	15.5/20

STATUS: NOT SELECTED FOR FUNDING

Feedback and Areas for Improvement

Technology Excellence and Innovation

The proposal is fully aligned with DRG4Food challenges. The objectives are clear. While the proposal details the technological approach and its relevance, there is room to more explicitly compare the technology against the current state of the art. Moreover, explaining how these technologies innovatively track food digitally could enhance understanding of the project's uniqueness. End-user engagement is well planned in beta testing, feed-back loops are proposed for end user involvement in co-designing, which is appropriate. Open source contribution is credibly committed.

Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs

The expertise of the team expertise in secure software design and cybersecurity is excellent. Cybersecurity threats are briefly identified in the proposal, and some appropriate mitigation measures are proposed. The proposed approach for privacy is credible, including how personal data is handled securely and transparently. The proposed strategies for ensuring dataset integrity by the use of using the BBS+ signing algorithm is credible. The user control over data and establishment of transparency measures are properly addressed. Mitigation of algorithmic bias is briefly addressed. The proposal has the potential to realize several DRG criteria.

Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact

The Unique Selling Points (USPs) presented are acknowledged as credible, though they are outlined at a broad level. The project effectively utilizes the Synelaxis IoT platform as a foundation, yet the analysis of competitive landscapes, such as benchmarks against similar market solutions, could be more comprehensive. While the proposed business model is

convincingly laid out, a deeper dive into financial forecasts and specific Key Performance Indicators, including strategies to achieve a customer base of 10,000 at the free tier and over 200 paying customers for €40,000 in revenue, would enrich the proposal. Clarifying the target customer profiles and engagement strategies could provide additional insight. The exploitation strategies outlined by individual partners are notably well-defined and articulated.

Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation

The work plan is clearly laid out and deemed feasible, with well-defined deliverables and outputs accompanied by appropriate measures. However, the proposal could benefit from a more thorough presentation of risk assessment procedures and detailed strategies for mitigating potential risks, which is currently a notable oversight. The consortium is well-composed, bringing together all necessary expertise to successfully carry out the project.

Appraisal Scale per Criterion

Each criterion is evaluated on a scale up to 5, detailed as follows:

- 1 / POOR** *The proposal addresses the criterion in an inadequate manner or there are significant weaknesses.*
- 2 / FAIR** *The proposal addresses the criterion broadly, but there are still several weaknesses.*
- 3 / GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion well, but improvements are necessary.*
- 4 / VERY GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion very well, but some improvements are still possible.*
- 5 / EXCELLENT** *The proposal successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the criterion. Any shortcomings are minor.*

The overall threshold for the total score is 12/20.

Evaluation Summary Report

DRG4Food Open Call #1

Proposal Title: Trace4Honey

Outcome of Phase 2 – Remote Evaluation

Criterion	Average Points
Technology Excellence and Innovation <i>Assessing projects on innovation, compliance with EU food policies, advancements in data-driven technology, user collaboration, ethical standards, and open-source contributions.</i>	4/5
Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs <i>Evaluating projects on cybersecurity expertise, privacy standards, dataset integrity, user data control, algorithm transparency, and enabling DRG realization.</i>	3.5/5
Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact <i>Assessing business viability, scalability, and impact through unique selling points, market research, competitor analysis, financial projections, and IP rights management.</i>	4/5
Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation <i>Assessing consortium capability and qualifications, including work plan clarity, milestone definition, resource allocation, and expertise for development.</i>	4.5/5
TOTAL POINTS	16/20

STATUS: NOT SELECTED FOR FUNDING

Feedback and Areas for Improvement

Technology Excellence and Innovation

- The proposal elaborates well how the proposal aligns with the specific challenges of DRG4FOOD.
- There is a detailed outline of the proposals' technological approach. Overall, the technological excellence of the proposal is more pronounced than the innovative character (except for the computer vision element that should help testing authenticity of honey, but which is not described in detail).
- Given the consortium's prior work on a similar system and the clear plan of implementation for the development of the proposed solution the TRL plan seems feasible.
- The proposal provides some measures for user engagement and co-design. Ethical, legal/policy considerations are addressed.
- Open-source contributions are not addressed.

Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs

- The proposal provides concise answers to all relevant criteria and describes some basic measures on how digital responsibility will be implemented, focusing on the verifiability of said implementation.

Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact

- USPs of the proposal are debatable, as the overall proposal's novelty is limited. However, the advanced and professional approach to an established idea can be seen as a USP in itself.

- Further, the computer vision element could boost the innovativeness of the solution and give it a strong position in the market.
- The market analysis and viability is well-founded and the elaboration of the business model is well done. Competitor research is, however, lacking.
- IPR management is not detailed and exploitation strategy is sufficiently discussed.

Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation

- The workplan is clear, feasible and cost-efficient.
- The proposal very transparently sets out a comprehensible roadmap and timeline for deliverables.
- The consortium partners are qualified and their fields of expertise provide for useful synergies.
- In terms of risk management, a comprehensive discussion is provided.

Appraisal Scale per Criterion

Each criterion is evaluated on a scale up to 5, detailed as follows:

- 1 / POOR** *The proposal addresses the criterion in an inadequate manner or there are significant weaknesses.*
- 2 / FAIR** *The proposal addresses the criterion broadly, but there are still several weaknesses.*
- 3 / GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion well, but improvements are necessary.*
- 4 / VERY GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion very well, but some improvements are still possible.*
- 5 / EXCELLENT** *The proposal successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the criterion. Any shortcomings are minor.*

The overall threshold for the total score is 12/20.

Evaluation Summary Report

DRG4Food Open Call #1

Proposal Title: TraceWell

Outcome of Phase 2 – Remote Evaluation

Criterion	Average Points
Technology Excellence and Innovation <i>Assessing projects on innovation, compliance with EU food policies, advancements in data-driven technology, user collaboration, ethical standards, and open-source contributions.</i>	3.5/5
Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs <i>Evaluating projects on cybersecurity expertise, privacy standards, dataset integrity, user data control, algorithm transparency, and enabling DRG realization.</i>	3.5/5
Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact <i>Assessing business viability, scalability, and impact through unique selling points, market research, competitor analysis, financial projections, and IP rights management.</i>	3.5/5
Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation <i>Assessing consortium capability and qualifications, including work plan clarity, milestone definition, resource allocation, and expertise for development.</i>	3.5/5
TOTAL POINTS	14/20

STATUS: NOT SELECTED FOR FUNDING

Feedback and Areas for Improvement

Technology Excellence and Innovation

- The proposal provides an outline of how a great variety of technological state-of-the-art elements will be put together to achieve their proposed solution; the proposal elaborates plausibly why their solution aligns with DRG4FOOD's challenges. However, the proposal remains rather vague on how rather broad technological fields such as blockchain, AI, satellite imagery, computer vision etc. more concrete come together in the proposed solution.
- Further, the proposal lays a great focus on consultations with stakeholders, however, it is a bit doubtful if the ambitions are realistic given the time and resources of the project.
- The proposal commits to offer the PoL backbone in the DRG4FOOD toolbox.

Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs

- The proposal answers to all criteria and proposes plausible arguments how DRGs will be enabled. However, some of the answers do not go into any detail on how the proposed outcomes will be achieved. E.g.: "Data Transferability and Protection: TraceWell will define mechanisms for data transferability between parties, ensuring balanced cooperation and protection of non-personal data, which is crucial for maintaining data fairness."

Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact

- The proposed USPs do not seem to be supported by a lot of facts and research. The business viability and scalability seem credible as it relies to on the extensive network of project partner CIA. However, what remains a bit unclear is how

demand will be created, e.g. through reduction of fraud which turns into X more value.

Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation

- Given the comprehensive functionalities of the solution (see 4.1.1. of the proposal) the proposal seems rather ambitious given time and resources. A slimming down of functionalities would have positively impacted feasibility.
- Risk assessment and mitigation is basic.
- Regarding the Consortium expertise and synergies, the participants are expertly qualified and well suited for delivering proposed solution.

Appraisal Scale per Criterion

Each criterion is evaluated on a scale up to 5, detailed as follows:

- 1 / POOR** *The proposal addresses the criterion in an inadequate manner or there are significant weaknesses.*
- 2 / FAIR** *The proposal addresses the criterion broadly, but there are still several weaknesses.*
- 3 / GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion well, but improvements are necessary.*
- 4 / VERY GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion very well, but some improvements are still possible.*
- 5 / EXCELLENT** *The proposal successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the criterion. Any shortcomings are minor.*

The overall threshold for the total score is 12/20.

Evaluation Summary Report

DRG4Food Open Call #1

Proposal Title: UFP

Outcome of Phase 2 – Remote Evaluation

Criterion	Average Points
Technology Excellence and Innovation <i>Assessing projects on innovation, compliance with EU food policies, advancements in data-driven technology, user collaboration, ethical standards, and open-source contributions.</i>	2/5
Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs <i>Evaluating projects on cybersecurity expertise, privacy standards, dataset integrity, user data control, algorithm transparency, and enabling DRG realization.</i>	3/5
Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact <i>Assessing business viability, scalability, and impact through unique selling points, market research, competitor analysis, financial projections, and IP rights management.</i>	2/5
Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation <i>Assessing consortium capability and qualifications, including work plan clarity, milestone definition, resource allocation, and expertise for development.</i>	3/5
TOTAL POINTS	10/20

STATUS: NOT SELECTED FOR FUNDING

Feedback and Areas for Improvement

Technology Excellence and Innovation

The proposal is aiming to address the DRG4Food specific challenge areas on “Food Tracking”, focusing on trust, citizen engagement, and user sovereignty. However, it’s not entirely convincing on this, as it proposed a “decentralized urban food production system that empowers users to actively participate in food cultivation and distribution”. The proposal's technological approach, including the quality, relevance, and how it advances over the current state of the art, are not convincing. The novelty of the concept is not easy to verify, as the description of the solution lacks sufficient clarity. The relevance of the concept to the DRG4Food open call is not sufficiently justified. Traceability is mentioned but the focus appears to be the urban food production. Not sufficient details are provided to be able to assess the market launch of the proposed solution as feasible. The planned engagement with end users in co-designing and testing the solution is presented at a somehow adequate level of detail. The proposal addresses ethical and legal considerations relevant to the project, at a mostly adequate way. There is no indication that the proposed project will contribute to the DRG4Food toolbox with open-source solutions.

Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs

The team’s expertise in cybersecurity is not presented in detail. The description of the identification of cybersecurity threats and the strategies for their mitigation are too generic. The proposal's approach to privacy, including how personal data is handled securely and transparently, appears to be adequate. However, it’s not clear what kind of data would be needed. The strategies for ensuring dataset integrity and mitigating potential biases presented by the proposal, appear to be adequate. A process for reviewing the clarity of

algorithmic outputs and the assessment and mitigation of algorithmic bias, is presented and appears to be adequate. The proposal adequately facilitates user control over data and establishes transparency measures. There is an indication that the proposal has the potential to realize at least one DRG but it's not clear what kind of data will be handled by the solution.

Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact

The presented USPs of the proposed solution, their alignment with user needs, and the value proposition of the solution, are not convincing. The market analysis and the competitor analysis are not sufficiently comprehensive. The clarity and credibility of the business model is not appropriate and there are no financial projections. The proposal's approach to IPR management is not presented in an appropriate level of detail.

Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation

The clarity and feasibility of the proposed work plan is not fully supported with the appropriate amount of details and the same applies to the definition and feasibility of milestones and deliverables. The procedures for risk assessment and the strategies for risk mitigation have been very broadly described. The resource allocation doesn't appear to be appropriate, as the consortium asks 112000 for 1,8PM. The strength of collaboration cannot be judged with the current level of information. The competencies of the specific team members appear to be adequate, but more information would be needed. Gender balance is achieved.

Appraisal Scale per Criterion

Each criterion is evaluated on a scale up to 5, detailed as follows:

- 1 / POOR** *The proposal addresses the criterion in an inadequate manner or there are significant weaknesses.*
- 2 / FAIR** *The proposal addresses the criterion broadly, but there are still several weaknesses.*
- 3 / GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion well, but improvements are necessary.*
- 4 / VERY GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion very well, but some improvements are still possible.*
- 5 / EXCELLENT** *The proposal successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the criterion. Any shortcomings are minor.*

The overall threshold for the total score is 12/20.

Evaluation Summary Report

DRG4Food Open Call #1

Proposal Title: Wild & Zilt (CSF)

Outcome of Phase 2 – Remote Evaluation

Criterion	Average Points
Technology Excellence and Innovation <i>Assessing projects on innovation, compliance with EU food policies, advancements in data-driven technology, user collaboration, ethical standards, and open-source contributions.</i>	4/5
Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs <i>Evaluating projects on cybersecurity expertise, privacy standards, dataset integrity, user data control, algorithm transparency, and enabling DRG realization.</i>	3.5/5
Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact <i>Assessing business viability, scalability, and impact through unique selling points, market research, competitor analysis, financial projections, and IP rights management.</i>	2.5/5
Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation <i>Assessing consortium capability and qualifications, including work plan clarity, milestone definition, resource allocation, and expertise for development.</i>	3/5
TOTAL POINTS	13/20

STATUS: NOT SELECTED FOR FUNDING

Feedback and Areas for Improvement

Technology Excellence and Innovation

The proposal is fully aligned with DRG4Food challenges. It addresses very well the specific challenges, for example, food tracking and human centric approach.

The proposed technological approach is very good, encompasses establishing a Community-Supported Fishery (CSF) coupled with a Blockchain-Based Traceability System.

The objectives are overall clear. However, they are not explicitly presented. The objectives are overall pertinent with the call, and aligned with Digital Responsibility Goals, for example addressing traceability goal of DRG.

However, the timeline for advancing the Technology Readiness Level (TRL) and its rationale for market introduction are not sufficiently sustained. This is an important shortcoming.

End-user engagement is well planned by the proposed pilot. Involvement of one end user in co-designing is appropriately proposed.

The ethical and legal considerations relevant to the project are only broadly addressed. Open source contribution is credibly proposed by involvement of developer community around our projects.

Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs

The proposal outlines a clear commitment to data stewardship and transparency, which aligns well with the DRGs. The detailed plan for the ethical handling of data, including the protection of personal data and the innovative use of blockchain for traceability, is good. The project team demonstrates an understanding of the importance of data integrity and the challenges of ensuring accurate and unbiased data entry. The approach to mitigating cybersecurity threats and implementing a user-friendly data rights policy is thorough.

However, there are concerns about the completeness and accuracy of the data, given the reliance on self-reporting and manual entry, which could introduce bias or inaccuracy.

Addressing these potential gaps with more robust validation and verification mechanisms would strengthen the proposal.

Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact

The market analysis and analysis of competitors within the proposal are conducted on a basic level, missing a thorough comparison with equivalent market offerings. This oversight is a notable deficiency. Although the business model is presented as viable, it requires more detailed explanation to be persuasive. The financial forecasts are compellingly shown but lack the essential substantiation to be considered dependable. Furthermore, while a strategy for scaling is proposed, it fails to convincingly demonstrate its efficacy for expanding in the market. The adaptability of the business model to various markets and regions is mentioned but not comprehensively explained. Providing further details on market analysis, how the proposal differentiates from competitors, and potential obstacles to scaling would offer a fuller understanding of the business's feasibility.

Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation

The team composition and resource allocation are strengths of the proposal. The diverse expertise and experience of the team members, particularly in blockchain technology, positions the consortium well for success. The involvement of industry leaders and the strategic partnership with academic institutions enhance the capability and credibility of the consortium. The detailed project plan, including milestones and resource allocation, is well laid out. However, the lack of clear values associated with each of the defined KPIs for assessing project success and impact may limit the possibility to monitor progress and outcomes effectively.

Appraisal Scale per Criterion

Each criterion is evaluated on a scale up to 5, detailed as follows:

- 1 / POOR** *The proposal addresses the criterion in an inadequate manner or there are significant weaknesses.*
- 2 / FAIR** *The proposal addresses the criterion broadly, but there are still several weaknesses.*
- 3 / GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion well, but improvements are necessary.*
- 4 / VERY GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion very well, but some improvements are still possible.*
- 5 / EXCELLENT** *The proposal successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the criterion. Any shortcomings are minor.*

The overall threshold for the total score is 12/20.

Evaluation Summary Report

DRG4Food Open Call #1

Proposal Title: WineDigiPass

Outcome of Phase 2 – Remote Evaluation

Criterion	Average Points
Technology Excellence and Innovation <i>Assessing projects on innovation, compliance with EU food policies, advancements in data-driven technology, user collaboration, ethical standards, and open-source contributions.</i>	2.5/5
Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs <i>Evaluating projects on cybersecurity expertise, privacy standards, dataset integrity, user data control, algorithm transparency, and enabling DRG realization.</i>	3/5
Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact <i>Assessing business viability, scalability, and impact through unique selling points, market research, competitor analysis, financial projections, and IP rights management.</i>	2.5/5
Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation <i>Assessing consortium capability and qualifications, including work plan clarity, milestone definition, resource allocation, and expertise for development.</i>	3/5
TOTAL POINTS	11/20

STATUS: NOT SELECTED FOR FUNDING

Feedback and Areas for Improvement

Technology Excellence and Innovation

The proposal is aiming to address the DRG4Food specific challenge areas on “Food Tracking” and “Consumers' Food Choices”, focusing on trust and citizen engagement. It’s not entirely clear, if user sovereignty is addressed by the proposal. The proposal's technological approach, including the quality, relevance, and how it advances over the current state of the art, are not convincing. The clarity, robustness, and innovation of the objectives, as well as the novelty of the concept are not easy to be verified, as the description lacks sufficient clarity. The same applies to its relevance to the call. Not sufficient details are provided to be able to assess the market launch of the proposed solution as feasible. The planned engagement with end users in co-designing and testing the solution is presented at a somehow adequate level of detail. The way that the proposal addresses ethical and legal considerations relevant to the project is not adequately convincing. There is no indication that the proposed project will contribute to the DRG4Food toolbox with open source solutions.

Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs

The team’s expertise in cybersecurity is not presented in detail. The description of the identification of cybersecurity threats and the strategies for their mitigation is somewhat generic. The proposal's approach to privacy appears to be adequate. However, it is mentioned that no personal would be needed. The strategies for ensuring dataset integrity and mitigating potential biases presented by the proposal, appear to be adequate. The process for reviewing the clarity of algorithmic outputs and the assessment and mitigation of algorithmic bias, is not clear enough. The proposal adequately facilitates user control over

data and establishes transparency measures. There is an indication that the proposal has the potential to realize at least one DRG.

Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact

The presented USPs of the proposed solution, their alignment with user needs, and the value proposition of the solution, are not convincing. The market analysis and the competitor analysis are not sufficiently comprehensive. The clarity and credibility of the business model is not appropriate and there are no financial projections. The proposal's approach to IPR management and the exploitation measures are not presented in an appropriate level of detail.

Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation

The clarity and feasibility of the proposed work plan is not fully supported with the appropriate amount of details and the same applies to the definition and feasibility of milestones and deliverables. There is no description of the procedures for risk assessment, the identified risks and the strategies for risk mitigation. The resource allocation appears to be appropriate. The strength of collaboration appears and the competencies of the specific team members appear to be adequate but more information would be needed. Gender balance is achieved.

Appraisal Scale per Criterion

Each criterion is evaluated on a scale up to 5, detailed as follows:

- 1 / POOR** *The proposal addresses the criterion in an inadequate manner or there are significant weaknesses.*
- 2 / FAIR** *The proposal addresses the criterion broadly, but there are still several weaknesses.*
- 3 / GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion well, but improvements are necessary.*
- 4 / VERY GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion very well, but some improvements are still possible.*
- 5 / EXCELLENT** *The proposal successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the criterion. Any shortcomings are minor.*

The overall threshold for the total score is 12/20.

Evaluation Summary Report

DRG4Food Open Call #1

Proposal Title: XAI_MicroBalancer

Outcome of Phase 2 – Remote Evaluation

Criterion	Average Points
Technology Excellence and Innovation <i>Assessing projects on innovation, compliance with EU food policies, advancements in data-driven technology, user collaboration, ethical standards, and open-source contributions.</i>	3.5/5
Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs <i>Evaluating projects on cybersecurity expertise, privacy standards, dataset integrity, user data control, algorithm transparency, and enabling DRG realization.</i>	4/5
Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact <i>Assessing business viability, scalability, and impact through unique selling points, market research, competitor analysis, financial projections, and IP rights management.</i>	3/5
Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation <i>Assessing consortium capability and qualifications, including work plan clarity, milestone definition, resource allocation, and expertise for development.</i>	2.5/5
TOTAL POINTS	13/20

STATUS: NOT SELECTED FOR FUNDING

Feedback and Areas for Improvement

Technology Excellence and Innovation

The proposal is overall aligned with DRG4Food challenges. It addresses the enhancement of consumers' food decisions to promote the growth of beneficial bacterial colonies in the intestinal microbiome.

The proposed technological approach is very good, including definition of software architecture and programming activities for developing the dietary supplement. The progress beyond the state of the art is credibly demonstrated, the main innovative element is the proposed Microbiota Simulation Engine (MSE).

The objectives are overall clear, pertinent with the call, and aligned with Digital Responsibility Goals.

However, the baseline Technology Readiness Level (TRL) and advancements are not sufficiently demonstrated. This is an important shortcoming.

End-user engagement and involvement in co-design are very well planned by the proposed Living lab activities.

The ethical and legal considerations relevant to the project are sufficiently addressed.

However, open source contribution and the willingness to contribute to the DRG4Food toolbox is not sufficiently provided, which is a shortcoming.

Data Responsibility, Transparency, Alignment with DRGs

The expertise of the team expertise in software design is appropriate. However, the expertise in cybersecurity is not sufficiently demonstrated. This is a shortcoming.

Cybersecurity threats are adequately identified in the proposal, and some appropriate mitigation measures are proposed.

The effective approach for handling privacy is sufficiently proposed.

The proposed strategy for ensuring dataset integrity is not sufficiently credible. This is an important shortcoming. User control over data and establishment of transparency measures are appropriate. Mitigation of algorithmic bias is appropriately addressed by large-scale studies collecting heterogeneous datasets to refine data processing algorithms.

The potential of the proposal to realize DRG criteria is only superficially elaborated. Nevertheless, the proposed project has the potential to realize some DRG criteria.

Business Viability, Scalability, and Impact

The USPs of the proposed solution, their alignment with user needs, and the value proposition of the solution, appear presented at an adequate level. A minor shortcoming is that part of the text is too focused on the research on the background, which makes this less clear.

The market analysis and the competitor analysis are comprehensive and multiple competitors are presented, explaining what the difference of the proposed solution is.

The business model is presented but more information is needed. There are no financial projections. This is a shortcoming.

The proposal's approach to IPR management appears to be appropriate. The exploitation strategy is not presented in sufficient detail.

Consortium Capability, Team, and Resource Allocation

The clarity and feasibility of the proposed work plan is mostly adequate and the same applies to the definition and feasibility of milestones and deliverables. Some more information would be needed. The procedures for risk assessment have not been described and there are no identified risks and strategies for risk mitigation. The resource allocation appears to be appropriate. The strength of collaboration is appropriate. However, although the individual capacities of the team members appear to be relevant, there is not enough information and there is a lack of team members with a business development background. Gender balance is achieved.

Appraisal Scale per Criterion

Each criterion is evaluated on a scale up to 5, detailed as follows:

- 1 / POOR** *The proposal addresses the criterion in an inadequate manner or there are significant weaknesses.*
- 2 / FAIR** *The proposal addresses the criterion broadly, but there are still several weaknesses.*
- 3 / GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion well, but improvements are necessary.*
- 4 / VERY GOOD** *The proposal addresses the criterion very well, but some improvements are still possible.*
- 5 / EXCELLENT** *The proposal successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the criterion. Any shortcomings are minor.*

The overall threshold for the total score is 12/20.

